

Supplementary Data Appendices for:

**Trace and critical metal behaviour
in seafloor massive sulfide
deposits: A mineralogical and
geochemical assessment**

Dissertation

zur Erlangung des Doktorgrades
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vorgelegt von

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This appendix is available online in the Zenodo scientific metadata repository (www.zenodo.org) for immediate and permanent access. Zenodo is hosted by CERN and is funded for at least the next 20 years by the European Commission via the FP7 and Horizon 2020 funded OpenAIRE project (codes 246686, 283595, 643410, 731011, 777541), CERN, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, and donations via the CERN & Society Foundation. The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013. Data files are citable by DOI.

Appendix C1 citation: 10.5281/zenodo.2550731

Appendix C1 link: [Zenodo record](#)

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 Trace element distribution and behaviour in seafloor massive sulphide deposits. Poster presented during the Marine Minerals: A New Resource for the 21st Century conference. Geological Society of London, October 2018.

Appendix A

Supplementary information for Chapter 2

Appendix A1: Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on log-transformed bulk geochemical data and LA-ICP-MS data.

- A1.1. All bulk geochemical data
- A1.2. All pyrite LA-ICP-MS data
- A1.3. All marcasite LA-ICP-MS data
- A1.4. All sphalerite LA-ICP-MS data
- A1.5. All chalcopyrite LA-ICP-MS data

Appendix A2: Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit.

Appendix A3: Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit.

Appendix A4: Calculated proportions of trace elements in each pyrite type.

Appendix A5: Box and whisker plots comparing variations in TAG pyrite LA-ICP-MS trace element concentrations from TAG sub-seafloor samples (data from Chapter 2), TAG surface pyrite samples and other MOR basalt-hosted massive sulfide deposits.

Appendix A6: Comparison of element concentrations for LA-ICP-MS standards calibrated on a) sulfide standards, and b) glass NIST standards (this study).

Appendix A7: Geochemical sections using the idealized section in Figure 2.3 for visualization of the bulk geochemical distribution of major and trace elements. Contour lines have been drawn based on bulk geochemical data from Hannington et al. (1998a), Herzig et al. (1998), Miller et al. (1998), and Petersen et al. (1998). All elements analyzed during LA-ICP-MS are illustrated, however Te and Bi were not analyzed for in the bulk geochemistry dataset. Zinc, Cu, Sb, Ag, and Au are modified from Hannington et al. (1998a) and Petersen et al. (2000).

Appendix A1.3. Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on log-transformed LA-ICP-MS data for marcasite.

No. analyses	Element	Zn	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	Au	As	Sb	Ag	Pb	Tl	Mo	Ni	W	V	Cr	Te	Sn	Cu	Co	Se	Bi
48	Zn	1																						
25	Cd	0.15	1																					
28	Mn	-0.27	-0.03	1																				
47	Ga	0.03	0.21	0.01	1																			
23	Ge	-	0.25	0.18	0.20	1																		
50	In	0.33	0.49	-0.19	0.25	-0.05	1																	
12	Au	-0.04	-0.04	-0.03	-0.06	-0.15	-0.05	1																
11	As	-0.03	-0.13	-0.08	-0.10	-0.08	-0.05	-0.16	1															
13	Sb	-0.14	-0.14	-0.21	0.15	-0.08	-	-0.11	0.11	1														
45	Ag	0.19	-0.02	-0.08	-0.02	-0.14	0.17	-0.07	0.55	0.12	0.14	1												
32	Pb	0.19	-0.02	-0.10	-0.08	-0.09	-0.06	-0.03	0.61	-	-0.02	0.90	1											
8	Tl	0.04	-0.10	-	-0.08	-0.09	-0.06	-0.03	0.61	-	-0.02	0.56	0.66	1										
21	Mo	-0.05	-0.12	-0.05	-0.08	0.05	-0.11	-0.05	0.26	0.08	0.04	0.56	0.02	-0.06	1									
10	Ni	0.14	-0.06	-0.14	-0.15	-0.11	0.06	-0.12	0.41	0.22	0.09	0.02	-0.06	-0.19	1									
5	W	0.07	0.4	-0.19	-0.08	0.14	0.07	0.17	-0.05	-0.08	-0.05	-0.05	-0.02	-0.10	-0.11	1								
29	V	0.03	0.16	-0.01	-0.05	-0.09	0.05	-0.08	0.09	0.77	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.27	-0.10	-0.03	1							
21	U	-0.06	-0.12	-0.15	0.18	-0.11	0.07	-0.10	0.27	0.79	0.07	0.14	-0.01	-0.04	0.09	-0.06	0.10	0.68						
6	Te	0.02	0.15	-0.23	0.05	-0.05	0.08	-0.13	0.22	0.27	0.05	0.11	-0.04	-0.09	0.07	0.39	-0.01	0.38	1					
50	Sn	-0.03	0.09	-0.10	-0.07	-0.13	0.15	-0.04	-0.08	-0.05	0.56	-0.13	-0.08	-0.01	0.01	-0.04	0.52	-0.07	-0.14	1				
50	Cu	0.13	0.06	-0.02	0.05	0.13	0.14	-0.11	-0.44	-0.01	0.07	-0.77	-0.86	-0.56	0.16	0.11	-0.06	-0.25	0.05	0.21	1			
36	Co	-0.14	0.05	0.38	-0.04	-	-0.05	0.19	-0.16	-0.09	0.13	-0.12	-0.11	0.02	-0.21	-0.10	0.10	0.18	-0.16	-0.01	-0.03	1		
14	Se	-0.15	-0.02	0.04	-0.02	0.07	-0.18	0.07	-0.17	-0.03	-0.16	-0.15	-0.11	0.09	-0.20	-0.14	-0.19	0.02	-0.13	-0.26	-0.04	-	1	
15	Bi	0.42	-	-0.04	0.09	0.11	0.41	-0.11	0.13	-0.12	0.02	0.35	0.10	0.01	0.12	-	-0.06	-0.11	0.18	0.04	0.12	-0.20	-0.13	1

Appendix A1.4. Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on log-transformed LA-ICP-MS data for sphalerite.

No. analyses	Element	Fe	Zn	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	Au	As	Sb	Ag	Pb	Tl	Mo	Ni	W	V	Cr	Te	Sn	Cu	Co	Se	Bi	
19	Fe	1																								
19	Zn	-0.80	1																							
19	Cd	0.14	-0.09	1																						
19	Mn	0.64	-0.68	-0.03	1																					
19	Ga	-0.31	0.34	0.56	-0.49	1																				
19	Ge	-0.54	0.46	0.23	-0.59	0.70	1																			
18	In	-0.49	0.50	0.16	-0.30	0.60	0.73	1																		
10	Au	0.06	-0.35	0.12	0.48	-0.16	0.72	0.02	1																	
15	As	-0.52	0.49	0.17	-0.51	0.31	0.76	0.46	0.14	1																
19	Sb	-0.12	0.22	0.04	0.16	-0.02	0.14	-0.01	0.42	0.29	1															
19	Ag	-0.34	0.56	-0.10	-0.38	-0.13	0.31	0.15	-0.16	0.58	0.21	1														
19	Pb	-0.14	0.09	-0.01	0.30	-0.29	0.03	-0.15	0.55	0.45	0.65	0.39	1													
16	Tl	0.15	0.11	-0.12	-0.15	-0.21	0.13	-0.11	0.03	0.29	0.31	0.47	0.25	1												
14	Mo	0.20	-	-0.02	0.48	-0.35	-0.38	0.02	0.25	-0.24	0.31	0.03	0.23	0.41	1											
4	Ni	0.26	0.04	-0.16	0.02	-0.29	-0.10	-0.03	0.04	0.07	0.15	0.23	0.03	0.83	0.67	1										
5	W	-0.40	0.31	-0.19	-0.38	0.26	0.12	-	-0.24	-0.09	-0.16	-0.20	-0.19	-0.14	-0.24	-0.17	1									
11	V	0.31	0.07	-0.22	-	-0.29	-0.19	-0.24	-0.18	-0.01	0.21	0.31	0.06	0.86	0.54	0.86	-0.16	1								
11	U	0.26	-0.21	0.12	0.44	-0.34	-0.27	-0.35	0.29	-0.13	0.21	0.05	0.46	0.47	0.52	0.32	-0.16	0.46	1							
-	Te	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
13	Sn	-	0.06	0.25	0.02	0.37	0.24	0.58	-0.18	-0.02	-0.33	-0.29	-0.38	-0.18	0.07	-0.07	0.01	-0.19	-0.04	-	1					
19	Cu	0.09	0.11	0.33	0.08	0.46	0.55	0.47	0.27	0.31	0.51	0.04	0.20	0.34	0.16	0.17	-0.14	0.14	0.23	-	0.43	1				
15	Co	0.36	-0.3	0.02	0.18	-0.06	-0.05	-0.03	-0.12	-0.18	-0.35	-0.23	-0.29	-0.10	-0.25	-0.15	-0.16	-0.07	0.12	-	0.60	0.21	1			
-	Se	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Bi	-0.29	0.26	-0.01	-0.19	-0.03	0.28	0.29	-0.06	0.29	-0.05	0.67	0.14	0.09	-0.14	-0.16	-0.16	-0.13	0.02	-	-0.13	-0.04	-0.07	-	1	

Appendix A1.5. Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on log-transformed LA-ICP-MS data for chalcopyrite.

No. analyses	Element	Zn	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	Au	As	Sb	Ag	Pb	Tl	Mo	Ni	W	V	Cr	Te	Sn	Cu	Co	Se	Bi
48	Zn	1																						
25	Cd	0.15	1																					
28	Mn	-0.27	-0.03	1																				
47	Ga	0.03	0.21	0.01	1																			
23	Ge	-	0.25	0.18	0.20	1																		
50	In	0.33	0.49	-0.19	0.25	-0.05	1																	
12	Au	-0.04	-0.04	-0.03	-0.06	-0.15	-0.05	1																
11	As	-0.03	-0.13	-0.08	-0.10	-0.08	-0.05	-0.16	1															
13	Sb	-0.14	-0.14	-0.21	0.15	-0.08	-	-0.11	0.11	1														
45	Ag	0.14	0.31	-0.21	-0.01	-0.25	0.32	-0.04	-0.04	0.07	1													
32	Pb	0.19	-0.02	-0.08	-0.02	-0.14	0.17	-0.07	0.55	0.12	0.14	1												
8	Tl	0.04	-0.10	-	-0.08	-0.09	-0.06	-0.03	0.61	-	-0.02	0.90	1											
21	Mo	-0.05	-0.12	-0.05	-0.08	0.05	-0.11	-0.05	0.26	0.08	0.04	0.56	0.66	1										
10	Ni	0.14	-0.06	-0.14	-0.15	-0.11	0.06	-0.12	0.41	0.22	0.09	0.02	-0.06	-0.19	1									
5	W	0.07	0.4	-0.19	-0.08	0.14	0.07	-0.05	-0.05	-0.08	-0.05	-0.05	-0.02	-0.10	-0.11	1								
29	V	0.03	0.16	-0.01	-0.05	-0.09	0.05	-0.08	0.09	0.77	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.27	-0.10	-0.03	1							
21	U	-0.06	-0.12	-0.15	0.18	-0.11	0.07	-0.10	0.27	0.79	0.07	0.14	-0.01	-0.04	0.09	-0.06	0.10	0.68						
6	Te	0.02	0.15	-0.23	0.05	-0.05	0.08	-0.13	0.22	0.27	0.05	0.11	-0.04	-0.09	0.07	0.39	-0.01	0.38	1					
50	Sn	-0.03	0.09	-0.10	-0.07	-0.13	0.15	-0.04	-0.08	-0.05	0.56	-0.13	-0.08	-0.01	0.01	-0.04	0.52	-0.07	-0.14	1				
50	Cu	0.13	0.06	-0.02	0.05	0.13	0.14	-0.11	-0.44	-0.01	0.07	-0.77	-0.86	-0.56	0.16	0.11	-0.06	-0.25	0.05	0.21	1			
36	Co	-0.14	0.05	0.38	-0.04	-	-0.05	0.19	-0.16	-0.09	0.13	-0.12	-0.11	0.02	-0.21	-0.10	0.10	0.18	-0.16	-0.01	-0.03	1		
14	Se	-0.15	-0.02	0.04	-0.02	0.07	-0.18	0.07	-0.17	0.03	-0.16	-0.15	-0.11	0.09	-0.20	-0.14	-0.19	0.02	-0.13	-0.26	-0.04	-	1	
15	Bi	0.42	-	-0.04	0.09	0.11	0.41	-0.11	0.13	-0.12	0.02	0.35	0.10	0.01	0.12	-	-0.06	-0.11	0.18	0.04	0.12	-0.20	-0.13	1

Appendix A1.5. Pearson correlation coefficients calculated on log-transformed data for element pairs from the TAG hydrothermal mound. A1.1) Bulk geochemical data from Fouquet et al. (1998) and Hamington et al. (1998). Number of elements (components) = 23. Superscripts indicate the method of analysis: 1) ICP-ES, 2) XRF, 3) Leco, 4) INAA, 5) ICP-MS. A1.2) LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite. Groupings of elements by pyrite type are highlighted and discussed in section 2.5.1. Number of elements = 23. A1.3) LA-ICP-MS data for marcasite. A1.4) LA-ICP-MS data for sphalerite. Number of elements = 22. A1.5) LA-ICP-MS data for chalcopyrite. Number of elements = 23. Correlations significant at the 99% confidence level are in bold and highlighted in dark gray; correlations at the 95-99% confidence level are in bold and highlighted in light gray. The significance thresholds (or critical values) are for n-2 degrees of freedom (i.e. components) and a one-tailed t-test. ‘-’ indicates no data. Number of analyses for each element are indicated in the left column.

Appendix A2. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
1	5-5	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.40	53.95	bdl	0.027	100.38
2	6-6	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.62	53.52	bdl	bdl	100.14
3	7-7	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.46	53.86	0.026	0.002	100.35
4	7-7	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.46	53.86	0.026	0.002	100.35
5	8-8	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.61	53.88	0.003	0.028	100.52
6	9-9	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.33	53.84	0.000	0.050	100.22
7	10-10	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	45.68	53.78	0.008	bdl	99.47
8	12-12	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.42	54.08	bdl	0.036	100.54
9	13-13	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	45.76	53.94	0.030	0.081	99.81
10	16-16	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.11	53.51	bdl	bdl	99.62
11	17-17	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.22	53.61	bdl	0.083	99.91
12	20-20	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.07	53.69	bdl	0.033	99.79
13	21-21	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.47	53.19	0.053	0.086	99.80
14	22-22	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.62	53.98	0.020	0.014	100.63
15	23-23	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.55	53.21	0.017	0.027	99.80
16	24-24	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.34	53.08	bdl	bdl	99.42
17	25-25	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.12	53.19	0.049	0.174	99.53
18	26-26	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.63	53.47	0.005	0.047	100.15
19	27-27	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.66	53.83	bdl	0.067	100.56
20	28-28	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.79	53.91	0.014	0.029	100.74
21	29-29	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.67	53.92	0.023	bdl	100.61
22	30-30	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.67	53.83	0.003	bdl	100.50
23	33-33	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.17	35.15	bdl	34.89	100.21
24	34-34	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.10	35.11	bdl	34.39	99.60
25	35-35	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.20	35.21	bdl	34.43	99.84
26	36-36	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.20	35.00	bdl	34.59	99.79
27	37-37	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.12	35.06	bdl	34.63	99.81
28	38-38	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.09	34.91	bdl	34.60	99.60
29	39-39	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.52	53.81	bdl	0.053	100.38
30	40-40	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.45	53.76	bdl	0.051	100.26
31	41-41	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.39	53.64	bdl	0.002	100.03
32	42-42	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.46	53.71	bdl	0.023	100.19
33	43-43	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.61	53.65	bdl	0.025	100.29
34	47-47	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.47	54.00	bdl	0.040	100.51
35	48-48	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.60	54.19	0.020	bdl	100.81
36	49-49	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.59	54.15	bdl	0.023	100.76
37	50-50	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.62	54.12	0.002	0.037	100.78
38	51-51	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.50	54.36	bdl	bdl	100.86
39	52-52	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.31	53.95	0.006	0.001	100.27
40	53-53	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.44	54.18	0.005	0.012	100.64
41	54-54	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.39	54.08	0.002	0.005	100.48
42	55-55	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.79	54.20	bdl	bdl	100.99
43	56-56	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.66	54.07	0.010	0.029	100.77
44	57-57	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.69	54.00	0.031	0.016	100.74
45	59-59	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.64	54.08	bdl	0.029	100.75
46	60-60	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.45	54.35	bdl	0.016	100.82
47	62-62	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	45.62	54.09	bdl	0.019	99.73
48	63-63	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	45.63	54.29	0.009	0.021	99.95
49	64-64	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	45.99	54.36	bdl	0.026	100.38
50	65-65	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	45.90	53.96	0.015	0.022	99.90
51	66-66	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.60	54.19	bdl	0.023	100.81
52	67-67	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.52	54.34	bdl	bdl	100.86
53	69-69	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.50	54.40	0.020	0.020	100.94
54	70-70	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.48	54.41	0.018	0.031	100.94
55	72-72	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.79	54.09	bdl	0.008	100.89
56	73-73	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.65	54.21	bdl	bdl	100.86
57	74-74	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.15	54.29	0.023	0.022	100.48
58	75-75	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.16	54.35	0.012	0.020	100.54
59	76-76	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.63	54.19	bdl	0.029	100.85
60	77-77	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.79	54.16	0.006	0.031	100.99
61	79-79	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.69	54.14	0.012	bdl	100.84
62	80-80	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.78	54.16	0.018	0.028	100.99
63	82-82	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.68	54.10	bdl	0.006	100.79
64	83-83	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.75	54.13	bdl	0.039	100.92
65	90-90	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.57	54.13	bdl	0.011	100.71
66	91-91	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.51	54.24	0.024	bdl	100.77
67	92-92	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.43	54.24	bdl	bdl	100.67
68	94-94	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.78	54.13	0.033	0.033	100.98
69	95-95	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.39	54.27	0.011	0.028	100.70
70	96-96	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.34	53.90	bdl	0.034	100.27
71	97-97	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.66	54.22	bdl	0.029	100.91
72	98-98	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.68	54.18	bdl	0.027	100.89
73	99-99	py	40.1	TAG-5	957P-9R-1-1	46.45	54.37	0.009	0.025	100.85

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
74	100-100	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.49	54.16	0.016	0.068	100.73
75	101-101	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.58	54.32	bdl	0.008	100.91
76	102-102	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.60	54.31	bdl	0.016	100.93
77	103-103	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.66	54.29	0.012	bdl	100.96
78	104-104	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.35	54.22	bdl	0.026	100.60
79	106-106	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.53	54.38	0.006	0.037	100.95
80	107-107	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.56	54.27	bdl	0.007	100.84
81	108-108	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.64	54.31	0.002	0.026	100.98
82	112-112	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.76	54.16	bdl	0.028	100.95
83	113-113	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.56	53.82	bdl	0.001	100.38
84	114-114	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.64	54.19	bdl	0.008	100.84
85	115-115	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.62	54.27	bdl	0.026	100.92
86	116-116	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.62	54.29	bdl	0.032	100.94
87	117-117	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.65	54.13	bdl	0.014	100.79
88	118-118	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.41	53.83	bdl	0.031	100.27
89	119-119	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.45	53.36	0.002	0.028	99.84
90	120-120	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.55	53.13	bdl	bdl	99.68
91	121-121	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.53	53.95	0.011	0.026	100.52
92	122-122	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.55	54.29	bdl	0.026	100.87
93	124-124	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.57	54.19	bdl	0.050	100.81
94	128-128	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	46.74	54.24	bdl	0.015	101.00
95	135-135	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.68	54.09	bdl	0.018	100.79
96	136-136	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.56	54.32	bdl	bdl	100.88
97	137-137	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.27	54.12	0.031	0.005	100.43
98	138-138	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.53	54.12	bdl	0.022	100.67
99	139-139	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.59	54.04	0.030	0.022	100.68
100	141-141	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.52	54.12	bdl	bdl	100.64
101	142-142	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.38	54.28	bdl	0.035	100.70
102	143-143	py	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	46.80	54.00	0.027	bdl	100.83
103	148-5	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.48	53.37	0.013	0.022	99.88
104	149-6	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.59	53.38	0.006	0.039	100.01
105	150-7	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.55	53.39	bdl	0.019	99.96
106	151-8	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.47	53.05	bdl	bdl	99.52
107	152-9	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.78	53.94	0.013	0.034	100.77
108	153-10	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.71	53.41	bdl	bdl	100.12
109	154-11	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.66	53.63	bdl	0.020	100.31
110	155-12	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.67	53.65	0.014	bdl	100.33
111	156-13	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.48	53.57	0.364	0.084	100.50
112	157-14	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.60	53.96	0.322	0.033	100.91
113	158-15	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.49	53.97	0.336	0.029	100.83
114	159-16	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.45	53.14	0.387	0.100	100.08
115	160-17	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.33	53.47	0.382	0.060	100.24
116	161-18	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.47	53.86	0.376	0.029	100.74
117	162-19	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.24	53.44	0.400	0.076	100.16
118	163-20	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.50	53.75	0.514	0.035	100.80
119	164-21	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.69	53.50	0.571	0.032	100.79
120	165-22	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.66	53.76	bdl	0.017	100.44
121	166-23	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.84	53.61	bdl	bdl	100.45
122	167-24	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.86	53.73	0.018	0.019	100.63
123	168-25	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.94	53.60	bdl	bdl	100.54
124	169-26	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.91	53.73	bdl	0.017	100.66
125	170-27	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.65	53.95	0.018	0.071	100.69
126	171-28	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.76	53.50	0.054	0.016	100.33
127	172-29	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.90	53.67	0.011	0.027	100.61
128	173-30	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.67	53.77	0.026	0.201	100.67
129	174-31	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.83	53.78	0.046	0.037	100.69
130	175-32	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.79	53.46	bdl	0.014	100.26
131	177-34	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.95	53.78	0.004	0.006	100.74
132	178-35	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.92	53.80	0.028	0.005	100.75
133	179-36	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.99	53.82	0.019	0.024	100.85
134	180-37	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.60	53.31	0.003	0.018	99.93
135	181-38	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.44	53.42	0.022	0.068	99.95
136	182-39	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.32	53.14	0.027	0.033	99.52
137	183-40	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.57	53.49	bdl	0.038	100.10
138	184-41	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.59	53.46	0.037	0.033	100.12
139	193-5	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.69	53.30	0.022	0.012	100.02
140	194-6	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.76	53.63	0.034	0.000	100.42
141	196-8	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.86	53.91	0.000	0.001	100.77
142	197-9	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.67	53.26	bdl	0.025	99.96
143	198-10	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.73	54.11	0.043	0.008	100.89
144	200-12	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.71	54.01	0.038	0.031	100.79
145	202-14	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.83	54.07	0.029	0.026	100.96
146	203-15	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.68	53.81	0.134	bdl	100.62

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
147	205-17	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.70	54.16	0.120	bdl	100.98
148	206-18	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.73	53.82	0.182	0.038	100.77
149	207-19	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.65	53.62	0.127	0.030	100.43
150	208-20	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.54	53.49	0.187	0.024	100.24
151	209-21	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.70	53.68	0.189	0.028	100.60
152	210-22	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.50	53.67	0.186	0.001	100.36
153	211-23	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.53	53.59	0.254	0.018	100.39
154	212-24	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.61	53.64	0.202	0.051	100.50
155	213-25	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.62	53.59	0.326	0.012	100.55
156	214-26	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.41	53.76	0.335	0.043	100.55
157	215-27	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.50	53.64	0.350	0.054	100.54
158	216-28	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.21	53.76	0.438	0.034	100.44
159	217-29	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.34	53.95	0.298	0.011	100.60
160	223-35	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.78	53.93	0.101	0.021	100.83
161	224-36	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.55	53.87	0.086	0.023	100.53
162	225-37	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.64	53.91	0.070	bdl	100.62
163	226-38	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.65	53.94	0.067	0.031	100.69
164	227-39	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.68	53.78	0.084	0.043	100.59
165	228-40	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.60	53.94	0.065	0.037	100.64
166	229-41	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.57	53.94	0.103	0.041	100.65
167	230-42	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.55	53.92	0.029	bdl	100.50
168	231-43	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.61	53.98	0.044	bdl	100.63
169	232-44	mc	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.50	53.99	0.081	0.010	100.58
170	233-45	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.77	54.13	0.015	0.006	100.92
171	234-46	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.60	54.15	0.053	0.022	100.83
172	236-48	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.68	54.09	0.055	0.009	100.83
173	237-49	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.55	53.88	0.033	0.007	100.47
174	238-50	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.44	53.97	0.507	0.015	100.93
175	239-51	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.16	53.52	0.550	0.019	100.25
176	241-53	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	45.90	53.32	0.528	0.047	99.79
177	242-54	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.57	53.91	0.278	0.080	100.84
178	245-57	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.45	54.03	0.400	0.007	100.89
179	246-58	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.40	53.90	0.528	0.001	100.83
180	247-59	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.60	54.03	0.344	bdl	100.97
181	258-70	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.51	33.80	56.37	1.31	99.99
182	260-72	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	10.57	33.99	54.66	0.90	100.12
183	261-73	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.31	33.83	55.48	1.81	99.43
184	262-74	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	7.03	33.85	57.09	1.85	99.82
185	263-75	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	7.87	34.06	58.39	0.221	100.54
186	264-76	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.87	34.03	57.70	0.080	100.68
187	265-77	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.45	33.83	57.55	0.100	99.93
188	266-78	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.90	34.01	57.51	0.094	100.51
189	267-79	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	8.25	34.15	58.10	0.085	100.58
190	268-80	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.65	53.41	0.025	bdl	100.08
191	269-81	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.79	53.44	bdl	bdl	100.23
192	270-82	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.72	53.74	bdl	0.013	100.47
193	271-83	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.62	53.33	0.027	0.033	100.01
194	272-84	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.68	53.58	bdl	0.039	100.30
195	273-85	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.72	54.12	bdl	bdl	100.84
196	274-86	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.69	54.08	0.005	0.003	100.78
197	275-87	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.75	54.09	0.014	bdl	100.85
198	276-88	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.78	54.02	0.017	0.030	100.85
199	277-89	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.77	53.92	0.044	bdl	100.73
200	278-90	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.04	52.95	0.019	0.007	99.02
201	280-92	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.31	53.41	bdl	0.014	99.73
202	281-93	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.15	53.24	0.005	0.019	99.41
203	282-94	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.33	53.44	0.033	0.021	99.82
204	283-95	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.33	53.40	0.008	0.028	99.77
205	284-96	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.27	52.98	0.000	0.054	99.30
206	285-97	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.19	53.25	bdl	0.029	99.47
207	286-98	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.14	52.85	0.069	0.028	99.09
208	287-99	py	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	46.32	53.05	bdl	0.013	99.38
209	289-2	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	53.89	bdl	0.019	100.40
210	290-3	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.55	53.99	bdl	0.031	100.57
211	291-4	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.43	53.99	0.043	0.124	100.59
212	292-5	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.66	54.18	bdl	0.017	100.86
213	293-6	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.46	54.10	bdl	0.010	100.57
214	294-7	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.55	53.86	0.000	0.027	100.44
215	295-8	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.51	53.73	bdl	0.052	100.29
216	296-9	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.52	53.83	bdl	0.153	100.50
217	297-10	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.44	53.54	bdl	0.185	100.16
218	298-11	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.59	54.14	bdl	0.205	100.93
219	299-12	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.31	53.93	0.003	0.023	100.27

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
220	300-13	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.22	54.03	0.021	0.039	100.31
221	301-14	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.29	54.01	bdl	0.048	100.35
222	302-15	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	54.31	bdl	0.017	100.82
223	303-16	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.51	54.19	0.028	0.019	100.75
224	304-17	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.43	53.76	0.017	0.051	100.26
225	305-18	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.71	54.03	0.008	0.019	100.77
226	306-19	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.77	53.98	0.017	0.028	100.80
227	307-20	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	45.91	53.67	0.008	0.406	99.99
228	308-21	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	45.91	53.73	bdl	0.607	100.25
229	309-22	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.40	53.98	bdl	0.187	100.57
230	310-23	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.73	54.02	0.013	0.194	100.96
231	311-24	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.54	53.80	bdl	0.097	100.44
232	312-25	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.48	53.79	bdl	0.125	100.39
233	313-26	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.75	54.09	bdl	0.044	100.88
234	314-27	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.56	53.95	bdl	0.019	100.53
235	315-28	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.45	53.77	bdl	0.028	100.25
236	316-29	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.59	53.90	0.002	bdl	100.49
237	317-30	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.65	53.80	bdl	0.023	100.47
238	318-31	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.62	54.05	0.019	0.014	100.70
239	319-32	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.74	54.03	bdl	0.050	100.82
240	320-33	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.76	53.87	0.007	0.018	100.65
241	321-34	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.52	53.74	0.022	0.003	100.29
242	322-35	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.39	54.05	0.057	0.019	100.52
243	323-36	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.86	53.73	0.017	bdl	100.61
244	324-37	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.72	53.85	0.020	0.036	100.63
245	325-38	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.63	53.95	bdl	0.040	100.62
246	326-39	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.53	53.84	bdl	0.020	100.39
247	327-40	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.71	53.80	0.001	0.028	100.54
248	328-41	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.47	53.53	0.008	0.069	100.08
249	329-42	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.53	53.87	bdl	0.065	100.46
250	330-43	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.41	53.83	bdl	0.048	100.29
251	331-44	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.74	54.15	0.017	0.024	100.93
252	332-45	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.63	53.95	bdl	0.003	100.58
253	333-46	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.51	53.79	bdl	0.013	100.31
254	334-47	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.68	53.96	bdl	0.018	100.66
255	335-48	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.93	54.05	bdl	0.017	101.00
256	336-49	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.77	54.03	bdl	0.020	100.82
257	337-50	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.74	53.95	bdl	0.019	100.71
258	338-51	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.63	53.94	bdl	bdl	100.57
259	339-52	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.87	54.00	bdl	0.006	100.88
260	340-53	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	53.96	bdl	0.031	100.48
261	341-54	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.01	54.26	0.034	0.012	100.32
262	342-55	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.50	54.18	0.014	0.007	100.70
263	343-56	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.89	53.89	bdl	0.034	100.81
264	347-60	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.41	53.61	0.021	0.053	100.09
265	348-61	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.46	53.55	0.047	0.063	100.12
266	349-62	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.68	54.09	bdl	0.037	100.81
267	350-63	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.54	53.87	0.009	0.059	100.48
268	351-64	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.53	53.88	bdl	0.030	100.44
269	352-65	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.68	54.16	bdl	0.062	100.90
270	353-66	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.77	53.79	bdl	0.012	100.57
271	354-67	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.61	53.87	bdl	0.045	100.52
272	355-68	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.69	53.83	0.016	0.006	100.54
273	356-69	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.61	54.15	0.035	0.065	100.86
274	357-70	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	53.91	bdl	0.016	100.42
275	358-71	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.56	53.68	0.022	0.022	100.28
276	359-72	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.51	53.78	bdl	0.035	100.33
277	360-73	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.65	53.97	bdl	0.023	100.64
278	361-74	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.37	53.66	bdl	0.008	100.04
279	362-75	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	45.26	53.74	0.008	0.003	99.01
280	363-76	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.26	53.84	bdl	0.013	100.11
281	364-77	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.54	53.95	0.007	0.009	100.51
282	365-78	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.26	53.87	bdl	0.045	100.17
283	366-79	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.53	53.78	bdl	0.063	100.37
284	367-80	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.63	53.94	bdl	bdl	100.57
285	368-81	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	53.76	bdl	0.061	100.31
286	369-82	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.53	53.88	bdl	0.006	100.42
287	370-83	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.44	54.02	bdl	0.021	100.48
288	371-84	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.49	53.91	0.037	bdl	100.44
289	382-95	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.31	52.92	0.008	0.067	99.31
290	383-96	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.13	53.89	0.029	0.126	100.17
291	384-97	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.30	53.34	0.005	0.047	99.69
292	385-98	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.67	54.07	bdl	0.031	100.77

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
293	386-99	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.72	54.19	bdl	0.040	100.95
294	387-100	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.60	54.09	bdl	0.024	100.71
295	389-102	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.68	54.03	0.003	0.057	100.77
296	390-103	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.31	53.16	bdl	0.049	99.52
297	392-105	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.61	53.91	0.012	0.026	100.56
298	393-106	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.75	53.95	bdl	0.041	100.74
299	394-107	py	43.34	TAG-1	957C-15N-2-1D	46.35	53.54	0.015	0.060	99.97
300	396-109	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.59	53.81	bdl	0.012	100.41
301	397-110	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.66	54.06	bdl	0.009	100.73
302	398-111	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.80	54.11	0.005	0.003	100.92
303	399-112	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.64	54.08	bdl	bdl	100.72
304	400-113	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.26	53.64	0.037	0.010	99.95
305	401-114	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.68	54.05	bdl	0.059	100.79
306	402-115	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.58	54.12	bdl	0.006	100.71
307	403-116	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.64	54.14	bdl	0.024	100.80
308	404-117	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.60	53.96	0.015	0.042	100.62
309	405-118	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.76	54.11	bdl	0.021	100.89
310	406-119	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.59	53.84	bdl	0.064	100.49
311	407-120	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.56	54.06	bdl	bdl	100.62
312	408-121	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.78	54.12	bdl	0.002	100.90
313	409-122	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.67	53.91	0.016	0.007	100.60
314	410-123	py	92	TAG-1	957E-12R-1-4	46.68	54.23	0.003	0.008	100.92
315	411-124	cpy	92	TAG-4	957E-12R-1-4	30.55	35.11	bdl	33.55	99.21
316	412-125	cpy	92	TAG-4	957E-12R-1-4	30.67	35.18	bdl	33.71	99.56
317	415-128	cpy	92	TAG-4	957E-12R-1-4	30.53	35.14	bdl	33.45	99.12
318	422-135	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.89	53.97	0.014	0.007	100.88
319	427-140	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.76	54.16	0.026	0.048	100.99
320	431-144	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.84	54.00	bdl	0.016	100.86
321	437-150	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.79	54.08	0.019	0.013	100.90
322	441-154	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.96	53.92	0.022	0.055	100.96
323	443-156	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.91	53.91	bdl	0.061	100.88
324	444-157	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.82	53.86	bdl	0.092	100.77
325	452-165	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.04	53.88	0.019	0.022	100.96
326	455-168	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	46.62	53.59	0.031	0.093	100.33
327	463-176	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.08	53.88	0.002	0.036	101.00
328	465-178	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.08	53.75	bdl	0.033	100.86
329	467-180	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.09	53.86	bdl	0.026	100.98
330	487-200	cpy	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	30.73	35.01	bdl	34.77	100.51
331	488-201	cpy	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	30.88	35.15	bdl	34.84	100.87
332	489-202	cpy	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	30.63	35.22	bdl	34.78	100.63
333	490-203	cpy	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	30.70	35.20	bdl	34.55	100.45
334	491-204	cpy	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	30.66	35.18	bdl	34.65	100.49
335	493-206	mc	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.00	53.73	0.005	0.020	100.76
336	494-207	mc	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.05	53.71	0.009	0.009	100.78
337	495-208	mc	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.20	53.75	0.014	0.039	101.00
338	500-213	py	1.68	TAG-1	957F-1N-1-10D	47.04	53.86	0.011	0.027	100.94
339	504-3	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	47.37	52.97	0.044	0.378	100.76
340	507-6	py	21.32	TAG-1	957C-7N-2-1D	47.56	53.14	0.006	0.033	100.74
341	513-12	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.41	34.75	bdl	33.93	99.09
342	514-13	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.66	34.87	bdl	34.10	99.63
343	515-14	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.93	34.89	bdl	34.25	100.07
344	516-15	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.82	35.03	bdl	34.11	99.96
345	517-16	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.86	34.91	bdl	34.16	99.93
346	518-17	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.60	34.86	bdl	34.15	99.61
347	519-18	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.79	35.00	bdl	34.17	99.96
348	520-19	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.85	35.18	bdl	34.29	100.32
349	521-20	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.92	35.08	bdl	34.20	100.20
350	522-21	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.65	35.09	bdl	34.20	99.94
351	523-22	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.60	34.81	bdl	34.07	99.48
352	524-23	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.51	34.79	bdl	34.05	99.35
353	525-24	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.65	34.82	bdl	34.12	99.59
354	526-25	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.47	34.91	bdl	34.10	99.48
355	527-26	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.70	34.87	bdl	34.05	99.62
356	528-27	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.22	34.75	bdl	34.00	99.97
357	529-28	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.15	34.76	bdl	33.96	99.87
358	530-29	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.07	34.86	bdl	34.15	100.08
359	531-30	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.98	34.90	bdl	34.20	100.08
360	532-31	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.94	34.76	bdl	34.17	99.87
361	533-32	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.97	35.13	bdl	34.13	100.23
362	534-33	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.87	34.81	bdl	34.08	99.76
363	535-34	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.83	34.95	bdl	33.95	99.73
364	536-35	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.87	34.97	bdl	34.04	99.88
365	537-36	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.87	34.97	bdl	34.17	100.01

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
366	538-37	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.95	34.96	bdl	33.96	99.87
367	539-38	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.97	35.06	bdl	34.13	100.16
368	540-39	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.96	34.92	bdl	34.12	100.00
369	541-40	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.95	34.85	bdl	33.74	99.54
370	542-41	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.03	34.83	bdl	34.17	100.03
371	543-42	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.54	34.83	bdl	33.95	99.32
372	544-43	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.03	35.18	bdl	34.19	100.40
373	545-44	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.91	35.08	bdl	33.98	99.97
374	546-45	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.89	35.00	bdl	34.41	100.30
375	547-46	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.92	34.98	bdl	34.14	100.04
376	548-47	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.00	34.83	bdl	34.14	99.97
377	549-48	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.91	34.79	bdl	34.15	99.85
378	550-49	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.17	34.83	bdl	34.14	100.14
379	551-50	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.84	34.88	bdl	34.12	99.84
380	552-51	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.97	34.93	bdl	34.11	100.01
381	553-52	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.83	34.96	bdl	34.19	99.98
382	554-53	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.82	35.15	bdl	34.19	100.16
383	555-54	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.71	34.85	bdl	34.19	99.75
384	556-55	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.93	34.95	bdl	34.20	100.08
385	557-56	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.81	35.00	bdl	34.07	99.88
386	558-57	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.87	35.15	bdl	34.14	100.16
387	559-58	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.62	34.94	bdl	34.13	99.69
388	560-59	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.93	35.21	bdl	34.20	100.34
389	561-60	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.84	35.25	bdl	34.23	100.32
390	562-61	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.78	34.91	bdl	34.10	99.79
391	563-62	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.90	34.99	bdl	34.12	100.01
392	564-63	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.03	34.94	bdl	34.11	100.08
393	565-64	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	30.98	34.68	bdl	34.13	99.79
394	566-65	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.14	34.90	bdl	33.97	100.01
395	567-66	cpy	32.19	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1B	31.03	34.99	bdl	34.06	100.08
396	573-72	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	31.07	34.96	bdl	34.69	100.72
397	574-73	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.97	35.01	bdl	34.70	100.68
398	575-74	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.93	35.14	bdl	34.77	100.84
399	576-75	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.74	35.15	bdl	34.73	100.62
400	577-76	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.87	35.04	bdl	34.77	100.68
401	578-77	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.47	34.92	bdl	35.01	100.40
402	579-78	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.53	34.80	bdl	35.04	100.37
403	580-79	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.38	34.80	bdl	34.83	100.01
404	581-80	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.13	35.08	bdl	35.04	100.25
405	582-81	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.14	34.76	bdl	34.93	99.83
406	583-82	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.31	35.02	bdl	35.16	100.49
407	584-83	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.32	34.97	bdl	35.28	100.57
408	585-84	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.34	34.87	bdl	35.09	100.30
409	586-85	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.18	34.91	bdl	35.11	100.20
410	587-86	cpy	15.6	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-30	30.38	34.97	bdl	34.89	100.24
411	596-95	cpy	15.39	TAG-1	957C-5N-1-6	29.74	35.05	bdl	34.27	99.06
412	606-3	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.12	33.15	64.76	0.175	100.20
413	607-4	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	3.03	33.23	63.44	0.331	100.03
414	608-5	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.21	33.05	64.71	0.062	100.03
415	609-6	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	1.81	32.76	65.01	0.397	99.98
416	610-7	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	1.65	32.61	65.12	0.258	99.64
417	613-10	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	3.19	32.96	63.15	0.178	99.48
418	614-11	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.11	32.57	63.97	0.406	99.06
419	615-12	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.69	33.29	63.91	0.223	100.11
420	616-13	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	31.12	35.14	0.146	34.24	100.65
421	617-14	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	31.00	35.06	0.144	34.19	100.39
422	618-15	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	31.21	35.07	0.195	34.31	100.79
423	619-16	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	31.02	34.96	0.148	34.15	100.28
424	620-17	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	31.01	35.01	0.145	34.08	100.24
425	621-18	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.38	32.72	63.82	0.281	99.20
426	622-19	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	1.74	32.75	64.40	0.411	99.30
427	623-20	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	1.78	33.01	64.15	0.478	99.42
428	624-21	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.08	32.54	64.03	0.406	99.06
429	625-22	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	1.75	32.95	64.53	0.434	99.66
430	626-23	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.41	33.03	64.81	0.640	100.89
431	627-24	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.57	32.70	64.70	0.859	100.83
432	628-25	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.74	33.10	64.31	0.723	100.87
433	629-26	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.74	32.80	64.54	0.820	100.90
434	630-27	sph	14.71	TAG-4	957M-3R-1-11A	2.21	33.03	64.82	0.872	100.93
435	631-28	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	30.38	34.97	0.414	34.24	100.00
436	632-29	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	30.41	34.95	0.417	34.40	100.18
437	633-30	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	30.63	34.97	0.358	34.47	100.43
438	634-31	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	30.38	34.84	0.372	33.99	99.58

Appendix A2 cont. Major element EMPA analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in wt.%)

No	Sample ID	Mineral	mbsf	TAG Area	Section	Fe	S	Zn	Cu	Total
439	635-32	cpy	32.35	TAG-1	957C-11N-2-1E	30.65	34.83	0.149	34.37	100.00
440	638-35	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.02	32.71	66.02	0.123	99.87
441	639-36	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.01	32.35	65.71	0.143	99.21
442	640-37	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.18	32.72	65.63	0.017	99.55
443	641-38	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.06	32.73	65.92	0.133	99.84
444	642-39	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.10	32.51	65.42	0.170	99.20
445	643-40	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.93	33.03	63.65	0.102	99.71
446	644-41	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.67	32.91	64.07	0.152	99.80
447	645-42	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.86	32.91	64.81	0.071	99.65
448	646-43	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	1.98	32.94	64.57	0.141	99.63
449	647-44	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.22	32.96	64.48	0.078	99.74
450	648-45	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.22	32.63	64.30	0.235	99.39
451	649-46	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.15	32.63	64.44	0.167	99.39
452	650-47	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	3.11	32.73	63.32	0.137	99.30
453	651-48	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.96	32.66	63.81	0.121	99.55
454	652-49	sph	14.61	TAG-4	957K-3X-1-3	2.71	32.85	63.94	0.201	99.70

Major element compositions (wt.%) determined by EMPA of selected minerals in ODP Leg 158 drill core from the TAG hydrothermal mound. Sample ID, mineral phases, and location in the deposit are indicated. bdl = below detection limit.

Appendix A3. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In
1	1-1	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		120.1	1.00	1.40	0.02		28.2	0.20	0.50	1.80	3.20	
2	2-2	py	Py VI	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		42.6	1.60	0.10			57.2		0.30	0.10	1.20	
3	4-4	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		38.8	1.10	42.1		0.10	31.1		0.60			
4	5-5	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		2.70				0.10			0.30	0.20		0.02
5	8-8	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		12.8	1.20	1.90	0.02		7.40		0.40		1.50	
6	9-9	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		54.8	0.90	0.90			12.3		0.30			
7	11-11	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		42.7	0.80				22.8		0.60	0.10	1.90	
8	12-12	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		3.70	0.80	0.20			1.80		0.30		1.50	
9	20-20	py	Py V	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		55.9	6.00	17.9	0.01	0.50	9.90	0.70	0.50	0.10	2.10	
10	21-21	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		49.7	5.20	19.8	0.02	0.60	9.20	0.50	0.40	0.10	2.30	
11	23-23	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		23.6	5.40	1.70			7.80	0.60	0.30	0.10		
12	24-24	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		7.70	0.60	1.10			14.9	0.30	0.30			
13	27-27	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		46.1	3.40	300.3	0.20	0.90	10.4		1.00		1.70	
14	28-28	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		111.7	3.50	32.8	0.20	1.50	25.4	0.30	1.00			
15	30-30	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		35.2	2.10	5.50	0.03	0.10	21.6	0.30	0.40			
16	31-31	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		62.3	2.60	1.30			10.2	0.30	0.30	0.20		0.04
17	32-32	py	Py I	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		182.6	9.70	16.4	0.02	0.80	24.6	0.20	0.70	0.10	1.90	0.02
18	33-33	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		35.0	1.30	0.50	0.02		10.1	0.40	0.40			
19	35-35	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		67.4	0.90	6.90			52.9	0.40	0.40			0.02
20	36-36	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		124.1	0.80	0.70		0.10	1.60	0.30	0.30			
21	39-39	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		611.4	5.30	96.7	0.40	3.00	55.4	0.50	2.00	0.20	1.70	0.03
22	40-40	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		1.00			0.02		2.70	0.40	0.10	0.20	0.90	0.10
23	42-42	py	Py I	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		364.9		27.8	0.04	1.60	77.8	2.10	3.10	0.60	2.00	0.02
24	43-43	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		420.5	368.1	40.2	0.05	0.20	35.7	1.10	20.4	0.40	2.60	
25	44-44	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		33.0	64.4	52.5		0.10	16.1	1.10	0.60	1.10	1.00	0.02
26	45-45	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		7.40	5.30	45.2		1.30	11.8	0.60	0.90	1.00	1.00	0.02
27	47-47	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		179.0		150.5	0.30	6.60	70.5	5.30	2.00	0.90	1.00	16.1
28	48-48	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	9203	985.5		96.9	0.12	118.0	79.1	1104	6.00	241.9	355.6	
29	51-51	py	Py IV	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		264.1	130.5	222.7	0.50	7.80	124.0	0.90	4.80	0.10	3.17	12.7
30	52-52	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		96.1	289.6	125.9	0.28	9.85	64.8	1.03	7.91	0.24	3.17	12.7
31	54-54	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	7957	1131		218.2	0.31	185.4	88.2	1046	6.48	240.6	401.7	
32	55-55	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		2.30		132.5	0.40	3.60	2.60	0.30	1.00	2.30	2.30	
33	56-56	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		136.0	34.2	359.3	0.60	18.4	23.3	0.80	3.80	2.80	1.80	
34	57-57	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		11.3	40.4	217.0	0.20	2.10	9.50	0.70	2.20	5.40	5.40	
35	59-59	py	Py I	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		2.10	0.80	162.8	0.40	3.80	2.60	1.10	1.10	0.10	5.80	0.10
36	60-60	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		64.1		130.1	0.50	4.40	54.5	21.3	24.9	4.50	5.80	0.20
37	63-63	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		2.20	403.7	48.7			25.1		24.9	4.50	5.80	0.20
38	64-64	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		3.25	121.2	0.96			7.16	1.58	4.01	2.30	2.30	
39	67-67	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		39.6	33.7	9.20		1.60	3.90	0.60	4.50	1.80	1.80	
40	68-68	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		44.3	815.7	23.7	0.07	2.41	42.3	2.28	11.5	1.50	11.3	
41	69-69	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		161.2		299.2	0.50	13.2	69.3	4.10	21.1	0.60	11.3	
42	71-71	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		3.83	4.42	58.3		1.29	17.0	0.77	5.64	7.60	7.60	0.09
43	72-72	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		61.4	54.1	20.0	0.20	3.70	53.0	28.0	28.0	208.6	17.3	0.20
44	76-76	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	42513	726.6		1.95		7.87		878.8	25.0	208.6	17.3	0.20
45	80-80	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		49.9	1.10	0.02	0.03			0.20	0.60			

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U	
1	1-1	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		9.20	1.00	0.80			0.10	15.8		4.00	2.70		
2	2-2	py	Py VI	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		9.20				0.02	0.10	4187		10.0	0.10		
3	4-4	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.20	3.60		2.30	0.80	0.30		109.7	84.9	4.90	0.20	0.01	
4	5-5	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.10				1.00			269.8		25.9	0.01		
5	8-8	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.10	1.20		0.10			0.20	2335		34.1			
6	9-9	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.30	7.40			0.70		0.04	1059	1.70	34.9	0.05	0.001	
7	11-11	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1						0.01	0.10	649.4		76.4			
8	12-12	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.03						0.10	569.2		33.2			
9	20-20	py	Py V	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		1.00		0.30		0.10	0.10	38.0		19.6	0.10	0.05	
10	21-21	py	Py I	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		1.20	0.04	0.30		0.10	0.60	2370		38.0	0.03		
11	23-23	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.10	1.00		0.10		0.10	0.40	184.0	2.00	14.9	0.10	0.01	
12	24-24	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		0.30		0.10		0.10	0.10	1215		47.9	0.04	0.20	
13	27-27	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1			0.05	0.10	0.60	5.20	0.04	15.7		0.30			
14	28-28	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.03			0.50		18.0	1.00	34.9	1.40	0.30			
15	30-30	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1	0.10	5.20		0.20	0.40	0.10	0.80	941.7	2.10	16.8	0.60	0.20	
16	31-31	py	Py III	5	40.1	3	9	957P-9R-1-1		0.70		0.10	1.00	0.04	0.50	1014		25.9	0.10	0.20	
17	32-32	py	Py I	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		66.5		1.30		1.20	0.80	769.2		5.10	0.50	0.10	
18	33-33	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		2.60		0.10	0.80	0.10	0.10	489.0		37.3	0.04	0.02	
19	35-35	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		5.10		0.30		0.20	0.20	272.0		11.2	0.02	0.02	
20	36-36	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		2.70					0.01	156.5	1.10		0.04		
21	39-39	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		15.9	0.03	1.80	0.70	0.90	0.10	44.1	1.50	1.00	0.10		
22	40-40	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D				0.10			0.10	0.10	3.00		0.001		
23	42-42	py	Py I	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		150.2	0.02	1.50		11.1	0.10	47.3		4.90	1.30		
24	43-43	py	Py IV	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		60.1		0.60	0.70	5.60	0.03	103.1		2.00	1.80	0.30	
25	44-44	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		77.7	0.10	0.40		28.0	0.02	0.60		6.00	0.50		
26	45-45	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.10	1.50		0.80		1.60	0.02	0.30	1.90	0.10	1.50		
27	47-47	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.04	15.7	0.10	2.30	2.40	2.40	0.03	51.4	2.50	1.60	0.15	0.01	
28	48-48	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.96			22.3		0.10	0.04	9.61	1.62	3.00	0.15	0.01	
29	51-51	py	Py IV	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.10	95.0	0.60	5.10		3.20	0.02	77.1	7.50	3.61	3.00	0.70	
30	52-52	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.06	91.3	0.23	1.91	0.46	7.46	0.02	5.99	4.19	3.61	0.08		
31	54-54	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	1.39	2.03	0.01	18.5		0.26	0.03	8.40		0.01	0.01		
32	55-55	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.04	0.60	0.10	0.30		0.10	0.20	0.20	1.90	0.30	0.10		
33	56-56	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.10	85.6		3.80	0.80	38.4	0.05	11.8	3.10	4.10	0.30		
34	57-57	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.30	10.4		3.10		21.0	0.10			1.20			
35	59-59	py	Py I	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	1.00	0.90		0.40	0.30	0.20				0.50	0.10		
36	60-60	py	Py VI	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		65.9		7.70		0.30		141.5		2.90	2.10		
37	63-63	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.62	121.5	0.20	0.70		25.1	0.20	3.60	4.80	3.00	0.50		
38	64-64	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		107.5	0.11	1.48		18.2	0.12	0.55	7.75	3.46	0.06		
39	67-67	py	Py V	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		50.0		2.10		18.9	0.10	1.40		2.00	0.04		
40	68-68	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.36	111.8	0.31	2.02		7.01		3.09	6.32	4.17	0.22		
41	69-69	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		77.4		2.70		25.7			7.30	2.00	0.02		
42	71-71	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		24.6	0.15	0.60	3.53	12.1		0.73		8.24	5.38	0.05	
43	72-72	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		57.9	0.10	1.40		9.00	0.10	5.50		16.2	3.00	0.01	
44	76-76	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3				3.34				1.23					
45	80-80	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		0.70			0.50		0.02	904.7		4.10			

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	PyritPy V TypPy	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In
46	81-81	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		107.7	1.20	0.10			1.10		0.60		2.10	0.03
47	83-83	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		194.2		0.10			3.20		0.20		0.90	
48	84-84	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		173.8				0.7			0.60			0.03
49	87-87	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		384.0	1.20	0.40	0.03		20.7		0.50	0.10	2.20	0.03
50	88-88	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		332.7	2.30	0.10	0.02		6.60	0.40	0.50			
51	90-90	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		256.0	0.70	0.10			7.40		0.50	0.20		0.10
52	91-91	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		88.1	0.90	0.10	0.01		9.30	0.40	0.40			
53	92-92	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		96.2	21.3	43.4	0.30	14.3	37.4	0.60	3.20	4.60		
54	93-93	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		46.5	13.5	38.5	0.20	5.10	19.4	1.00	2.50	6.20		0.05
55	95-95	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		42.4	48.6	103.7	0.40	5.30	42.6	0.40	1.90			
56	96-96	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		395.9	46.6	14.4	0.60	0.70	50.2	0.60	0.60	0.10	3.10	0.04
57	99-99	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		909.3	0.60	0.10	0.10		1.40	0.50	0.30			0.10
58	100-100	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30			8.61			46.0	2.06	0.85	2.70			7.39
59	102-102	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30			9.23	1.52	0.06	56.9	2.67	0.71	2.61			7.23
60	103-103	py	Py I	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		1900	68.7	6.50	0.40	4.70	12.7	2.60	0.20	0.70		0.70
61	104-104	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		21.9		0.10	0.10	0.50	3.80	0.40	0.90	0.10		
62	105-105	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		22.2	2.10	18.7	0.10	1.10	16.6	0.60	1.40			
63	107-107	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		243.0	590.0	147.2	0.20	7.30	80.6	4.40	27.1	1.00		0.03
64	108-108	mc	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30		17.8	1.61	2.84	0.01	0.09	9.66		0.40			0.02
65	111-111	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		122.2	0.90	30.1	0.04	2.50	5.90		0.50	0.10	1.50	
66	112-112	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		119.4	103.8	14.2	0.10	2.00	13.9	0.90	228.3	1.80		
67	114-114	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		52.2	0.60	0.20			6.10	0.40	0.60			
68	115-115	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		17.3	15.4	2.90			44.8	0.20	0.30	0.10		0.28
69	117-2	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30		41.2	131.4	2.28		2.16	44.1	0.84	1.32	8.98		15.1
70	119-4	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30												
71	120-5	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30		24.8	6.49	29.0		1.39	88.3	1.12				
72	123-8	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30					0.78	33.5	2.50	7.44	0.69	5.01		6.67
73	124-9	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30		61.0	19.1	8.59		1.30	15.4					0.09
74	126-11	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30						19.3			0.94	51.6	13.8	52.8
75	127-12	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30			568.5	10.4	0.58	23.2	9.66	1.12	1.12	91.0		27.8
76	128-13	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		25.4		3.40			10.4		1.10		5.40	
77	129-14	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		106.7		1.30			26.0		1.40			
78	131-16	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		49.5	8.50	1.40		0.40			0.90			0.20
79	132-17	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		45.0	2.80				38.4		0.90			
80	135-20	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		10.8	2.30	1.50		1.20	10.1		0.90			0.10
81	136-21	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		396.5	5.40	30.4			71.5		3.90			
82	138-23	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		227.8	4.00	6.10			34.5		1.10			
83	139-24	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		388.3	64.7	46.5	1.30	0.70	56.5	0.80	1.50	0.40	10.1	
84	140-25	py	Py I	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		344.4	3.50	2.70		0.20	29.1		0.50	0.10		
85	141-26	py	Py VI	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		529.0	3.60	11.1		0.20	10.6		0.80	0.10		
86	143-28	py	Py VI	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		179.2	3.10	13.4		0.20	9.90		0.50			
87	144-29	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		2.90	9.70	8.80		1.00	5.60		0.40			
88	147-32	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		210.5	1.10	0.90		1.00	11.6		0.40			0.03
89	148-33	py	Py II	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		49.7	1.00	5.20			16.1		2.90		2.10	
90	150-35	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		24.4	1.10	8.50		0.30	22.1		0.30			

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	PyritPy V TypPy	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U	
46	81-81	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	0.05	8.90		0.10	3.10		0.03	1149		10.1	0.10		
47	83-83	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		5.40	0.02		3.70		0.02	1076		9.30	0.10		
48	84-84	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		9.60					0.40	1837		41.1			
49	87-87	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		3.70		0.10	0.60		0.50	341.3		20.6	0.10	0.002	
50	88-88	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		5.50		0.10	3.20		0.03	2091	2.60	63.1	0.10		
51	90-90	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	0.10	1.40				0.04	0.20	2275		23.7			
52	91-91	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		0.40					0.10	689.3		112.4			
53	92-92	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	25.2	0.03		4.80	4.40			1.50	3.30		0.10		
54	93-93	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	120.4			3.40	152.2			1.30	4.80		0.80	0.10	
55	95-95	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	62.2			1.20	11.7		0.02	0.40		0.10	0.10	0.02	
56	96-96	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	0.05	56.3		0.60	0.40		0.70	316.8	1.70	3.10	1.10	0.30	
57	99-99	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	4.80	1.60					0.02	121.2		2.10	0.10		
58	100-100	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30	186.6	6.47	0.04	0.25				66.4		11.5			
59	102-102	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30	232.3	2.76					0.04	68.5	6.50	7.24			
60	103-103	py	Py I	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	4.40	4.10		0.30	1.10		0.20	2052		0.70			
61	104-104	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		1.60	0.03				0.30	90.2	77.7	4.90	0.60	0.30	
62	105-105	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		44.7		1.40	0.80			4.30		0.20	0.20	0.01	
63	107-107	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	0.10	48.9		6.00	0.80		0.02	8.00	2.10	1.40	0.10	0.10	
64	108-108	mc	-	4	15.6	1	9	957M-3R-1-30	0.08	2.16		0.06			0.06	45.8	2.99		0.03	0.03	
65	111-111	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		1.40		0.20	0.90			0.10		0.05			
66	112-112	py	Py V	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30		99.1	0.10	1.40	37.0			1.50	5.90	0.80	0.80	0.30	
67	114-114	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	129.1			0.10			0.03	1.60		0.60	0.01	0.01	
68	115-115	py	Py IV	4	15.6	3	9	957M-3R-1-30	3.60	52.0		0.40	0.60			38.7	3.80		0.30	0.01	
69	117-2	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30				1.32				24.2	4.60		0.30	0.01	
70	119-4	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30	40.1						32.1			2.21		0.04	
71	120-5	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30	0.89	24.4				7.87	0.04	81.7		2.21			
72	123-8	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30	35.5	4.84					0.13	38.7	11.2	4.97			
73	124-9	mc	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30		221.6	0.09	1.11	0.47		0.51	108.8		1.51	0.04		
74	126-11	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30	73.4			0.19	0.06			77.4		2.59			
75	127-12	cpy	-	4	15.6	1	5	957M-3R-1-30	58.1									0.54		0.13	
76	128-13	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		1.50		0.40	3.00		0.10	1816	16.5	28.2	0.60	0.02	
77	129-14	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		11.2	0.20				0.20	737.9		106.8	0.60	0.01	
78	131-16	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D	0.40	1.60	0.20										
79	132-17	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		4.40	0.20										
80	135-20	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D	0.30												
81	136-21	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		82.1		1.30	1.50		0.10	129.7		5.40	0.60		
82	138-23	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		5.60								19.0	1.20	0.20	
83	139-24	py	Py III	1	21.32	2	7	957C-7N-2-1D		33.0		1.70	1.30			127.4		1.40	2.50		
84	140-25	py	Py I	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		22.2		0.10	1.10		0.40	552.4	24.0	0.10	0.20		
85	141-26	py	Py VI	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		40.7	0.04	0.20			0.10	219.7		0.90	0.01		
86	143-28	py	Py VI	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D	0.20	26.7					0.03	146.1		0.70	0.30		
87	144-29	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D	0.10	0.60		0.20	2.60		0.10	134.3		0.30	1.20		
88	147-32	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		10.6					0.10	475.2		10.2	0.10		
89	148-33	py	Py II	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D		1.10		0.10	0.50			61.6	2.40		0.10		
90	150-35	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-1D	5.60						0.10	701.5		76.4	0.002		

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	
91	151-36	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		63.0	10.5	58.9		2.10	38.6		0.70		2.00	0.05	
92	152-37	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		34.3	2.50	27.6		1.60	61.0		0.90	0.20			
93	153-38	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		54.2		11.0		0.50	49.4		0.50				
94	155-40	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		64.1		5.30			20.7		0.70				
95	159-44	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		7.60			0.40			0.50	0.30				
96	160-45	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		123.8					5.50	0.40	0.40				
97	162-47	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		15.4	2.60	0.50		0.10	12.2		0.20	1.30	0.04		
98	163-48	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		4.80	1.70	0.30			12.6		0.30	1.30			
99	164-49	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		52.0	4.90	3.00			6.20	0.40	0.30	0.30			
100	165-50	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		100.6	3.00	0.60		0.30	2.10		0.30				
101	167-52	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		73.3	6.50	21.3		0.40	27.6	0.50	0.60	3.60	0.04		
102	168-53	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		164.1		92.3			117.2		0.30				
103	171-56	py	Py I	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		13.8		28.1		1.70	31.3		0.30	5.20	0.20		
104	172-57	py	Py VI	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		352.5		19.6		1.40	119.1		1.00				
105	174-59	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		310.7	3.70	35.3	0.40	0.80	516.2		1.80	7.20	0.50		
106	175-60	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		281.2	2.50	91.6		2.90	143.9		1.80				
107	176-61	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		95.5	4.50	25.1		0.70	207.4		0.80	5.90	3.00		
108	177-62	py	Py VI	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		4.60		2.30		0.20	7.90		0.80		0.04		
109	180-65	py	Py I	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4			1.00	0.10			3.30	0.30	0.30				
110	183-68	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		76.1	2.50	55.3		1.10	191.4		0.40			0.10	
111	184-69	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		598.7	2.80	1.90	0.40		45.8	0.80	0.80	0.20			
112	186-71	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		110.6	149.9	196.5		15.4	56.2	6.10	7.27			0.10	
113	187-72	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4			35.6	10.8		0.29	7.22		0.80	9.77			
114	188-73	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3				159.7		0.31	7.98	1.61	7.62				
115	189-74	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		3.20		54.0			28.4	1.30	18.9	0.80			
116	191-76	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		3.35	393.2	11.4			3.36	1.38	7.40	0.33			
117	192-77	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		1428		106.1		178.1	90.0	1183	8.92	384.9	505.5	25.6	
118	195-80	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	12933			85.3	0.73		50.4	1013	10.7	57.7	385.7	3.62	
119	196-81	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	33363			9.2	0.46		59.8		13.2			0.05	
120	198-83	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		36.6	139.4	92.5		2.00	99.7	22.7	0.70				
121	199-84	py	Py IV	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		32.5	29.1	92.5		49.0	129.7	6.06	670.4	680.4	30.5		
122	200-85	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	9385	2061		89.5		52.0	98.3	6.74	558.9	415.6	14.2		
123	201-86	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	11397	1493		73.7	0.43		67.8	1566	8.62	1135	900.2	34.5	
124	203-88	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	12151	3023		35.3	0.54		9.11	1116	26.4	82.7	16.4	0.47	
125	204-89	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	45701	1741		15.8			9.48	1.04	9.03	0.81			
126	207-92	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		2184	897.7	1.37		33.6	5.85	1054	35.8	35.9	31.6	0.15	
127	208-93	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	44754	810.8		238.5	0.61	7.69	792.8	32.9	133.7	30.2	0.07		
128	210-95	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	54302	1138		13.5	0.37		4.13	2615	18.9	688.0	16.7	0.16	
129	211-96	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	51868	166.8	1.20	9.12		8.07	4.13	2615	18.9	688.0	16.7	0.16	
130	212-97	py	Py I	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D				2.80		0.20	8.40		9.80				
131	213-98	py	Py IV	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		194.2	12.1	6.10		4.00	48.0		1.50				
132	215-100	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		474.9	3.40	19.9		0.90	47.8		0.50				
133	216-101	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		96.6	5.40	0.90		4.64	13.4	1.00	0.50			9.00	
134	219-104	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			45.4			4.22		1.21	1.40	24.4	5.88	8.10	7.18
135	220-105	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			41.2										

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U
91	151-36	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		49.8		0.50	1.40	0.30	1.10	643.3	6.80	27.9	0.20	0.50
92	152-37	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		220.7		1.00	1.60	0.30	1.50	1828	10.2	62.9	0.60	0.10
93	153-38	py	Py III	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		3.90		0.30	1.90	0.03	0.05	641.9		19.6	0.20	
94	155-40	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		19.9			3.10	1.40	0.90	433.1		77.9		
95	159-44	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID	0.30				0.03	0.03	0.10	672.3		41.4		
96	160-45	py	Py V	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID	0.40	1.90		0.10	1.60	0.02	3.40	636.6		43.1	0.20	
97	162-47	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		2.10	0.02	0.10	1.70	0.02	0.10	1169	3.50	33.1	0.40	0.02
98	163-48	py	Py IV	1	43.34	3	10a	957C-15N-2-ID		1.10	0.20	0.30	1.70	0.10	0.10	8.20	13.3			
99	164-49	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		19.2				0.10	0.10	23.4		0.20		
100	165-50	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4												0.02
101	167-52	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		25.0		0.30		0.20	0.10	198.1		0.70	0.03	
102	168-53	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		3.10		1.10		6.60	0.90	552.3	9.00	0.60	0.80	
103	171-56	py	Py I	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		42.6		0.40			0.80	1298	11.8	31.5	0.50	
104	172-57	py	Py VI	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		12.5		3.50				49.8				
105	174-59	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4	0.50	8.30		2.30	2.80	2.80	2.60	241.4		0.80	0.10	
106	175-60	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		247.1		1.70	4.40	4.40	2.50	512.9	9.70	41.6	1.40	
107	176-61	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4				0.60				275.5		10.7		2.30
108	177-62	py	Py VI	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		3.40	0.20	0.70	2.70	0.10	3.20	1092	15.8		0.10	
109	180-65	py	Py I	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		24.7		0.30		0.01	0.10	760.5		13.9		
110	183-68	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4	0.10	0.30					3.90			1.50		
111	184-69	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4	0.40	2.70		1.50	0.03	0.40	261.9		29.5	0.60	0.20	
112	186-71	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		1.80		0.50	1.90		1.10	503.7		61.0	0.20	
113	187-72	py	Py III	1	92	3	10a	957E-12R-1-4		18.1		0.80		1.80	0.50	81.6		12.6	0.20	0.10
114	188-73	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		134.1		0.57	17.5	17.5		1.32		1.82	0.01	
115	189-74	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		113.1		3.05	15.7	15.7				4.46	0.03	
116	191-76	py	Py II	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		190.7		1.40	25.4	25.4				6.60	0.10	
117	192-77	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		97.2		1.55	15.9	15.9				2.24	0.14	
118	195-80	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	1.27	0.78		41.2	0.36	0.07	16.2		0.43			
119	196-81	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		3.63		28.9	0.84		13.9		1.39			
120	198-83	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3		116.0	0.29	1.88	3.54	3.54		1.00		1.06	0.26	
121	199-84	py	Py IV	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.40	96.5	0.10	7.90	20.6	20.6		15.4		2.30	0.20	
122	200-85	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	7.13		0.07	28.8	0.33	0.33		16.8		0.22	0.01	
123	201-86	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	1.72	1.07		64.4	0.08	0.08		18.3			0.02	
124	203-88	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	4.46	0.59	0.08	66.4	0.18	0.18		21.4				
125	204-89	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	7.86	1.39		1.26	0.20	0.20		113.8		0.51	0.48	
126	207-92	mc	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.32	125.3		2.78	17.9	17.9		0.73		3.88	0.12	
127	208-93	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.37	6.34		120.6	0.23	0.23		7.69				
128	210-95	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	0.37			3.35				41.4		1.02		
129	211-96	sph	-	4	14.61	1	5	957K-3X-1-3	2.82	4.27		8.44				8.92			0.06	
130	212-97	py	Py I	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		1.00					0.02	6.80				
131	213-98	py	Py IV	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		47.7		1.40	2.70	2.70		27.8		13.1	0.70	0.10
132	215-100	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		28.2			1.70	1.70	0.03	9.80			0.30	0.10
133	216-101	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		1.90			0.40	0.40		15.1	7.20			0.10
134	219-104	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	92.2	18.1		0.77	0.24	0.24		9.72		0.54		
135	220-105	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	190.2	1.43					0.06	7.87				0.21

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	
136	222-107	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			39.1	0.14	0.54	3.60			0.80	7.80		1.93	
137	223-108	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			43.1	4.60	0.60	5.23		3.50		6.11	10.9	2.22	
138	224-109	py	Py I	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		105.7				0.20	30.4						
139	225-110	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		442.0	24.9	39.7	0.50	3.10	34.4	1.00	3.90	0.40	5.50		
140	227-112	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		706.0	1041	5.80	0.80	0.50	560.8	4.00	4.00		6.10	0.30	
141	228-113	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		686.3	480.4	29.4	0.90	12.8	73.3	85.9	0.60		11.8		
142	231-116	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		29.5	378.0	3.00				1.60					
143	232-117	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			36.8	0.10	0.79	3.70		1.15	23.9		12.0	6.32	
144	234-119	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		20.0	50.0	1.60	0.50	0.40	35.4	1.00		8.60			
145	235-120	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		524.6	26.9	21.5		1.80	28.2	2.80					
146	236-121	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		280.1	150.5	17.5			39.9	1.40	0.60		7.10	0.04	
147	237-122	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		379.3	17.8	25.1		1.52	48.5	0.34	1.92				
148	239-124	py	Py IV	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		4.20	136.6	0.40			5.00	0.50	0.20		0.10		
149	240-125	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		4.42	2.20			0.13	6.33	0.81					
150	243-128	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		3.37			0.61		1.90	0.39	0.32			2.07	
151	244-129	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			52.1			5.80		1.88	4.72			2.07	
152	246-131	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			36.3	0.09		4.86	2.40	0.93	20.7	23.8	8.43		
153	247-132	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D			49.4			3.59			18.3	9.27	11.2		
154	249-2	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		269.4	12.0	8.60	0.30	0.30	12.2	10.3	0.20	0.30	1.20	0.02	
155	251-4	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		618.9	1.40	15.1	0.10	0.40	11.1	0.70	0.30	183.5	15.0	2.76	
156	252-5	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			74.7	0.30		2.82			1.54	33.4	14.8	2.60	
157	255-8	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			37.3			2.26			1.21	3.12	3.02	2.72	
158	256-9	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			34.3	0.03	0.19	2.28			1.04	13.6	3.84		
159	258-11	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			43.2	0.09		2.51		0.60	0.97	6.60	7.43	7.81	
160	259-12	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			38.1			3.77			1.09	30.9	75.1	5.50	
161	260-13	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			34.6		0.23	2.18			0.40				
162	261-14	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		25.1	0.50	0.04									
163	263-16	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		128.1	1.50	9.00		0.10	9.60	0.30	0.50				
164	264-17	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		72.8	2.00	0.10		0.20	1.30	0.70					
165	267-20	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			34.2	0.21		2.67		1.31	1.94	44.6	12.2	2.78	
166	268-21	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			28.6	0.10		2.31	3.81	0.77	1.43	8.73		2.55	
167	270-23	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		57.9					2.40	0.50					
168	271-24	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		92.1	1.20	1.40			7.10	0.30					
169	272-25	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		44.0					1.40						
170	273-26	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			29.1			3.06		1.08	1.37	5.86	3.35	5.18	
171	275-28	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			35.8	0.03		3.39		1.09	1.88	1.88		3.86	
172	276-29	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B			32.2			3.09	3.08	0.75	1.24	11.9	19.3	4.71	
173	279-32	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		46.2	1.40	0.03			3.80	0.40	0.10	1.70			
174	280-33	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		72.9		0.04		0.20	4.20	0.20	0.20	0.20			
175	282-35	py	Py VI	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		41.5	1.20	0.10			8.60	0.20	0.20				
176	283-36	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		14.2		0.10			6.90	0.70	0.10				
177	284-37	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		28.2		0.10			5.00						
178	285-38	py	Py I	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		289.9			0.10		1.40		1.10	0.20			
179	287-40	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		40.7			0.10		1.20	0.30					
180	288-41	py	Py I	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		8.40	1.50	0.50	0.20		3.40				2.50		

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U
136	222-107	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	9.11							5.28	7.74	10.9	0.36	0.02
137	223-108	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	10.6	1.06						5.47		12.6	0.34	
138	224-109	py	Py I	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		7.90	0.20	0.30			0.20	444.7		18.0		0.01
139	225-110	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		60.1		1.90	3.70	2.20		90.0			0.80	0.20
140	227-112	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	0.40	8.00	0.10			0.40	141.6			5.70	0.10	
141	228-113	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		11.1		3.80		1.50		79.9			1.00	0.20
142	231-116	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		9.00						1.60			1.00	0.20
143	232-117	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	11.8	11.4						5.84		30.8	0.64	0.03
144	234-119	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	0.50	2.50		0.70	3.50			1.00			0.80	0.10
145	235-120	py	Py V	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	0.20	35.7	0.20	1.50		3.90		108.2			0.80	0.10
146	236-121	py	Py VI	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		6.70		0.70		0.30		358.9		5.00		0.10
147	237-122	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		11.9		1.15		1.00		5.35	4.15		0.63	0.36
148	239-124	py	Py IV	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		0.50						0.20		6.40	0.20	
149	240-125	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D		0.65	0.06							5.71	0.14	
150	243-128	mc	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D								2.02		5.24	0.26	
151	244-129	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D				0.64				4.56		32.1	0.52	0.01
152	246-131	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	8.66	4.32						7.89		10.4	0.58	
153	247-132	cpy	-	1	1.68	1	6	957F-1W-1-10D	151.8							2.82			1.90	9.00
154	249-2	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	19.7	154.7		0.60		1.10	0.20	16.6	9.70		0.30	0.40
155	251-4	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.10	4.10	0.02	0.30		0.50	0.20	134.7	2.30		0.20	0.05
156	252-5	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	11.1			0.51				12.3			0.20	0.01
157	255-8	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	10.9	7.69		0.17	2.15	0.03		23.5		9.25	0.45	1.28
158	256-9	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	28.2							22.9			0.003	0.003
159	258-11	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	23.3	1.51						21.4			0.48	0.01
160	259-12	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	3.08	13.9		0.16				33.4		2.14		
161	260-13	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	4.23	1.80				0.03		26.9		0.46		0.003
162	261-14	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.10							3.30		5.30	0.10	0.70
163	263-16	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		5.40		0.30		0.30	0.01	101.8	1.80	2.00	0.20	0.10
164	264-17	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		0.70				0.02		9.90			0.20	0.01
165	267-20	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	12.4	1.49		0.17				14.4	9.25	11.5	1.00	0.08
166	268-21	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	20.2							21.4		24.9	0.27	
167	270-23	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.10			0.20				67.6		7.70		
168	271-24	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		1.90						144.3	3.20	13.0		
169	272-25	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.10							216.7		20.1		
170	273-26	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	27.9	4.49						31.6		3.02		
171	275-28	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	31.0	1.02						20.2		11.3		
172	276-29	cpy	-	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	14.4				1.64			21.7		19.3		
173	279-32	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		0.40				0.01		60.6	2.60	2.80	0.20	0.10
174	280-33	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.10	2.10	0.05	0.10				93.3				
175	282-35	py	Py VI	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B								47.1	6.40	21.1		
176	283-36	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.20	0.50	0.04			0.02	399.7		47.1			
177	284-37	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B				0.20	4.60	0.03	0.20	117.7		47.1		
178	285-38	py	Py I	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		2.20		0.20			0.30	135.8	5.30	68.4		
179	287-40	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		2.40	0.02	0.10			0.02	417.1		8.80		0.01
180	288-41	py	Py I	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		0.50						39.4	115.1			

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In
181	291-44	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		51.2		1.30		0.10	4.30					
182	292-45	py	Py VI	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		210.7	2.50	7.30	0.20	0.70	17.6		0.60			
183	294-47	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		24.4		0.05			2.90					
184	295-48	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		288.7	1.70				5.00		0.80			
185	296-49	py	Py I	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		185.7	8.20	7.60		0.20	20.6		0.90	0.10		
186	297-50	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		423.8	242.0	126.5	0.10	1.60	70.5		7.90		1.70	
187	299-52	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		23.5	1.50	4.70		0.10	47.5		0.90		2.80	
188	300-53	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		591.3	9.80	44.3	0.90	2.70	101.3		1.40			
189	303-56	cpy	-	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6			28.3	23.1		14.1				1.20		8.92
190	306-59	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		466.2	1893	84.4	0.40	1.60	139.3	5.70	21.8	0.70		0.10
191	307-60	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		179.0		81.3		0.80	75.4	3.00	3.20	0.40		0.04
192	308-61	cpy	-	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6				10.4		11.8	12.0			54.7		11.8
193	309-62	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		288.5	0.60	1.60			3.80	1.00	0.40	0.10		
194	311-64	py	Py I	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		223.8	92.0	11.8	0.10	0.20	51.2		1.20	0.20		
195	312-65	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6				0.80	0.20	0.20			0.50	0.50	2.90	0.10
196	315-68	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		332.2	1.30	4.00		0.30	39.2	0.40	0.60	0.10	2.60	
197	316-69	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		547.6	1.60	4.20		0.80	23.5		0.60	0.10	2.60	0.02
198	318-71	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		86.4	23.7	5.10	0.10	0.20	17.3		0.40	1.30		
199	319-72	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		52.6	1.20	18.5		0.80	44.0		0.40	0.10	1.30	
200	320-73	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		44.5	1.90				9.50			6.70		
201	321-74	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		65.4	12.2	0.60		0.50	6.00		1.00	0.20	5.50	
202	323-76	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		86.7	30.2	1.40			146.7		0.80			
203	324-77	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		103.2	3.70	12.3		1.60	297.7					0.10
204	327-80	py	Py VI	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		21.6	76.1	2.30	0.50	1.20	139.1	0.90	1.20		0.10	
205	328-81	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		13.4	4.70	0.60			3.10		0.20		0.10	
206	330-83	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			919.2	56.1		20.5				34.1		37.6
207	331-84	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		12.7		0.10			1.60	0.50	1.00		0.10	
208	332-85	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		24.3	2.40	0.10			1.90		0.80			
209	333-86	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		25.9			0.20	0.10			0.30		5.10	
210	335-88	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		22.1				0.20			1.00	0.20		
211	336-89	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		81.4	9.80	5.20	0.30	0.50	263.7		0.80			7.12
212	339-92	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			273.5	7.27		13.8	6.71	5.07		2.69		7.82
213	340-93	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			39.8		0.67	4.43				1.70		13.4
214	342-95	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			50.2			8.83				6.10		
215	343-96	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		51.9				0.10			0.90			
216	344-97	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		19.2		89.4	0.70	1.30	69.0	0.90				6.70
217	347-100	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			139.1			9.71	11.8			1.68		
218	354-107	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			35.7			5.69		1.55		2.53		7.31
219	355-108	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7			121.9			4.41		3.14	1.30	2.93	7.40	8.70
220	345-98	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7												
221	351-104	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7												
222	366-1	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3												0.02
223	367-2	cpy	-	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3												0.10
224	369-4	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		9.70	2.30	3.92		3.72	5.30		0.50	0.30		0.83
225	370-5	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		15.8	5.20	0.50		0.20	1.10		0.10	1.80		0.03

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U
181	291-44	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.20	67.2	0.04	0.10	1.20	0.20	0.10	71.6			0.10	0.03
182	292-45	py	Py VI	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B	0.20	4.00		0.40	0.10	0.10		101.0			0.20	0.10
183	294-47	py	Py V	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		152.9					0.10	41.1		7.30	0.30	
184	295-48	py	Py IV	1	32.19	2	8	957C-11N-2-1B		3.50					0.20	0.50	5.00	7.20		
185	296-49	py	Py I	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		12.6	0.03	0.30	1.10	1.10		882.4		98.1	0.30	0.01
186	297-50	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		92.1	0.03	1.60	7.70	7.70	0.02	30.5		79.7	1.50	0.70
187	299-52	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		2.00		0.30	0.10	0.10	0.20	214.7			0.20	0.04
188	300-53	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		7.30			0.90	0.90		23.3			0.50	0.30
189	303-56	cpy	-	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6	30.7			2.58				39.7				2.13
190	306-59	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6	0.10	70.0	0.03	5.60	3.80	3.80	0.10	114.2	3.30	1.30	1.30	1.80
191	307-60	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		13.8		3.70	3.20	3.20	0.02	216.1	10.3	10.3	0.50	0.30
192	308-61	cpy	-	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6	30.1			2.16	12.3			5.96			3.44	5.20
193	309-62	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		4.70	0.02	0.10	0.20	0.20		297.9	1.80	9.80	0.20	0.01
194	311-64	py	Py I	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		34.3		1.50	2.60	2.60	0.10	227.5	2.80	6.40	0.30	0.40
195	312-65	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6	0.20		0.10	0.30			0.10	250.8	12.3	0.30	0.70	
196	315-68	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		5.10	0.10	0.30	0.50	0.50	0.05	296.0	4.50	3.30	0.90	0.03
197	316-69	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6	0.10	2.00	0.05	0.30	0.50	0.03	2.40	162.3	11.4	0.20	0.02	
198	318-71	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		6.00	0.02	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.20	538.8	5.50	7.80	0.20	0.02
199	319-72	py	Py IV	1	21.05	2	7	957G-3N-1-6		5.00		0.20	0.40	0.10	0.60	351.3		10.3	0.40	0.10
200	320-73	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7	0.20			0.30	3.10			808.4	18.9	0.20		0.10
201	321-74	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		21.8				0.10		396.9	20.5	2.20	0.20	0.20
202	323-76	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		1.80		23.8		0.05	0.03	63.7		27.3	0.01	0.01
203	324-77	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		3.60	0.10	0.20				677.5	9.60	2.30	0.10	0.10
204	327-80	py	Py VI	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7				0.20	2.60			288.5		44.3	0.10	0.10
205	328-81	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7	0.30							12.5			0.10	0.10
206	330-83	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	7.84	5.40		6.20	6.20	0.19	2.31				0.56	0.02
207	331-84	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7			0.10							62.0	0.20	0.02
208	332-85	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		0.40				0.03		666.9		27.3	0.01	0.01
209	333-86	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		5.40						227.2		28.0	0.20	0.20
210	335-88	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7			0.05					174.0	7.70	25.1	0.20	0.04
211	336-89	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		8.50		0.50		0.20		58.0		5.30	0.40	0.24
212	339-92	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	21.2				11.9			2.45	27.9	21.4	0.50	0.20
213	340-93	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	28.0			0.38			0.16			1.03	0.20	0.01
214	342-95	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	38.7									0.20	0.20	0.01
215	343-96	py	Py IV	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		207.8	0.10	4.30		0.05		43.1	6.90	83.5	0.20	0.01
216	344-97	py	Py V	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7								142.2	32.7		0.20	0.01
217	347-100	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	23.7											0.01
218	354-107	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	32.2											0.01
219	355-108	cpy	-	5	35.37	3	10a	957P-8R-1-7	30.5											0.05
220	345-98	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		6.80						133.1		54.3	0.10	0.03
221	351-104	py	Py I	5	35.37	1	5	957P-8R-1-7		1.30						96.9		41.2	0.10	0.10
222	366-1	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.20	0.30	0.10	0.10	3.60	0.20	0.20	814.6	9.10	58.1	0.10	0.10
223	367-2	cpy	-	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	3.22							143.6		852.5		
224	369-4	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.30	13.7	0.05	1.60	1.60	0.50	0.50	1319	163.8	22.4	8.10	0.80
225	370-5	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.20	0.70		1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	848.3	212.8	23.1	5.30	0.40

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In
226	373-8	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		12.8	14.0	30.4		0.60	26.4		0.50			
227	374-9	py	Py VI	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		4.20		4.00		0.10	17.7	0.30	0.40		0.90	0.10
228	376-11	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		18.9	7.50	66.6	0.50	0.70	48.6		5.80			
229	377-12	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		9.30	0.50	0.10			33.5	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.02	
230	378-13	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		6.30	0.70	0.20				0.80	0.80	0.20	0.20	
231	379-14	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		46.1	1.10	0.10			2.10	0.30	0.40			
232	381-16	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		12.7	21.6	14.2			15.1		0.40			
233	382-17	py	Py III	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		4.60		0.20			4.10		0.60			
234	385-20	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		8.70		0.90		0.10	42.4		3.10	0.10		0.20
235	386-21	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		27.2	0.70	0.10	0.10		8.50	0.20	0.20	2.40		
236	388-23	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		50.4		52.4			37.9	0.60	0.60			
237	389-24	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		35.8		0.50				0.70	0.70	0.20		
238	390-25	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		11.1	1.80	0.20			1.70					
239	391-26	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		14.9	12.2	2.50			11.9					
240	393-28	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		140.3		17.4		0.50	29.6		0.50			0.10
241	394-29	py	Py III	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		94.9	15.2	0.20			6.30					
242	397-32	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		9.50	1.70	2.70		0.30	7.80	0.40	0.60			0.80
243	398-33	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		2.20	1.50	0.10		0.30	126.2	5.00	0.60	4.60		
244	400-35	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		65.1		42.1		2.30	4.40	1.40				
245	401-36	py	Py VI	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		12.2		8.90								
246	402-37	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		379.1	24.5	504.6		13.6	66.5		1.50	0.30		0.10
247	403-38	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		99.2	7.30	374.5		4.60	5.80	3.20				
248	405-40	py	Py VI	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		107.0	1.20	9.30	0.30	0.20	10.6	0.50	0.30			0.10
249	406-41	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		134.2	5.70	19.1		1.20	40.0	1.60				0.04
250	409-44	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		125.6	1.60	1.50			3.00	0.50				0.80
251	410-45	py	Py VI	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		17.4	10.0	10.0	1.30	1.70	79.5	1.20	0.40	4.30		
252	412-47	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		303.8	29.4	267.7	0.30	6.60	109.5	9.62	3.93	64.8	69.5	5.67
253	413-48	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		81.0	69.9	580.2		5.50	5.00	6.60				0.10
254	414-49	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		158.5		0.40			3.40	0.20	0.30			0.10
255	415-50	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		50.2		3.60			3.80		1.30			
256	417-52	py	Py IV	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		30.8		69.5			51.3	6.00				
257	418-53	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1			30.4									
258	421-56	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		119.9	1.07	1.07	2.55					4.47		11.3
259	422-57	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		1967	20.8	20.8		1.48				12.1	18.0	10.5
260	424-59	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		43.9	4.09	4.09						14.5	15.4	0.01
261	425-60	py	Py IV	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		66.2	27.9	119.4		0.10	2.70	0.50	0.40			0.40
262	426-61	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4			50.8	23.5	0.60	7.30	21.4		1.30			
263	430-65	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4			25.3	301.3	1.70	102.1	153.4	3.10	3.10	20.3		0.90
264	433-68	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4		575.1	549.2	31.1		27.1	12.1	55.10	5.93	231.1	50.5	0.90
265	434-69	sph	-	2	10.19	0	4	957A-3X-1-4	6159	549.2				10.7	10.4	709.1	3.08	361.2	139.0	0.48
266	436-71	sph	-	2	10.19	0	4	957A-3X-1-4	4449	585.5				0.70	12.5	1.10	120.9	6.70		0.05
267	437-72	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4		6.30	111.1	34.1			1.10	0.50				
268	438-73	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		2.30										
269	439-74	py	Py VI	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		17.6	1.80				67.3	0.70	0.70	0.30		0.10
270	441-76	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		40.5	3.00	12.4	1.20		105.9					

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U	
226	373-8	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		43.3		0.40	2.10	0.80	0.10	850.3	10.5	24.9	0.40	3.00	
227	374-9	py	Py VI	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		3.40		0.10	2.30	0.10	0.10	1125	4.40	23.9		0.10	
228	376-11	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		30.3		4.60		75.7		3.10	10.8		0.20	0.01	
229	377-12	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		0.70		0.50				659.0	5.10	80.0	0.10	0.002	
230	378-13	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.30		0.40	0.30		0.04	0.50	30.0	5.50	4.10	0.30	0.20	
231	379-14	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		0.40					0.03	1251	4.10	58.9	0.10		
232	381-16	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		6.00		0.10	2.40	0.10	2.00	1209	7.10	32.2	2.60	0.01	
233	382-17	py	Py III	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.10	9.50	0.02	0.10	0.90	0.04	0.30	141.4	45.4	3.00	2.60	0.40	
234	385-20	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.10	0.80			4.20		0.70	2314	160.6	18.4	0.30	0.10	
235	386-21	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		0.20			1.90		0.10	753.8	6.30	17.4		0.02	
236	388-23	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		13.4		1.30	1.80	2.10	1.10	1578	27.6	7.80		1.30	
237	389-24	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3				0.20			2.90	1823	10.1	179.9			
238	390-25	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3			0.04		5.70		1.10	960.4		93.3			
239	391-26	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.30	49.8			1.10		1.50	1026	12.3	34.5	3.30	0.50	
240	393-28	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		20.5		0.40	4.30		0.40	917.2	5.10		0.20	0.10	
241	394-29	py	Py III	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3	0.20	90.5			3.50	0.02	2.30	250.3		12.1		0.003	
242	397-32	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3					1.30		0.10	965.7		51.3			
243	398-33	py	Py IV	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		2.50				0.30	1.00	204.5	3.90	21.7	0.50	0.01	
244	400-35	py	Py I	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		34.8		1.40			0.40	577.7		15.3		0.20	
245	401-36	py	Py VI	1	116.19	4	10b	957E-17R-1-3		2.70					0.40	758.1		44.4			
246	402-37	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		152.5		6.00		8.10	2.00	2.6		0.40		0.02	
247	403-38	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	0.20	7.90		1.70		0.10	0.05				0.002		
248	405-40	py	Py VI	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	0.20	3.00	0.10	0.20		0.40	0.80	831.7		24.2		0.003	
249	406-41	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		59.6		1.90		1.30	2.90	301.8	12.4	11.5		0.10	
250	409-44	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	0.10	1.10		0.40	1.30	0.03	0.40	519.2	5.00	22.9	0.10	0.10	
251	410-45	py	Py VI	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	1.20	36.0		0.40		4.20	1.00	3.4		0.30	0.30	2.00	
252	412-47	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		139.0	0.04	4.20		2.60	0.60	8.5		1.20	0.20	0.20	
253	413-48	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	44.5						0.94			1.78			
254	414-49	py	Py V	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		23.7		1.50	3.20	12.5	0.70	955.5	8.20	30.4	0.30	0.04	
255	415-50	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		3.50		0.10	0.60	0.70	0.10	13.5			0.002		
256	417-52	py	Py IV	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		27.1		0.40		4.90	6.30	472.5	21.9	21.4	2.20	0.50	
257	418-53	py	Py I	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		52.1		1.10		0.23							
258	421-56	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	45.7	2.26	0.22			0.39	1.00			2.14		0.05	
259	422-57	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	65.7	3.79				0.18	1.16						
260	424-59	cpy	-	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1	120.8									3.40			
261	425-60	py	Py IV	4	34.3	0	3	957M-7R-1-1		26.3		0.20		2.90	0.10				3.90	0.20	
262	426-61	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4	0.40	301.3		0.50		39.8		1.10		2.50			
263	430-65	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4	0.60	72.6		8.10		6.70						0.03	
264	433-68	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4	1.40	3.07		50.8		0.23				1.03		0.01	
265	434-69	sph	-	2	10.19	0	4	957A-3X-1-4	0.49		0.39	12.7		0.09						0.01	
266	436-71	sph	-	2	10.19	0	4	957A-3X-1-4	0.60	80.1	0.10	1.00		6.50				6.00		0.10	
267	437-72	py	Py IV	2	10.19	1	5	957A-3X-1-4	0.60	0.50				0.03	0.10	2.90	78.2	0.30		0.01	
268	438-73	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5					2.30								
269	439-74	py	Py VI	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5	0.20												
270	441-76	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		37.9		0.50		0.10	0.10	26.2	58.9		0.40		

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In
271	442-77	py	Py I	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		13.7	0.80	0.20					1.10			
272	445-80	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		3.60		0.20			4.00	0.50				
273	446-81	py	Py VI	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		21.7	3.40	1.20			40.3		0.40			
274	448-83	cpy	-	4	38.51	1	5	957M-8R-1-5				0.51				8.47			25.2	0.64
275	449-84	cpy	-	4	38.51	1	5	957M-8R-1-5			29.2	1.92			13.2		2.67		31.4	9.72
276	450-85	py	Py I	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		4.20		0.10			41.4		0.20			
277	451-86	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		372.6		1.05			14.8		0.69	0.33		
278	453-88	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		11.8		0.87				0.95				
279	454-89	py	Py I	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		25.4		0.10		0.40	2.30		1.00			
280	457-92	py	Py V	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		52.3		10.6			3.10		0.40		7.30	
281	458-93	py	Py V	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		6.00		0.80			15.0		0.60			
282	460-95	py	Py VI	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		44.5		0.21			1.87	0.96				0.09
283	461-96	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		267.8		5.50			18.8	1.00			14.7	
284	462-97	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7			47.6	0.55	1.45		3.47		2.98	9.53		0.97
285	463-98	cpy	-	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7			65.4	0.31			3.13	4.08	2.98	5.37	58.3	1.43
286	465-100	cpy	-	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7			543.7	96.4			0.60	2.90	2.80			
287	466-101	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		195.3		65.4			119.1	2.90	2.80			
288	469-104	py	Py I	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		206.7		75.1			33.7	1.80	6.70	1.40	5.80	0.10
289	470-105	py	Py V	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		198.0	454.4	34.9			22.4	1.60	2.80		4.90	
290	472-107	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		315.2	26.9	7.00			7.20	1.00	3.70			
291	473-108	py	Py V	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		314.3	8.10	71.6			76.1	0.90	1.80			
292	474-1	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		5.20	7.90	0.50			3.00		1.30	0.40	7.20	
293	475-2	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		6.80	8.70	0.50	0.70		5.00		2.70	0.30		0.10
294	477-4	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		7.29	7.36	2.03			0.37		2.05	0.38		0.04
295	478-5	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		114.6	1338	1006			175.5	245.6	12.7	0.98		
296	481-8	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		8.39	9.35	51.5			30.0	5.23	0.69			
297	482-9	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		191.4		25.9			17.9	8.53	1.06			
298	485-12	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	43386	2124		224.5		148.8	59.0	1036	17.0	119.8	103.7	0.06
299	487-14	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	12173	597.9		143.0		82.0	29.4	1041	18.4	150.2	52.6	
300	489-16	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		5.35	7.64	73.1			25.0	0.66	0.20			
301	490-17	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		10.6	7.40	28.7			2.10	1.50				
302	493-20	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		54.1	36.9	75.8			2.00	13.3				
303	494-21	mc	-	4	14.7	3	5	957M-3-1-11A		21.2	21.1	1.46			1.33	5.74				
304	496-23	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	13588	1442		504.5	0.52		91.0	1025	20.9	306.0	326.1	10.7
305	497-24	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		189.7	82.4	329.6			60.6	304.1	9.30		8.90	
306	498-25	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		180.0	34.6	184.3			49.9	120.0	16.4			
307	499-26	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	23133	1503		455.1	1.08		33.5	38.8	40.8	34.0	116.8	0.03
308	501-28	cpy	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A			1423	2.63			13.8	2.47		10.8		15.1
309	502-29	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		12.6		28.6	0.40		1.70	0.80	0.30			
310	505-32	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		1.48	1.41	0.48			0.13	1.50				
311	506-33	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		35.7	12.3	5.81			0.51	3.01				
312	508-35	cpy	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		1348	1348	2.56			10.8	6.11		13.4	29.4	15.4
313	509-36	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		5.90		0.05			4.20		0.40			
314	510-37	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		29.4					4.20		0.40		2.80	
315	511-38	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		3.30	22.5	1.10	0.10	0.10	0.50	17.6	14.1	0.10	1.70	

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Te	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U
271	442-77	py	Py I	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		0.20				0.02	0.60	13.6	211.6		1.30	0.20
272	445-80	py	Py IV	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5		0.30			1.80		0.04	17.9	83.2	7.40	0.20	0.01
273	446-81	py	Py VI	4	38.51	3	10a	957M-8R-1-5	0.20	12.0					1.40	27.9	6.60			
274	448-83	cpy	-	4	38.51	1	5	957M-8R-1-5	9.91		0.47		10.8		0.18					0.02
275	449-84	cpy	-	4	38.51	1	5	957M-8R-1-5	16.0						0.49		40.4			
276	450-85	py	Py I	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		90.3		0.25	1.00			299.5		12.6		0.002
277	451-86	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		28.0			2.39		0.56	409.8		17.6	0.48	0.13
278	453-88	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4						0.03	0.10	371.2		23.6	0.21	0.65
279	454-89	py	Py I	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4							0.10	50.9	78.3			
280	457-92	py	Py V	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4							0.10	850.0	15.3	41.0		0.00
281	458-93	py	Py V	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		3.20				0.10	0.10	668.7		20.0		
282	460-95	py	Py VI	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4		0.60				0.30		6.20	8.80			
283	461-96	mc	-	1	37.31	2	7	957C-13N-1-4	203.3		0.10		2.30		0.53	487.8		24.1		
284	462-97	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7	8.34							62.3	16.2	26.2	0.30	
285	463-98	cpy	-	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7	1.29							251.1				
286	465-100	cpy	-	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		14.6		0.66				115.6	32.4		4.00	
287	466-101	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		77.7		0.50		9.90	0.30	441.6		5.00	3.90	
288	469-104	py	Py I	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		146.1	0.10	0.30		33.9		67.8	6.30	3.90	3.00	
289	470-105	py	Py V	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		129.4				15.3		166.3	10.4	3.00	1.60	
290	472-107	py	Py IV	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		77.9				19.8	0.10	61.4	9.20	1.60	1.10	
291	473-108	py	Py V	1	63.58	3	10a	957E-6R-1-7		16.6	0.10	1.10		1.50		43.7		0.20	0.30	
292	474-1	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		2.60		0.20		6.30		0.90		19.6		
293	475-2	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		9.70				4.50				0.30	0.53	0.003
294	477-4	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		0.96	0.09			2.68				4.41	0.06	
295	478-5	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		82.5		15.2		12.5				4.41	0.06	
296	481-8	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		110.1		2.70		6.51		23.4		0.34	0.34	
297	482-9	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		5.23		1.12		0.86			18.9	4.79	0.11	
298	485-12	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		16.9		84.1		1.36				5.28	0.76	
299	487-14	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		5.48	0.11	52.9		0.03		0.29		0.67	0.15	
300	489-16	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		25.4		0.82		1.31		0.73	14.0	3.27	0.04	
301	490-17	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		51.7		0.90		3.80		31.2	6.30	1.50	0.10	
302	493-20	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		145.9		214.4		10.1		8.10	5.60	0.30	0.30	
303	494-21	mc	-	4	14.7	3	5	957M-3-1-11A		20.0	0.04	0.80		3.65		6.38		1.48	0.07	
304	496-23	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		2.26		88.9		0.08						
305	497-24	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		34.9	0.10	12.0		6.40			17.3	15.5	0.10	
306	498-25	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		52.5	0.04	17.4		8.00		0.80		0.30	0.05	
307	499-26	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	0.12	11.2		66.6		0.29				0.14	1.08	
308	501-28	cpy	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	27.5								36.4	0.89	0.89	
309	502-29	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		0.50		2.60		0.30		8.70		0.40	0.40	
310	505-32	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		4.71		0.10		6.07		0.43		2.00	0.01	
311	506-33	mc	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A		44.8		0.74		0.64		5.00		0.20	0.20	
312	508-35	cpy	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11A	28.9		0.17						0.89	0.89	0.01	
313	509-36	py	Py V	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11A		1.30			1.40		0.10	1072	46.0	0.30	0.30	
314	510-37	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		0.90	0.04	0.10	4.50		0.02	1242	13.7	0.30	0.01	
315	511-38	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		29.6		0.20	0.50	3.40		0.01	0.20	0.50	0.50	0.002

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Fe	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	As	Cd	Mn	Ga	Ge	In	
316	513-40	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		0.80					2.20	0.60					
317	514-41	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		13.6		0.20			6.60	0.70		0.40			
318	517-44	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		195.1		24.3			110.8	0.40		9.80			
319	518-45	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		159.3	50.6	46.8			40.1	0.40					
320	520-47	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11B	21211	1285		4.77	0.43		990.4	32.6		193.8	30.4	34.5	
321	522-49	cpy	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		2.70	43.6	0.11			2.76	1.36	1.23	4.08	3.70	0.02	
322	523-50	py	Py III	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		15.4	1.10				1.02	0.60					
323	525-52	mc	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		62.9	15.1	0.50	0.44		18.6	0.34		3.21			
324	526-53	py	Py VI	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		11.8	52.2	0.30			7.50	0.50		7.70		0.10	
325	529-56	py	Py V	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		5.70		0.50				0.70					
326	530-57	py	Py V	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E			38.8		0.98				0.85	3.93	5.63	2.94	
327	532-59	cpy	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		48.9	48.6					1.96	3.43		3.60		
328	533-60	cpy	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		17.4	69.6	0.26				4.91	3.75		2.55		
329	534-61	cpy	-	1	78	1	5	957E-9R-1-3A			56.9					2.89	2.89	20.6	11.6		
330	535-62	cpy	-	1	78	1	5	957E-9R-1-3A				3.50				0.20		2.70			
331	537-64	py	Py VI	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A			8.10					0.40		3.10			
332	538-65	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A				8.10				0.40		9.70			
333	541-68	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		3.40		0.10				0.40		8.60			
334	542-69	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A				0.10				0.40					
335	544-71	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A			1.70					1.20					
336	545-72	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		2.10	3.00	2.90				3.10					
337	546-73	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		32.1	2.20	20.8	1.60			1.00		0.40			
338	547-74	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		548.8	2.20	64.2				0.90					
339	549-76	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		14.2	2.20	1.30				1.10					
340	550-77	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		146.3	6.20	6.20				0.60					
341	553-80	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		24.2	99.3	18.8	1.90			1923		4.90		0.10	
342	554-81	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		9.30	64.0	7.60				19.2				0.04	
343	556-83	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		127.6	60.4	31.5				14.9					
344	557-84	py	Py VI	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		52.2	4.00	29.5	0.60			1.30					
345	558-85	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		19.9						0.30					
346	559-86	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		170.4	3.10	0.05				0.40					
347	561-88	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		99.6	2.50	28.2				0.80					
348	562-89	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		259.0	3.00					1.50					
349	566-93	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		6.50	2.00	17.4				0.80				0.10	
350	568-95	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		36.6						0.50					
351	571-98	py	Py III	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		143.7	5.00	14.1	0.90			2.40					
352	573-100	py	Py III	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		213.7		3.30				0.40					
353	574-101	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		44.0		20.2				1.70					
354	577-104	py	Py VI	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		269.3	13.0					8.00					
355	578-105	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		658.0		2.80				1.20					
356	580-107	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		168.2	2.60					16.4					
357	581-108	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6		243.1	1.40	1.00	0.60			39.7			8.70	0.10	

Appendix A3 cont. Individual trace element LA-ICP-MS analyses for sulfides from the TAG deposit (data in ppm)

No.	Sample ID	Mineral	Pyrite Type	TAG area	mbsf	Min. Zone	Min. Type	Section	Sn	Mo	W	Sb	Tl	Bi	Co	Ni	Se	V	U
316	513-40	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B	0.20				1.00		116.0	60.8	12.4	0.30	0.01
317	514-41	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		12.3				0.10	238.4		21.9	0.20	
318	517-44	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B		21.3		2.20	0.30	0.10	240.5			0.30	0.10
319	518-45	py	Py IV	4	14.7	1	5	957M-3-1-11B	0.20	14.0		2.00	1.00	0.60	221.8	7.30		0.30	0.04
320	520-47	sph	-	4	14.7	3	9	957M-3-1-11B	6.82	19.3		21.2	1.77	0.01	9.24	8.41		0.52	
321	522-49	cpy	Py III	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E	28.3						37.8		16.1	0.20	
322	523-50	py	Py III	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E	0.10						603.5		52.9		
323	525-52	mc	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E						0.09	671.9		81.9		0.002
324	526-53	py	Py VI	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		2.20		0.30	0.10	0.03	142.5	9.00		0.20	
325	529-56	py	Py V	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E		0.80	0.10	0.20		0.10	57.0		22.1	0.30	
326	530-57	py	Py V	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E				0.20	1.50	0.10	183.0				
327	532-59	cpy	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E	87.9			0.15			9.40				
328	533-60	cpy	-	1	32.35	2	8	957C-11N-2-1E	13.3						3.26			0.87	
329	534-61	cpy	-	1	78	1	5	957E-9R-1-3A	44.7	1.31					117.5			0.61	
330	535-62	cpy	-	1	78	1	5	957E-9R-1-3A	2.10	2.94					112.2				
331	537-64	py	Py VI	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	2.10	2.94					112.2				
332	538-65	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	0.30	21.4		0.30	0.10	0.10	420.3	4.30	9.60	0.10	
333	541-68	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A		0.90		0.30	0.10	0.10	418.6	22.4	28.7		
334	542-69	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A				0.10	9.80		817.3	41.6	43.3		
335	544-71	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A							975.5	48.7	13.3		0.01
336	545-72	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	78.5		0.10	0.20	2.50		49.6		12.7	1.00	0.02
337	546-73	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	136.5				4.10	0.10	1081	62.7	62.9	0.40	0.10
338	547-74	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	4.30			0.30	0.30	0.20	32.8		17.9	0.40	0.03
339	549-76	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	63.6			0.60	2.70	0.03	33.7				0.10
340	550-77	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	0.80						49.6				0.01
341	553-80	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	14.6		0.10		0.30		207.5				0.02
342	554-81	py	Py IV	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	8.40		0.04	0.40	0.40						2.10
343	556-83	py	Py V	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	71.3				3.00		18.3				0.03
344	557-84	py	Py VI	1	78	3	10a	957E-9R-1-3A	12.2				0.70		2.50				
345	558-85	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	0.20	0.30	0.03	0.10	0.02	0.04	190.5		14.3		
346	559-86	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	0.20					0.05	23.8		8.5		
347	561-88	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	2.00		0.05	2.30	0.10	0.10					
348	562-89	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	0.80				1.50						
349	566-93	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6			0.10		0.04	0.04	1018		51.9		0.01
350	568-95	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	5.30				0.03	0.10	253.2	28.6	12.7		
351	571-98	py	Py III	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6				1.90	0.60	0.10	129.3	12.4			0.03
352	573-100	py	Py III	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	0.40	25.8			1.20	0.10	44.0		0.20		0.60
353	574-101	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	4.40				0.80	0.10	42.8		0.60		0.10
354	577-104	py	Py VI	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	22.9			0.50	0.10	0.10	3.80		0.50		0.02
355	578-105	py	Py V	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6							75.1				
356	580-107	py	Py I	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	5.90			0.20	0.10	0.10	12.9				0.30
357	581-108	py	Py IV	1	15.39	2	7	957C-5N-1-6	1.50				0.80						

Complete trace element dataset of LA-ICP-MS analyses of selected minerals in ODP Leg 158 drill cores from the TAG Hydrothermal Mound. Sample ID, mineral phases, mineralization type, and location in the deposit are indicated. Blanks indicate below detection limit or not detected. Sample ID is an internal analytical ID.

Appendix A4. Calculated proportions of trace elements in each pyrite type as displayed in Figure 2.15.

Pyrite type	Modal abundance %	Co	Se	Ni	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	Cd	Ga	Ge	In	Sn	Bi	As	Mo	Sb	Cu	Tl	Te	Mn	W	V	U	Total trace elements	% total trace elements
I	1	1.0	0.6	1.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.8	0.3	0.7	0.8	1.7	1.1	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.1	0.4	0.0	0.8	0.4	0.2	12.6	0.5
II	4	0.2	1.5	1.4	13.8	9.9	3.5	5.4	8.4	6.1	6.8	4.7	-	1.5	3.2	14.1	2.2	2.5	19.7	-	8.1	4.8	16.2	2.5	136.3	5.9
III	31	39.1	41.3	17.6	6.2	25.3	25.3	12.9	14.3	48.9	26.9	28.0	19.6	44.7	36.1	26.5	10.4	27.7	11.6	28.1	3.4	39.4	24.8	39.0	597.2	26.0
IV	43	43.9	38.5	65.2	46.5	34.2	34.7	59.9	36.6	19.2	41.7	26.4	59.8	27.4	31.8	37.0	29.9	46.7	41.5	42.3	17.7	36.8	39.0	43.3	900.0	39.1
V	14	8.9	13.3	11.8	27.6	24.0	18.1	14.9	13.8	7.9	18.3	9.7	10.8	16.0	16.0	18.3	52.7	15.7	23.2	22.1	70.1	11.0	11.9	6.6	442.5	19.2
VI	7	7.0	4.8	2.8	5.8	6.4	18.1	6.8	26.1	17.6	5.6	30.4	8.1	9.4	12.5	3.8	4.4	6.8	4.0	7.1	0.7	7.2	7.7	8.2	211.4	9.2
Sum		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	2300.0	100.0

Calculated proportions of trace elements in each pyrite type based on average trace element contents of pyrite (Table 2.4) and modal abundances of each pyrite type estimated from petrography.

Appendix A5. Box and whisker plots comparing variations in TAG pyrite LA-ICP-MS trace element concentrations from TAG sub-seafloor samples (Chapter 2), TAG surface pyrite samples and other MOR basalt-hosted massive sulfide deposits. Data are in ppm.

Boxes show the interquartile range, the median is displayed as an internal line, and whiskers show the entire data range. Average values are shown by a red diamond. The number of analyses are indicated in parentheses. The TAG surface LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite sand is from Keith et al. (2016). Basalt-hosted MOR LA-ICP-MS data are from Melekestseva et al. (2012, 2014, 2017), Wohlgemuth-Ueberwasser et al. (2015), Keith et al. (2016), and Wang et al. (2017). Basalt-hosted MOR sample sites compiled here are: Turtle Pits, Comfortless Cove, TAG, Logatchev-1, Semenov-2, Semenov-4 (all Mid-Atlantic Ridge), Wocan-1 and Wocan-2 (Carlsberg Ridge), and Meso Zone (Central Indian Ridge).

Appendix A5. Box and whisker plots comparing variations in TAG pyrite LA-ICP-MS trace element concentrations from TAG sub-seafloor samples (Chapter 2), TAG surface pyrite samples and other MOR basalt-hosted massive sulfide deposits. Data are in ppm.

Boxes show the interquartile range, the median is displayed as an internal line, and whiskers show the entire data range. Average values are shown by a red diamond. The number of analyses are indicated in parentheses. The TAG surface LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite sand is from Keith et al. (2016). Basalt-hosted MOR LA-ICP-MS data are from Melekestseva et al. (2012, 2014, 2017), Wohlgemuth-Ueberwasser et al. (2015), Keith et al. (2016), and Wang et al. (2017). Basalt-hosted MOR sample sites compiled here are: Turtle Pits, Comfortless Cove, TAG, Logatchev-1, Semenov-2, Semenov-4 (all Mid-Atlantic Ridge), Wocan-1 and Wocan-2 (Carlsberg Ridge), and Meso Zone (Central Indian Ridge).

Appendix A6. Comparison of concentrations for Fe and Ni calibrated on sulfide standards (other studies) and glass NIST standards (this study).

Standard	Fe (std)		Ni (std)		Fe (this study)			Ni (this study)		
	Min	Max	Min	Max	Avg.	SD	n	Avg.	SD	n
trans_1	569000	569000	49000	49000	560528	12643	46	50726	2366	46
PGE_Ni7B	568000	568000	47900	47900	554401	18504	47	47958	1844	47
GOR132	77902	82500	1000	1330	78635	1980	47	1244	420	47
T1	42956	53900	6.30	65.0	48916	1214	47	11.3	1.7	16
ATHO	26800	30400	2.40	80.0	24564	1197	9	16.0	1.5	5
KL2	83200	83200	83.4	139.0	83638	1761	9	112.9	3.3	9

Quality control comparison of Fe and Ni concentrations of standards used in this study calibrated on a) sulfide standards (data from GeoReM; Jochum et al. 2005), and b) on glass NIST standards this study. There is little variation for average trace element concentrations between the two methods.

Appendix A7. Geochemical zonation in the TAG deposit using bulk geochemical data from ODP Leg 158.

Appendix B

Supplementary information for Chapter 3

Appendix B1: All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field.

Appendix B2: Details of RN-10 sample preparation.

B2.1. Examples of downhole RN-10 samples

B2.2. Flow chart for RN-10 sample preparation

B2.3. RN-10 sample preparation documentation

Appendix B3: Electron microprobe analyses

B3.1. Major element EMPA analyses for metallic sulfide and Au-bearing phases in downhole RN-10 scale samples. Data deviating more than +/- 2% from 100 wt.% were not used in statistics. All data is included to show the difficulty in producing analyses on intimately-intergrown and very fine-grained minerals.

B3.2. Major element EMPA analyses for silicates in downhole RN-10 scale samples.

Appendix B4: Mineralogical report on RN-10 downhole samples produced for HS Orka and ISOR, Iceland. XRD spectra for downhole RN-10 scale samples are at the end of the report.

Appendix B5: Explanation of calculations performed in section 3.5.4.

B5.1. Mass accumulation rate of scales in downhole pipes of well RN-10 and a mass accumulation rate estimation

B5.2. Estimation of the potential maximum metal fluxes for well RN-10 over the estimated lifetime of the Reykjanes geothermal system

B5.3. Calculation of the relative contribution to the total metal accumulation of mineralization in surface versus down hole pipes for well RN-10

Appendix B6: Location of samples taken in all Reykjanes geothermal wells in this study.

Appendix B1. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Source	Sampling location	Location/well	Year taken	Group	DH depth (m)	Pbar	WP	SiO2 wt. %	Al2O3 wt. %	CaO wt. %	Na2O wt. %	K2O wt. %	MnO wt. %	MgO wt. %	TiO2 wt. %	P2O3 wt. %	
1	RNSS-2014-2	7	GL	GL	2014	5	-	-	-	>64.2	0.36	0.31	0.32	0.12	0.05	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	
2	1GL*	1	GL	GL	na	5	-	1	H	84.1	0.1	0.6	2.9	0.4	0.02	0.0			
3	2GL06	1	GL	GL	na	5	-	1	-	56.6	0.4	1.1	3.2	0.8	0.02	0.2			
4	3GL06	1	GL	GL	na	5	-	1	-	50.8	0.1	1.1	4.6	0.8	0.03	0.1			
5	14_00	1	SS	SS	na	5	-	11	H	82.1	2.7	0.7	1.4	0.9	0.4	0.6			
6	RN24-2014-1	7	SS	SS	2014	5	-		M	28.24	3.00	1.40	1.73	0.24	0.57	6.98	<0.02		
7	42_00 (Vent house)	1	VH	VH	na	5	-	1	H	92.2	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.1	<0.01			
8	HP15_23RN6-07	3	dnstr	RN-23	2007	4	-	22	H	2.8	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.06	0.3			
9	RN11-2013-4	7	dnstr	RN-11	2013	4	-		H	15.21	0.93	0.45	0.22	<0.12	1.16	0.33	<0.02		
10	LPI_13TRN4-04	3	dnstr	RN-13	2004	4	-	28-26	L	84.0	1.5	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.030			
11	LP4_15RN6-05	3	dnstr	RN-15	2005	4	-	24.5	L	48.9	4.6	1.1	1.3	1.1	0.1	0.2			
12	LPI1_18RN2-07	3	dnstr	RN-18	2007	4	-	22	L	5.3	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.020	0.4	0.8			
13	LPI0_15RN3-07	3	dnstr	RN-15	2007	4	-	22	L	10.9	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.7	2.7			
14	RN13B-2014-2	7	dnstr	RN-13B	2014	4	-		L	6.38	0.28	0.21	0.28	<0.12	0.28	0.22	<0.02		
15	RN12-2014-16	7	dnstr	RN-12	2014	4	-		M	14.29	0.81	0.67	0.39	<0.12	>1	0.75	<0.02		
16	MP4_12RN1-07	3	dnstr	RN-12	2007	4	-	22	M	12.53	0.81	0.53	0.57	0.11	1.16	1.15			
17	RN26-2014-2	7	dnstr	RN-26	2014	4	-		H	1.78	0.15	0.10	0.32	<0.12	0.07	0.08	<0.02		
18	RN24-2007-3	7	dnstr	RN-24	2007	4	-		M	3.10	0.19	0.11	0.05	<0.12	0.32	0.17	<0.02		
19	MP9_24RNE1	3/4	dnstr	RN-24	2007	4	-	22	M	0.84	0.06	0.04	0.07	<0.01	0.08	0.01	0.002	<0.01	
20	RN28-2014-2	7	dnstr	RN-28	2014	4	-		H	0.68	0.09	0.07	0.20	<0.12	0.02	0.05	<0.02		
21	HP10_23RNEO-07	3	dnstr	RN-23	2007	4	-	43	H	2.3	0.4	0.2	<0.01	0.1	0.02	0.4			
22	RN23-2014-3	7	dnstr	RN-23	2014	4	-		H	3.06	0.40	0.20	0.39	<0.12	0.04	0.60	<0.02		
23	HP14_23RN5-07	3	dnstr	RN-23	2007	4	-	22	H	1.9	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.04	0.2			
24	HP13_23RN4-07	3	dnstr	RN-23	2007	4	-	22	H	4.2	0.3	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.10	0.2			
25	HP16_23RN1_06RE	3	dnstr	RN-23	2006	4	-	22	H	<0.01	0.3	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01			
26	HP17_23RN1_09	3	dnstr	RN-23	2009	4	-	22	H	<0.01	0.2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01			
27	HP8_22RN16-07	2	dnstr	RN-22	2007	4	-	22	H	1.9	0.1	0.1	0.09	0.06	0.11	0.1			
28	RN10-2003-2C	7	dnstr	RN-10	2003	4	-		H	32.95	0.42	0.25	0.67	0.12	0.29	0.07	<0.02		
29	RN14B-2014-2	7	dnstr	RN-14B	2014	4	-		H	10.31	0.23	0.20	0.53	<0.12	0.14	0.56	<0.02		
30	14BRN1_2006	4	dnstr	RN-14B	2009	4	-		H	<0.01	0.11	<0.01	0.02		<0.1	<0.01			
31	HP19_14RN2-07	3	dnstr	RN-14	2007	4	-	22	H	2.0	0.4	0.2	0.1	<0.01	0.1	0.5			
32	RN11-2014-4	7	dnstr	RN-11	2014	4	-		H	11.72	0.66	0.32	0.32	<0.12	0.79	0.27	<0.02		

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	C Total wt. %	LOI wt. %	Cu wt. %	Zn wt. %	Pb wt. %	Fe wt. %	S wt. %	Au ppm	Ag ppm	As ppm	Sb ppm	Tl ppm	Hg ppm	Cd ppm
1	RNSS-2014-2	GL	GL	-			0.138	0.277	0.138	0.06	0.12	0.0978	112	<0.5	1.9	<0.1	<1	<2
2	1GL*	GL	GL	H		12.0			0.0	0.1	0.0	<0.01	0.15	2	1	<0.1		<0.7
3	2GL06	GL	GL	-	0.02	34.8			0.0	0.5	0.0	0.3	<5	10	<0.1	<0.1	<1	<30
4	3GL06	GL	GL	-	0.02	37.3			0.0		0.0	0.4	<5	11	<0.1	<0.1	<1	<30
5	14_00	SS	SS	H	0.04	6.0		0.4	0.1	3.2	0.4	4	38	8	1	0.1	<1	<30
6	RN24-2014-1	SS	SS	M			1.85	10.3	0.62	15	7.99	137	131	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	271
7	42_00 (Vent house)	VH	VH	H		6.4			0.0	0.2	0.1	0.2	10	1	3	<0.1	<1	<0.3
8	HP15_23RN6-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.02	14.2		44.9	0.6	5.1	29.8	82.4	1290	25	<0.1	<0.1	<1	5220
9	RN11-2013-4	dnstr	RN-11	H			11.4	17.5	5.62	12.7	16	103	2700	40.6	3.3	<0.1	<1	145
10	LPI_13TRN4-04	dnstr	RN-13	L	0.06	5.7		2.8	1.4	1.1	2.2	229	1410	56	35	0.2	<1	<30
11	LP4_15RN6-05	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.18	10.8		8.5	5.6	2.2	8.7	414	6570	46	47	0.1	14	80
12	LP11_18RN2-07	dnstr	RN-18	L	0.15	11.5		17.9	11.5	7.0	22.2	32	21300	<0.5	<0.1	0.2	<1	160
13	LP10_15RN3-07	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.14	13.1		13.6	10.6	7.8	17.6	137	14100	<0.5	10	<0.1	<1	120
14	RN13B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-13B	L			2.17	36.3	10.3	8.39	24.9	79.4	10000	16.6	6.7	<0.1	<1	72
15	RN12-2014-16	dnstr	RN-12	M			12.9	16	11.6	10.8	16	421	5470	105	16.4	<0.1	<1	52
16	MP4_12RN1-07	dnstr	RN-12	M	0.09	15.3		13.9	10.5	9.3	16.5	328	6060	471	45	<0.1	<1	100
17	RN26-2014-2	dnstr	RN-26	H			14.7	42.6	6.59	3.59	> 25.0	90.4	4380	486	25.1	<0.1	<1	283
18	RN24-2007-3	dnstr	RN-24	M			23.8	21.6	15.7	5.55	23.4	324	13300	65	12.2	<0.1	<1	177
19	MP9_24RNE1	dnstr	RN-24	M		10.7		20.7	16.7	7.4	23.3	359	15200	100	4	0.2	46	233
20	RN28-2014-2	dnstr	RN-28	H			5.19	52.3	0.65	5.03	> 25.0	121	1040	36.6	<0.1	<0.1	<1	16200
21	HP10_23RNEO-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.03	16.5		56.3	0.0	3.4	31.2	341	193	<0.5	3	<0.1	<1	12600
22	RN23-2014-3	dnstr	RN-23	H			14.9	34.1	9.9	3.67	24.2	77.8	3490	15.2	3.3	<0.1	<1	918
23	HP14_23RN5-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.04	15.6		44.6	0.1	3.1	30.6	116	1670	27	<0.1	<0.1	<1	8930
24	HP13_23RN4-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.04	15.8		40.9	0.4	4.3	26.4	54.6	2250	396	7	<0.1	<1	4730
25	HP16_23RN1_06RE	dnstr	RN-23	H		0.0		33.3	0.5	6.4	25.0	87.2	2830	589	19	0.3	20	3650
26	HP17_23RN1_09	dnstr	RN-23	H		0.0		43.2	1.9	4.8	29.1	64.1	3000	747	24	0.1	13	4900
27	HP8_22RN16-07	dnstr	RN-22	H	0.04	16.4		42.3	1.0	3.8	28.3	79.9	3510	454	21	<0.1	<1000	4380
28	RN10-2003-2C	dnstr	RN-10	H			3.64	23.2	1.9	9.16	17.2	225	2410	833	36.5	0.6	<1	140
29	RN14B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-14B	H			9.29	36.1	7.06	3.85	22.6	74.6	4660	11.4	6.8	<0.1	<1	285
30	14BRN1_2006	dnstr	RN-14B	H			0.506	1.53	0.0524	0.62	1.05	1.28	176	2.1	<0.1	<0.1	5	70
31	HP19_14RN2-07	dnstr	RN-14	H	0.07	13.7		42.7	1.3	3.4	28.7	4.51	7200	1010	38	<0.1	5	1720
32	RN11-2014-4	dnstr	RN-11	H			14.3	20.1	7.49	11.7	19.7	77.4	4090	72	4.6	<0.1	<1	180

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	In ppm	Bi ppm	Ge ppm	Ga ppm	Mo ppm	V ppm	Sn ppm	W ppm	Ni ppm	Cr ppm	Co ppm	Te ppm	Se ppm	Ir ppm
1	RNSS-2014-2	GL	GL	-	<0.2	<2	<0.7	23.2	<1	7	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	<0.2	<6	<3	<5
2	IGL*	GL	GL	H	<2	<2	<1	<1	<1	<2	<1	<1	<1	<5	2	<3	<3	<5
3	2GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	20	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1	20	20	<5
4	3GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	6	<1	<1	<20	47	<1	<3	<3	<5
5	14_00	SS	SS	H	<0.2	<0.4	<1	10	6	13	<1	<1	<20	113	2	9	9	<5
6	RN24-2014-1	SS	SS	M	<0.2	2	<0.7	15.1	8	30	<0.5	<0.7	<10	26	22.3	67	142	<5
7	42_00 (Vent house)	VH	VH	H	<2	<0.4	<1	63	<2	<5	<1	8	<1	<5	<1	<3	<3	<5
8	HP15_23RN6-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.06	0.7	<1	1	2	119	<1	<1	<20	<5	129	497	0.06	0.06
9	RN11-2013-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4.1	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	4	10	284	<5
10	LPI_13TRN4-04	dnstr	RN-13	L	<0.2	<0.4	<1	43	10	67	<1	<1	<20	123	<1	53	53	<5
11	LP4_15RN6-05	dnstr	RN-15	L	<0.2	<0.4	<1	9	12	72	1	<1	<20	<5	<1	382	<5	<5
12	LP11_18RN2-07	dnstr	RN-18	L	<0.2	0.4	<1	3	13	41	<1	<1	<20	<5	12	530	<5	<5
13	LP10_15RN3-07	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.04	<0.4	<1	7	7	111	<1	<1	<20	<5	19	490	0.04	<5
14	RN13B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-13B	L	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4.6	3	17	<0.5	1.1	30	<5	25.9	<6	298	<5
15	RN12-2014-16	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	3.7	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	0.9	49	542	<5
16	MP4_12RNI-07	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.2	1.1	<1	3	<2	20	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1	546	<5	<5
17	RN26-2014-2	dnstr	RN-26	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.1	6	10	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	20.3	<6	108	<5
18	RN24-2007-3	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.1	4	23	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	2.2	<6	1030	<5
19	MP9_24RNE1	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	<5	<1	<1	<20	43	<1	1350	<5	<5
20	RN28-2014-2	dnstr	RN-28	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.8	12	43	6.9	<0.7	<10	<5	129	<6	1250	<5
21	HP10_23RNEO-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	0.6	<1	5	5	76	1	<1	<20	<5	364	923	923	<5
22	RN23-2014-3	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.5	4	49	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	34.7	<6	396	<5
23	HP14_23RN5-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	1.1	<1	<1	7	22	<1	<1	<20	<5	213	578	578	<5
24	HP13_23RN4-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	22	18	<1	<1	<20	<5	135	367	367	<5
25	HP16_23RNI_06RE	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1	70	13	<0.5	2	<10	35	136	454	454	<5
26	HP17_23RNI_09	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1	10	35	<0.5	1.7	<10	<5	138	606	606	<5
27	HP8_22RNI16-07	dnstr	RN-22	H	<0.2	0.8	<1	1	10	10	<1	<1	<20	92	88	379	379	<5
28	RN10-2003-2C	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	6.3	17	28	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	7.6	24	138	<5
29	RN14B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-14B	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.6	3	30	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	49.5	<6	536	<5
30	14BRNI_2006	dnstr	RN-14B	H	<0.2	<2	1	0.4	26	6	<0.5	<0.7	<10	402	7	<6	10.9	<5
31	HP19_14RN2-07	dnstr	RN-14	H	<0.2	<0.4	<1	4	33	187	<1	<1	<20	<5	146	<6	149	<5
32	RN11-2014-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.7	<1	<5	<0.5	2	20	<5	4.2	<6	344	<5

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Pt ppb	Pd ppb	Re ppm	Ba ppm	Rb ppm	Sr ppm	Cs ppm	Li ppm	Be ppm	B ppm	Br ppm	F ppm	U ppm
1	RNSS-2014-2	GL	GL	-				5	5.6	13	0.2	<3	<3	30	1.1	<0.1	
2	1GL*	GL	GL	H				22	<15	20	<0.5	<1	<1	119	119	<0.5	
3	2GL06	GL	GL	-				36	14	36	<0.5	<1	<1	299	299	<0.1	
4	3GL06	GL	GL	-				41	15	43	<0.5	<1	<1	429	429	<0.1	
5	14_00	SS	SS	H				126	33	34	1.3	<1	<1	54	54	<0.1	
6	RN24-2014-1	SS	SS	M				24	7.1	42	<0.1	11	11	<10	52.9	<0.01	<0.1
7	42_00 (Vent house)	VH	VH	H				8	6	4	<0.5	1	1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
8	HP15_23RN6-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.51	11.94		15	6	7	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
9	RN11-2013-4	dnstr	RN-11	H				14	3.6	19	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	0.2	<0.1
10	LPI_13TRN4-04	dnstr	RN-13	L				31	18	10	0.9	2	2	2.8	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
11	LP4_15RN6-05	dnstr	RN-15	L				185	41	57	2.1	1	1	<0.5	<0.5	0.3	<0.1
12	LP11_18RN2-07	dnstr	RN-18	L				5	<2	5	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
13	LP10_15RN3-07	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.32	5.85		8	<2	8	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
14	RN13B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-13B	L				<3	0.7	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	0.5	<0.1
15	RN12-2014-16	dnstr	RN-12	M				9	2.7	19	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
16	MP4_12RN1-07	dnstr	RN-12	M				26	4	12	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
17	RN26-2014-2	dnstr	RN-26	H				5	0.6	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	6.6	0.1	0.1
18	RN24-2007-3	dnstr	RN-24	M				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
19	MP9_24RNE1	dnstr	RN-24	M				5	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
20	RN28-2014-2	dnstr	RN-28	H				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
21	HP10_23RNEO-07	dnstr	RN-23	H				28	<2	7	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	0.2	<0.1
22	RN23-2014-3	dnstr	RN-23	H				10	0.5	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	4.9	<0.1	<0.1
23	HP14_23RN5-07	dnstr	RN-23	H				6	<2	4	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	0.1	0.1
24	HP13_23RN4-07	dnstr	RN-23	H				12	<2	9	<0.5	<1	<1	46.4	46.4	<0.1	<0.1
25	HP16_23RN1_06RE	dnstr	RN-23	H				9	<0.4	5	<0.1	<3	<3	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
26	HP17_23RN1_09	dnstr	RN-23	H				<3	1	<3	<0.1	<3	<3	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
27	HP8_22RN16-07	dnstr	RN-22	H				5	<2	4	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	0.5	0.5
28	RN10-2003-2C	dnstr	RN-10	H				12	5.7	15	0.3	<3	<3	40	22.7	<0.01	<0.1
29	RN14B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-14B	H				<3	1.2	13	<0.1	9	9	<10	15.9	0.2	0.2
30	14BRN1_2006	dnstr	RN-14B	H				7	<0.4	<3	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	2.8	<0.1	<0.1
31	HP19_14RN2-07	dnstr	RN-14	H				5	<2	3	<0.5	<1	<1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1
32	RN11-2014-4	dnstr	RN-11	H				9	2.9	19	0.3	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	0.3	0.3

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Th ppm	Sc ppm	Y ppm	Zr ppm	Nb ppm	Hf ppm	Ta ppm	La ppm	Ce ppm	Pr ppm	Nd ppm	Sm ppm	Eu ppm
1	RNSS-2014-2	GL	GL	-	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	1.5	1.3	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
2	1GL*	GL	GL	H	<2		<1	11	-5	<1	<0.1	<0.5	<3	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2
3	2GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.1	2.1	<2	6	<1	<1	<0.1	3.2	0.3	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
4	3GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.1	1.1	<2	<4	<1	<1	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
5	14_00	SS	SS	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<1	<0.1	0.6	0.3	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
6	RN24-2014-1	SS	SS	M	0.1	0.8	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.9	0.9	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
7	42_00 (Vent house)	VH	VH	H	<0.1	<1	<1	<1	1	<1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
8	HP15_23RN6-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.3	1	0.09	0.4	<0.1	<0.05
9	RN11-2013-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
10	LP1_13TRN4-04	dnstr	RN-13	L	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.3	0.3	<0.05	0.1	<0.1	<0.05
11	LP4_15RN6-05	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.4	<0.1	<2	17	<1	0.4	0.5	1.5	2.7	0.3	1.2	<0.1	0.08
12	LP11_18RN2-07	dnstr	RN-18	L	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
13	LP10_15RN3-07	dnstr	RN-15	L	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.1	0.2	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
14	RN13B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-13B	L	0.7	<0.1	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	20	<0.2	0.7	0.9	<0.1	0.8	0.1	<0.1
15	RN12-2014-16	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	1.8	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.1	<0.1
16	MP4_12RN1-07	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
17	RN26-2014-2	dnstr	RN-26	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
18	RN24-2007-3	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.1	0.9	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.5	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
19	MP9_24RNE1	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.1	<1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
20	RN28-2014-2	dnstr	RN-28	H	<0.1	3.2	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
21	HP10_23RNEO-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.6	1.4	0.14	0.6	<0.1	<0.05
22	RN23-2014-3	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
23	HP14_23RN5-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.2	<0.1	<2	12	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.3	1.1	0.09	0.4	<0.1	<0.05
24	HP13_23RN4-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	8	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	0.4	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
25	HP16_23RN1_06RE	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.4	9	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.2	<0.1
26	HP17_23RN1_09	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
27	HP8_22RN16-07	dnstr	RN-22	H	0.1	<0.1	<2	7	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.4	1.1	0.1	0.4	<0.1	<0.05
28	RN10-2003-2C	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.7	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	14	1.4	1.2	18.8	3.2	<0.1
29	RN14B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-14B	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
30	14BRN1_2006	dnstr	RN-14B	H	0.6	0.3	3.1	<2.4	<2.4	1	<0.2	2.5	5.4	0.7	2.7	0.5	0.1
31	HP19_14RN2-07	dnstr	RN-14	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<1	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.2	0.5	0.07	0.4	<0.1	<0.05
32	RN11-2014-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	0.1	0.6	0.1	<2.4	<2.4	20	<0.2	1.4	1.4	<0.1	1.1	0.2	<0.1

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Gd ppm	Tb ppm	Dy ppm	Ho ppm	Er ppm	Tm ppm	Yb ppm	Lu ppm
1	RNSS-2014-2	GL	GL	-	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
2	1GL*	GL	GL	H								
3	2GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.05
4	3GL06	GL	GL	-	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.05
5	14_00	SS	SS	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.05
6	RN24-2014-1	SS	SS	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
7	42_00 (Venthouse)	VH	VH	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.05
8	HPI5_23RN6-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.1	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
9	RN11-2013-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
10	LPI_13TRN4-04	dnstr	RN-13	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
11	LP4_15RN6-05	dnstr	RN-15	L	0.2	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
12	LPI1_18RN2-07	dnstr	RN-18	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
13	LPI0_15RN3-07	dnstr	RN-15	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
14	RN13B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-13B	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
15	RN12-2014-16	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
16	MP4_12RNI-07	dnstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
17	RN26-2014-2	dnstr	RN-26	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
18	RN24-2007-3	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
19	MP9_24RNE1	dnstr	RN-24	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
20	RN28-2014-2	dnstr	RN-28	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
21	HPI0_23RNEO-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	0.1	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
22	RN23-2014-3	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
23	HPI4_23RN5-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
24	HPI3_23RN4-07	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	1.9	<0.04
25	HPI6_23RNI_06RE	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
26	HPI7_23RNI_09	dnstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
27	HP8_23RNI6-07	dnstr	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
28	RNI0-2003-2C	dnstr	RN-10	H	1	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
29	RNI4B-2014-2	dnstr	RN-14B	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
30	14BRNI_2006	dnstr	RN-14B	H	0.4	<0.1	0.5	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.3	0.06
31	HPI9_14RN2-07	dnstr	RN-14	H	0.1	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
32	RN11-2014-4	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Source	Sampling location	Location/well	Year taken	Group	DH depth (m)	Pbar	WP	SiO2 wt. %	Al2O3 wt. %	CaO wt. %	Na2O wt. %	K2O wt. %	MnO wt. %	MgO wt. %	TiO2 wt. %	P2O3 wt. %
33	RN11-2014-1	7	dnstr	RN-11	2014	4	-		H	5.88	0.28	0.21	0.20	<0.12	0.32	0.20	<0.02	
34	RN11-2013-2B	7	dnstr	RN-11	2013	4	-		H	19.85	1.25	0.66	0.51	0.12	>1	0.45	<0.02	
35	RN11-2007-5	7	dnstr	RN-11	2007	4	-		H	13.65	0.51	0.85	0.50	<0.12	0.94	0.32	<0.02	
36	HP5_11RN4-07	3	dnstr	RN-11	2007	4	-	22	H	12.3	0.5	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.8	0.3		
37	HP20_10RN8_03	3	dnstr	RN-10	2003	4	-	22	H	2.8	0.4	0.1	<0.01	<0.01	0.1	0.1		
38	RN10-2003-1	7	dnstr	RN-10	2003	4	-		H	>64.2	0.30	0.29	0.53	0.12	0.14	0.35	<0.02	
39	RN11-2013-1	7	dnstr	RN-11	2013	4	-		H	7.53	0.40	0.27	0.04	<0.12	0.42	0.25	<0.02	
40	RN21-2007-3	7	dnstr on OP	RN-21	2007	4	-		M	4.92	0.32	0.20	0.22	<0.12	0.35	0.48	<0.02	
41	MP7_21RN2-07	3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	2007	4	-	22	M	5.38	0.40	0.19	0.23	0.02	0.35	0.53		
42	RN26-2014-3	7	dnstr on OP	RN-26	2014	4	-		H	8.96	0.38	0.53	0.82	0.12	0.17	0.33	0.03	
43	MP3_12RN2-07	3	dnstr on OP	RN-12	2007	4	-	22	M	4.65	0.31	0.23	0.19	0.05	0.49	0.17		
44	LP9_15RN2-07	3	FFCV	RN-15	2007	4	-	26	L	2.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	<0.01	0.1	0.5		
45	RN12-2014-13	7	FFCV	RN-12	2014	4	-		M	10.87	0.79	0.35	<0.01	<0.12	0.84	1.34	<0.02	
46	RN12-2014-12	7	FFCV	RN-12	2014	4	-		M	12.75	0.89	0.49	0.04	<0.12	0.94	1.59	<0.02	
47	RN26-2014-4	7	FFCV	RN-26	2014	4	-		H	1.37	0.09	0.08	0.12	<0.12	0.05	0.17	<0.02	
48	RN24-2007-4	7	FFCV	RN-24	2007	4	-		M	1.75	0.09	0.04	0.08	<0.12	0.15	0.15	<0.02	
49	MP8_24RNE2	3/4	FFCV	RN-24	2007	4	-	30	M	2.14	0.15	0.11	0.09	<0.01	0.26	0.18	<0.001	<0.01
50	RN21-2007-4	7	FFCV	RN-21	2007	4	-		M	1.35	0.06	0.07	0.19	<0.12	0.11	0.07	<0.02	
51	MP6_21RNE2	3/4	FFCV	RN-21	2007	4	-	22	M	0.90	0.06	0.04	0.11	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.002	<0.01
52	MP5_21RNE1	3/4	FFCV	RN-21	2007	4	-	28	M	0.68	0.05	0.04	0.07	<0.01	0.06	0.07	0.002	<0.01
53	RN12-2014-15	7	FFCV	RN-12	2014	4	-		M	4.51	0.23	0.15	0.13	<0.12	0.41	0.22	<0.02	
54	MPI_12RNE1	3/4	FFCV	RN-12	2007	4	-	37	M	6.72	0.47	0.34	0.14	0.02	0.30	1.44	0.002	<0.01
55	MP2_12RNE2	3/4	FFCV	RN-12	2007	4	-	22	M	1.51	0.10	0.09	0.05	<0.01	0.14	0.19	<0.001	<0.01
56	RN11-2014-6B	7	FFCV	RN-11	2014	4	-		H	3.57	0.21	0.13	0.11	<0.12	0.18	0.27	<0.02	
57	RN11-2014-6C	7	FFCV	RN-11	2014	4	-		H	2.89	0.17	0.15	0.03	<0.12	0.17	0.20	<0.02	
58	RN11-2014-6A	7	FFCV	RN-11	2014	4	-		H	1.20	0.08	0.08	0.04	<0.12	0.11	0.07	<0.02	
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	3	FFCV	RN-11	2007	4	-	43	H	9.3	0.6	0.3	0.1	<0.01	0.2	1.1		
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	3	FFCV	RN-23	2007	4	-	43	H	2.5	0.5	0.1	<0.01	0.1	0.03	0.2		
61	RN22-2007-8	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	11.40	0.21	0.91	0.53	<0.12	0.29	0.22	<0.02	
62	RN22-2007-4	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	10.12	0.15	1.18	0.44	<0.12	0.28	0.23	<0.02	
63	RN22-2007-3	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	3.94	0.19	0.11	0.27	<0.12	0.12	0.12	<0.02	
64	RN22-2007-14	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	0.36	0.02	0.06	0.07	<0.12	0.03	0.03	<0.02	

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/well	WP	C Total wt.%	LOI wt.%	Cu wt.%	Zn wt.%	Pb wt.%	Fe wt.%	S wt.%	Au ppm	Ag ppm	As ppm	Sb ppm	Tl ppm	Hg ppm	Cd ppm
33	RN11-2014-1	dnstr	RN-11	H			18.6	22.4	9.35	10.5	22.3	89	6080	226	15	<0.1	<1	184
34	RN11-2013-2B	dnstr	RN-11	H			8.44	15.2	4.94	13.3	12.8	91.8	2140	62	4	<0.1	<1	110
35	RN11-2007-5	dnstr	RN-11	H			13.3	20.4	4.31	9.17	17.5	322	1570	352	14.1	<0.1	<1	162
36	HP5_11RN4-07	dnstr	RN-11	H	0.06	15.6	15.6	20.8	4.7	8.4	18.1	247	1670	313	16	<0.1	<1	220
37	HP20_10RN8_03	dnstr	RN-10	H	0.09	23.0	15.1	37.5	0.5	7.4	25.8	110	5260	733	23	<0.1	<1	3650
38	RN10-2003-1	dnstr	RN-10	H			0.862	7.84	1.61	2.38	5.19	146	1270	108	61	0.7	<1	21
39	RN11-2013-1	dnstr	RN-11	H			18.3	21.2	8.71	9.95	21	105	4820	245	18.1	<0.1	<1	163
40	RN21-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M			19.6	23	12.3	5.44	20.7	208	12400	187	39.3	<0.1	<1	229
41	MP7_21RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	0.12	13.2	22.8	22.6	13.1	5.4	20.9	201	10800	174	48	<0.1	<1	230
42	RN26-2014-3	dnstr on OP	RN-26	H			12.6	40.9	3.88	3.48	> 25.0	72.7	3710	408	17.1	<0.1	<1	340
43	MP3_12RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-12	M	0.06	12.7	23.4	18.9	14.9	7.4	22.4	370	6620	35	5	<0.1	32	150
44	LP9_15RN2-07	FFCV	RN-15	L	0.17	11.0	31.2	16.3	14.4	5.8	23.2	163	23200	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	160
45	RN12-2014-13	FFCV	RN-12	M			8.82	17.4	15.1	12.9	18.4	651	6040	<0.5	6.7	<0.1	<1	34
46	RN12-2014-12	FFCV	RN-12	M			7.83	15	14.4	12	15.6	657	5690	14.5	6	<0.1	<1	33
47	RN26-2014-4	FFCV	RN-26	H			14.6	49.7	0.295	3.56	> 25.0	201	7490	611	26.1	<0.1	<1	611
48	RN24-2007-4	FFCV	RN-24	M			27.1	20.1	17	5.95	24	355	17200	64.7	7.2	<0.1	<1	204
49	MP8_24RNE2	FFCV	RN-24	M			23.6	22.2	15.3	7.8	22.1	326	13800	153	20	0.2	24	192
50	RN21-2007-4	FFCV	RN-21	M			21.7	25.6	14.3	4.59	23.5	131	17500	178	19.7	<0.1	<1	313
51	MP6_21RNE2	FFCV	RN-21	M		12.1	24.1	26.0	13.3	5.9	24.4	127	16300	175	8	0.1	14	391
52	MP5_21RNE1	FFCV	RN-21	M		11.7	25.9	24.6	12.4	6.4	24.9	154	17500	53	<0.5	<0.1	15	435
53	RN12-2014-15	FFCV	RN-12	M			15.2	20.3	18.8	10.1	22	617	10400	18.2	4.2	<0.1	<1	32
54	MPI_12RNE1	FFCV	RN-12	M		12.5	19.9	20.0	13.1	9.6	19.8	589	6920	68	1	<0.1	18	223
55	MP2_12RNE2	FFCV	RN-12	M		12.2	25.7	21.3	15.7	8.9	23.6	554	9480	88	<0.5	<0.1	21	221
56	RN11-2014-6B	FFCV	RN-11	H			16.4	32.4	1.37	10.7	> 25.0	154	5930	51.6	7	<0.1	<1	327
57	RN11-2014-6C	FFCV	RN-11	H			17.3	33.2	1.43	10.8	> 25.0	164	6420	34.3	7.9	<0.1	<1	383
58	RN11-2014-6 A	FFCV	RN-11	H			20.8	31.6	4.19	9.28	> 25.0	156	11100	88.9	6.7	<0.1	<1	373
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.05	14.8	11.4	37.7	0.7	8.2	25.3	822	1160	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	580
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	FFCV	RN-23	H	0.03	15.1	10.9	49.4	0.1	2.8	30.8	109	1350	23	<0.1	<0.1	<1	7240
61	RN22-2007-8	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			13.1	31.8	1.35	5.05	21.6	172	3420	629	20.8	<0.1	<1	2490
62	RN22-2007-4	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			13.6	33.7	1.18	4.83	22.2	135	3420	424	14.6	<0.1	<1	3460
63	RN22-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			15.9	35.3	1.67	5.31	> 25.0	199	4210	964	26.2	<0.1	<1	2840
64	RN22-2007-14	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			22.2	37.6	0.5	4.04	> 25.0	1.41	6630	174	5.2	<0.1	<1	6220

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	In ppm	Bi ppm	Ge ppm	Ga ppm	Mo ppm	V ppm	Sn ppm	W ppm	Ni ppm	Cr ppm	Co ppm	Te ppm	Se ppm	Ir ppm
33	RN11-2014-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.6	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	4.4	6	498	<5
34	RN11-2013-2B	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4.8	<1	<5	<0.5	1.1	<10	<5	3.1	8	284	<5
35	RN11-2007-5	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.6	9	9	<0.5	0.7	<10	<5	3.8	49	418	<5
36	HP5_11RN4-07	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	1.1	<1	2	6	6	<1	<1	<20	<5	5		290	<5
37	HP20_10RN8_03	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.2	0.5	<1	<1	12	<5	<1	<1	<20	<5	168		441	<5
38	RN10-2003-1	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	22.4	3	48	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	1	<6	43	<5
39	RN11-2013-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.7	2	<5	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	4.5	9	434	<5
40	RN21-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.1	<1	46	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	2	<6	486	<5
41	MP7_21RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.2	<0.4	<1	1	<2	45	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1		354	<5
42	RN26-2014-3	dnstr on OP	RN-26	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.8	2	16	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	22.3	<6	82	<5
43	MP3_12RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-12	M	<0.2	0.4	<1	<1	<2	9	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1		707	<5
44	LP9_15RN2-07	FFCV	RN-15	L	<0.2	0.4	<1	2	<2	20	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1		587	160
45	RN12-2014-13	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4.9	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	1.1	71	630	<5
46	RN12-2014-12	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	5.5	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	1	80	595	<5
47	RN26-2014-4	FFCV	RN-26	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.7	10	20	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	41.1	19	160	<5
48	RN24-2007-4	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.8	2	14	<0.5	<0.7	60	<5	1.8	<6	1000	<5
49	MP8_24RNE2	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.2	0.9	<1	<1	<2	<5	<1	<1	<20	<5	22		1328	<5
50	RN21-2007-4	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.3	<1	8	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	2.1	<6	633	<5
51	MP6_21RNE2	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	<5	<1	<1	<20	34	<1		764	<5
52	MP5_21RNE1	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	<5	<1	<1	<20	34	<1		721	<5
53	RN12-2014-15	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.4	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	0.9	58	576	<5
54	MP1_12RNE1	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.2	0.5	<1	3	<2	<5	<1	3	<20	45	170		1199	<5
55	MP2_12RNE2	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.2	<0.4	<1	<1	<2	<5	<1	<1	<20	<5	19		1199	<5
56	RN11-2014-6B	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.9	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	8.2	12	407	<5
57	RN11-2014-6C	FFCV	RN-11	H	1.3	3	<0.7	1	4	<5	19.1	11.1	10	<5	9.2	15	410	<5
58	RN11-2014-6A	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.5	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	8.6	13	481	<5
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.8	28.7	<1	5	4	8	25	<1	<20	<5	25		490	<5
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	FFCV	RN-23	H	<0.2	2.0	<1	3	4	51	<1	<1	<20	<5	190		659	<5
61	RN22-2007-8	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.6	12	26	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	57.6	<6	248	<5
62	RN22-2007-4	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.6	8	39	<0.5	<0.7	20	<5	76.4	<6	351	<5
63	RN22-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.6	28	29	<0.5	0.8	20	<5	64.9	<6	306	<5
64	RN22-2007-14	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.2	12	9	<0.5	<0.7	20	<5	155	<6	828	<5

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Pt ppb	Pd ppb	Re ppm	Ba ppm	Rb ppm	Sr ppm	Cs ppm	Li ppm	Be ppm	B ppm	Br ppm	F ppm	U ppm
33	RN11-2014-1	dnstr	RN-11	H				<3	0.6	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.3
34	RN11-2013-2B	dnstr	RN-11	H				23	6.2	215	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	4.8		<0.1
35	RN11-2007-5	dnstr	RN-11	H				10	2.3	19	<0.1	4	4	<10	14.8		0.2
36	HP5_11RN4-07	dnstr	RN-11	H				23	2	13	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
37	HP20_10RN8_03	dnstr	RN-10	H				8	<2	5	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		0.1
38	RN10-2003-1	dnstr	RN-10	H				8	4.1	13	0.1	<3	<3	40	23.4	<0.01	<0.1
39	RN11-2013-1	dnstr	RN-11	H				<3	<0.4	19	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
40	RN21-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M				3	0.5	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.3
41	MP7_21RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M				8	<2	6	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
42	RN26-2014-3	dnstr on OP	RN-26	H				9	1.2	19	<0.1	10	10	<10	34.8		<0.1
43	MP3_12RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-12	M				10	<2	7	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
44	LP9_15RN2-07	FFCV	RN-15	L				<3	<2	2	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
45	RN12-2014-13	FFCV	RN-12	M				<3	<0.4	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
46	RN12-2014-12	FFCV	RN-12	M				4	<0.4	17	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
47	RN26-2014-4	FFCV	RN-26	H				71	<0.4	15	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
48	RN24-2007-4	FFCV	RN-24	M				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		1
49	MP8_24RNE2	FFCV	RN-24	M				4	<2	2	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.2
50	RN21-2007-4	FFCV	RN-21	M				<3	<0.4	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
51	MP6_21RNE2	FFCV	RN-21	M				3	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
52	MP5_21RNE1	FFCV	RN-21	M				3	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
53	RN12-2014-15	FFCV	RN-12	M				<3	<0.4	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
54	MP1_12RNE1	FFCV	RN-12	M				7	<2	6	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
55	MP2_12RNE2	FFCV	RN-12	M				3	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		<0.1
56	RN11-2014-6B	FFCV	RN-11	H				<3	<0.4	8	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
57	RN11-2014-6C	FFCV	RN-11	H				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.3
58	RN11-2014-6A	FFCV	RN-11	H				<3	<0.4	21	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.4
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	FFCV	RN-11	H				26	2	12	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		0.2
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	FFCV	RN-23	H				67	<2	47	<0.5	<1	<1		<0.5		0.2
61	RN22-2007-8	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				5	2.4	16	<0.1	6	6	<10	22.4		0.3
62	RN22-2007-4	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				31	1.7	18	<0.1	5	5	<10	7.8		0.4
63	RN22-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				12	1.4	16	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.7
64	RN22-2007-14	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.2

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Th ppm	Sc ppm	Y ppm	Zr ppm	Nb ppm	Hf ppm	Ta ppm	La ppm	Ce ppm	Pr ppm	Nd ppm	Sm ppm	Eu ppm
33	RN11-2014-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	1.9	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.1	<0.1
34	RN11-2013-2B	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	1.2
35	RN11-2007-5	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	7.3	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	2.4	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
36	HP5_11RN4-07	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	13	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.2	0.2	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
37	HP20_10RN8_03	dnstr	RN-10	H	0.2	<0.1	<2	6	<1	<0.2	0.1	0.9	1.9	0.19	0.9	<0.1	<0.05
38	RN10-2003-1	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
39	RN11-2013-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	0.3	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
40	RN21-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.1	0.4	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
41	MP7_21RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.2	0.3	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
42	RN26-2014-3	dnstr on OP	RN-26	H	<0.1	1.1	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.2	<0.1
43	MP3_12RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<2	10	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
44	LP9_15RN2-07	FFCV	RN-15	L	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
45	RN12-2014-13	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	5.5	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.1	<0.1
46	RN12-2014-12	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	4.6	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
47	RN26-2014-4	FFCV	RN-26	H	0.2	7.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	1.2	1.1	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
48	RN24-2007-4	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	2.4	2.5	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
49	MP8_24RNE2	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.1	2	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
50	RN21-2007-4	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
51	MP6_21RNE2	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
52	MP5_21RNE1	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
53	RN12-2014-15	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	3.5	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
54	MP1_12RNE1	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
55	MP2_12RNE2	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	2	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	0.1	<0.05
56	RN11-2014-6B	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
57	RN11-2014-6C	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.7	4.3	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	1.6	1.9	0.2	2.2	0.4	<0.1
58	RN11-2014-6A	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.3	6.2	0.1	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	1.8	2.3	0.2	2	0.1	<0.1
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.4	<0.1	<2	4	4	<0.2	0.2	1.6	3.5	0.39	1.3	<0.1	0.06
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	FFCV	RN-23	H	0.3	<0.1	<2	2	2	0.3	0.2	1.4	3.2	0.31	1.1	<0.1	0.07
61	RN22-2007-8	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	3.5	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.2	<0.1
62	RN22-2007-4	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	3.5	1.4	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	30	<0.2	1.9	1.4	<0.1	0.8	0.1	<0.1
63	RN22-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	30	<0.2	0.6	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.2	<0.1
64	RN22-2007-14	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	20	<0.2	0.5	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Gd ppm	Tb ppm	Dy ppm	Ho ppm	Er ppm	Tm ppm	Yb ppm	Lu ppm
33	RN11-2014-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
34	RN11-2013-2B	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	2.5	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
35	RN11-2007-5	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.13
36	HP5_11RN4-07	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
37	HP20_10RN8_03	dnstr	RN-10	H	0.2	<0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
38	RN10-2003-1	dnstr	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
39	RN11-2013-1	dnstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
40	RN21-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
41	MP7_21RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
42	RN26-2014-3	dnstr on OP	RN-26	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
43	MP3_12RN2-07	dnstr on OP	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
44	LP9_15RN2-07	FFCV	RN-15	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
45	RN12-2014-13	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
46	RN12-2014-12	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
47	RN26-2014-4	FFCV	RN-26	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
48	RN24-2007-4	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
49	MP8_24RNE2	FFCV	RN-24	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
50	RN21-2007-4	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
51	MP6_21RNE2	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
52	MP5_21RNE1	FFCV	RN-21	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
53	RN12-2014-15	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
54	MPI_12RNE1	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
55	MP2_12RNE2	FFCV	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.1	<0.04
56	RN11-2014-6B	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
57	RN11-2014-6C	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
58	RN11-2014-6A	FFCV	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
59	HP3_11RNE1-2_07	FFCV	RN-11	H	0.2	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
60	HP11_23RNE2-07	FFCV	RN-23	H	0.2	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
61	RN22-2007-8	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
62	RN22-2007-4	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
63	RN22-2007-3	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
64	RN22-2007-14	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Source	Sampling location	Location/well	Year taken	Group	DH depth (m)	Pbar	WP	SiO ₂ wt. %	Al ₂ O ₃ wt. %	CaO wt. %	Na ₂ O wt. %	K ₂ O wt. %	MnO wt. %	MgO wt. %	TiO ₂ wt. %	P ₂ O ₃ wt. %
65	RN22-2007-12	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	1.07	0.11	0.15	0.19	<0.12	0.06	0.15	0.03	
66	RN22-2007-11	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	0.51	0.06	0.10	0.19	<0.12	0.03	0.07	<0.02	
67	RN22-2007-10	7	dnstr on OP	RN-22	2007	4	-		H	5.73	0.19	0.13	0.22	<0.12	0.10	0.12	<0.02	
68	HP4_11RN3_07	3	dnstr on OP	RN-11	2007	4	-	22	H	11.5	0.8	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	1.5		
69	RN13B-2014-3	7	upstr	RN-13B	2014	3	-		L	3.21	0.42	0.14	0.01	<0.12	0.17	0.35	<0.02	
70	LP8_15RN1-07	3	upstr	RN-15	2007	3	-	24	L	22.8	2.2	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.6	6.8		
71	RN12-2014-11	7	upstr	RN-12	2014	3	-		M	14.20	1.00	0.48	0.04	<0.12	1.10	1.69	<0.02	
72	RN26-2014-5	7	upstr	RN-26	2014	3	-		H	3.98	0.43	0.14	0.04	<0.12	0.10	0.65	<0.02	
73	RN28-2014-1	7	upstr	RN-28	2014	3	-		H	0.47	0.08	0.03	0.04	<0.12	0.03	0.10	<0.02	
74	HP9_23RN1-07	3	upstr	RN-23	2007	3	-	43	H	1.8	0.2	0.0	<0.01	0.0	0.03	0.2		
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	3	upstr	RN-23	2007	3	-	22	H	0.4	0.1	0.0	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.1		
76	RN23-2014-2	7	upstr	RN-23	2014	3	-		H	4.66	0.72	0.21	0.01	<0.12	0.06	1.06	0.02	
77	RN23-2014-1	7	upstr	RN-23	2014	3	-		H	4.47	0.68	0.18	0.04	<0.12	0.06	1.03	<0.02	
78	RN23-2007-2	7	upstr	RN-23	2007	3	-		H	2.08	0.42	0.11	0.04	<0.12	0.04	0.40	0.03	
79	RN14B-2014-1	7	upstr	RN-14B	2014	3	-		H	5.33	0.74	0.28	0.22	<0.12	0.08	1.13	<0.02	
80	HP2_11RN1-07	3	upstr	RN-11	2007	3	-	43	H	9.2	0.6	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.2	1.3		
81	HP7_22RN5-07	2	upstr	RN-22	2007	3	-	32	H	3.6	0.5	0.2	0.02	0.03	0.44	0.030		
82	HP18_14RN1-07	3	upstr	RN-14	2007	3	-	34	H	1.0	0.1	0.1	<0.01	0.1	0.03	0.2		
83	RN11-2014-3	7	upstr	RN-11	2014	3	-		H	3.59	0.23	0.15	0.09	<0.12	0.18	0.32	<0.02	
84	RN10-2006-1	7	upstr	RN-10	2006	3	-		H	19.23	4.69	2.00	0.28	<0.12	0.12	4.89	0.35	
85	RN12-2014-1	7	WH	RN-12	2014	3	-		M	23.75	1.64	0.83	0.58	<0.12	1.27	3.80	<0.02	
86	HP1_11RN5T_02G	3	WH	RN-11	2002	3	-	40	H	23.9	2.0	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.2	4.7		
87	RN10-2014-1	7	WH	RN-10	2014	3	-		H	0.19	0.08	0.10	0.05	<0.12	0.05	0.03	<0.02	
88	22RN141	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	141		H	<0.02	1.6	0.35	0.43	<0.12	0.08	1.8		
89	22RN150	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	150	~46	H	<0.02	1.6	0.70	0.43	<0.12	0.10	1.8		
90	22RN160Fe*	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	160		H	<0.02	1.2	0.56	0.51	<0.12	0.28	1.4		
91	22RN270Fe*	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	270		H	11.3	1.6	0.62	0.70	<0.12	0.11	1.9		
92	22RN350Fe*	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	350		H	<0.02	1.8	0.53	0.65	<0.12	0.10	2.3		
93	22RN449	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	449		H	<0.02	1.6	0.34	0.62	<0.12	0.08	2.2		
94	22RN570	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	570		H	<0.02	1.1	0.20	0.40	<0.12	0.05	1.2		
95	22RN618	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	618		H	<0.02	1.0	0.17	0.38	<0.12	0.05	1.1		
96	RN10-2014-660	7	DH	RN-10	2014	3	660		H	7.72	2.49	2.31	0.16	<0.12	0.21	1.59	0.27	

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	C Total wt. %	LOI wt. %	Cu wt. %	Zn wt. %	Pb wt. %	Fe wt. %	S wt. %	Au ppm	Ag ppm	As ppm	Sb ppm	Tl ppm	Hg ppm	Cd ppm
65	RN22-2007-12	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			17.3	39.8	1.15	3.8	> 25.0	1.83	4320	272	8.9	<0.1	<1	4910
66	RN22-2007-11	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			16.6	42.3	0.92	3.87	> 25.0	45.1	4100	414	13.6	<0.1	<1	5380
67	RN22-2007-10	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H			15.1	36.3	1.64	5.23	24.9	185	4130	754	29.2	<0.1	<1	2730
68	HP4_I1RN3_07	dnstr on OP	RN-11	H	0.05	15.4	8.1	38.3	0.2	7.9	24.2	948	956	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	600
69	RN13B-2014-3	upstr	RN-13B	L			2.1	41	9.54	9.16	> 25.0	65.5	272	50.9	2.3	<0.1	<1	158
70	LP8_I5RN1-07	upstr	RN-15	L	0.07	13.3	12.0	6.9	7.0	15.5	14.6	136	1260	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	140
71	RN12-2014-11	upstr	RN-12	M			7	15.4	11	13.4	16.2	439	3580	<0.5	5.2	<0.1	<1	32
72	RN26-2014-5	upstr	RN-26	H			5.07	54.8	0.049	3.78	> 25.0	238	10600	692	47.6	<0.1	<1	798
73	RN28-2014-1	upstr	RN-28	H			0.702	64.7	0.362	1.97	> 25.0	374	101	24.4	<0.1	<0.1	<1	13300
74	HP9_23RN1-07	upstr	RN-23	H	0.02	16.0	2.0	58.7	0.0	3.1	34.4	385	128	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	13300
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	upstr	RN-23	H	0.04	16.0	2.0	58.9	0.0	2.5	33.2	288	522	176	7	<0.1	<1	17100
76	RN23-2014-2	upstr	RN-23	H			12.8	35.5	12.5	5.36	> 25.0	242	1460	11.8	0.7	<0.1	<1	1610
77	RN23-2014-1	upstr	RN-23	H			12.6	36.2	6.08	4.81	24.5	188	1160	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	2240
78	RN23-2007-2	upstr	RN-23	H			1.25	57.6	0.044	3.96	> 25.0	598	264	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	13900
79	RN14B-2014-1	upstr	RN-14B	H			10	26.3	10.6	11.4	> 25.0	288	492	7.4	0.5	<0.1	<1	260
80	HP2_I1RN1-07	upstr	RN-11	H	0.06	14.9	7.8	40.8	0.2	8.4	25.9	448	464	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	600
81	HP7_22RN5-07	upstr	RN-22	H	0.07	14.8	11.0	47.8	0.3	2.7	30.3	106	887	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1000	8900
82	HP18_14RN1-07	upstr	RN-14	H	0.04	19.9	4.1	57.5	0.1	1.8	31.2	12.2	22000	3030	301	<0.1	<1	6470
83	RN11-2014-3	upstr	RN-11	H			17.6	32.4	1.13	9.8	> 25.0	188	12000	73.6	16.3	<0.1	<1	382
84	RN10-2006-1	upstr	RN-10	H			1.34	30	0.010	11.2	15.9	375	131	5.5	1.2	<0.1	<1	12500
85	RN12-2014-1	WH	RN-12	M			6.37	7.27	5.75	16.2	11.4	250	632	<0.5	1.1	<0.1	<1	22
86	HP1_I1RN5T_02G	WH	RN-11	H		13.1	1.3	25.1	0.1	13.5	12.3	115	44	53	1	0.1	na	272
87	RN10-2014-1	WH	RN-10	H			5	54.2	0.034	5.75	> 25.0	153	2750	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	1730
88	22RN141	DH	RN-22	H			3.8	44.4	0.014	7.0	25.0	103	445	<0.5	<0.1	0.1	17	> 5000
89	22RN150	DH	RN-22	H			3.7	41.0	0.014	8.0	25.5	125	584	<0.5	<0.1	0.1	14	> 5000
90	22RN160Fe*	DH	RN-22	H			2.9	25.6	0.020	23.1	16.4	75	378	28	7.4	1.4	34	4080
91	22RN270Fe*	DH	RN-22	H			3.4	32.5	0.008	13.2	22.1	81	129	9	2.2	0.2	18	4770
92	22RN350Fe*	DH	RN-22	H			1.8	38.2	0.006	8.9	22.8	80	85	<0.5	<0.1	0.2	11	> 5000
93	22RN449	DH	RN-22	H			1.6	42.2	0.003	8.3	24.1	82	57	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	6	> 5000
94	22RN570	DH	RN-22	H			1.2	45.9	0.003	5.7	27.4	82	37	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	6	> 5000
95	22RN618	DH	RN-22	H			2.1	48.0	0.003	6.2	28.2	85	38	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	8	> 5000
96	RN10-2014-660	DH	RN-10	H			4.71	33.2	0.016	15.4	22.2	95.1	438	9.6	2.1	<0.1	<1	1640

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	In ppm	Bi ppm	Ge ppm	Ga ppm	Mo ppm	V ppm	Sn ppm	W ppm	Ni ppm	Cr ppm	Co ppm	Te ppm	Se ppm	Ir ppm
65	RN22-2007-12	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.7	8	36	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	113	<6	820	<5
66	RN22-2007-11	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	0.6	12	26	<0.5	1.7	10	<5	136	<6	600	<5
67	RN22-2007-10	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.8	17	32	<0.5	<0.7	20	<5	63.4	<6	342	<5
68	HP4_11RN3_07	dnstr on OP	RN-11	H	<0.2	16.8	<1	5	4	13	<1	<1	<20	<5	<1	<6	<3	<5
69	RN13B-2014-3	upstr	RN-13B	L	<0.2	<2	<0.7	7.4	2	17	<0.5	1.1	20	<5	27.8	<6	619	<5
70	LP8_15RN1-07	upstr	RN-15	L	<0.2	0.4	<1	14	4	201	1	<1	<20	<5	3	446	<5	
71	RN12-2014-11	upstr	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	6.2	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	0.6	63	526	<5
72	RN26-2014-5	upstr	RN-26	H	<0.2	3	<0.7	5	10	76	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	48.3	16	121	<5
73	RN28-2014-1	upstr	RN-28	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	26	5	29	30.3	<0.7	30	<5	202	26	1260	<5
74	HP9_23RN1-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	38.2	<1	1	<2	30	12	<1	<20	<5	395	923	<5	
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	0.8	<1	8	10	14	<1	<1	<20	<5	331	781	<5	
76	RN23-2014-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.6	2	216	<0.5	3	<10	<5	55.4	<6	1010	<5
77	RN23-2014-1	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.5	1	211	<0.5	1.6	<10	25	67	<6	692	<5
78	RN23-2007-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	3.1	2	124	10.5	2.4	<10	<5	449	55	1030	<5
79	RN14B-2014-1	upstr	RN-14B	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	2.9	2	227	0.8	<0.7	30	<5	51.7	18	1410	<5
80	HP2_11RN1-07	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	9.4	<1	4	<2	9	<1	<1	<20	<5	15	345	<5	
81	HP7_22RN5-07	upstr	RN-22	H	<0.2	<0.4	<1	3	3	79	<1	<1	<20	<5	206	982	<5	
82	HP18_14RN1-07	upstr	RN-14	H	<0.2	<0.4	<1	14	119	147	2	<1	<20	<5	387	181	<5	
83	RN11-2014-3	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	1.2	<1	<5	<0.5	<0.7	10	<5	8.6	14	413	<5
84	RN10-2006-1	upstr	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	17.9	21	314	13.8	5.3	200	129	200	<6	636	<5
85	RN12-2014-1	WH	RN-12	M	<0.2	<2	<0.7	10.2	<1	8	<0.5	<0.7	<10	<5	0.5	58	374	<5
86	HPI_11RN5T_02G	WH	RN-11	H	<0.2	<0.4	15	12	18	195	3	<1	7	<5	13	320	<5	
87	RN10-2014-1	WH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4.4	2	7	<0.5	<0.7	20	<5	82.8	<6	113	<5
88	22RN141	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	0.7	12	<1	847	4.2	<0.7	20	<5	161	7.0	910	<5
89	22RN150	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	12	2	814	3.5	<0.7	20	<5	180	7.0	1110	<5
90	22RN160Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	2.2	12	36	466	18	2.7	180	155	131	<6	664	<5
91	22RN270Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	10	7	378	5.8	4.6	40	157	180	9.0	975	<5
92	22RN350Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	11	6	458	4.2	22.5	30	122	195	11.0	1010	<5
93	22RN449	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	13	<1	442	3.6	1.5	20	37	219	13.0	1180	<5
94	22RN570	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	12	<1	269	4.2	1	20	<5	251	12.0	1360	<5
95	22RN618	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	13	<1	256	5.8	<0.7	20	37	240	15.0	1490	<5
96	RN10-2014-660	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	9.9	65	66	9.2	7.8	100	237	135	<6	169	<5

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Pt ppb	Pd ppb	Re ppm	Ba ppm	Rb ppm	Sr ppm	Cs ppm	Li ppm	Be ppm	B ppm	Br ppm	F ppm	U ppm
65	RN22-2007-12	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	12	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.2
66	RN22-2007-11	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	10	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
67	RN22-2007-10	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H				<3	1.1	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
68	HP4_1 RN3_07	dnstr on OP	RN-11	H				18	2	13	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		<0.1
69	RN13B-2014-3	upstr	RN-13B	L				<3	<0.4	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.1
70	LP8_15RN1-07	upstr	RN-15	L				16	5	23	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		0.1
71	RN12-2014-11	upstr	RN-12	M				7	<0.4	19	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
72	RN26-2014-5	upstr	RN-26	H				<3	<0.4	13	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
73	RN28-2014-1	upstr	RN-28	H				<3	<0.4	11	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
74	HP9_23RN1-07	upstr	RN-23	H				<3	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		<0.1
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	upstr	RN-23	H				<3	<2	<2	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		<0.1
76	RN23-2014-2	upstr	RN-23	H				<3	<0.4	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
77	RN23-2014-1	upstr	RN-23	H				7	<0.4	14	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
78	RN23-2007-2	upstr	RN-23	H				<3	<0.4	10	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
79	RN14B-2014-1	upstr	RN-14B	H				6	0.6	16	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.3
80	HP2_1 RN1-07	upstr	RN-11	H				15	<2	11	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		<0.1
81	HP7_22RN5-07	upstr	RN-22	H				12	<2	9	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		0.3
82	HP18_14RN1-07	upstr	RN-14	H				<3	<2	2	<0.5	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		0.2
83	RN11-2014-3	upstr	RN-11	H				<3	<0.4	15	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		0.2
84	RN10-2006-1	upstr	RN-10	H				19	2.3	37	<0.1	22	22	100	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
85	RN12-2014-1	WH	RN-12	M				13	3.3	26	<0.1	5	5	<10	3.7	<0.01	<0.1
86	HP1_1 RN5T_02G	WH	RN-11	H				12	17	20	0.7	<1	<1	<10	<0.5		<0.1
87	RN10-2014-1	WH	RN-10	H				<3	0.4	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
88	22RN141	DH	RN-22	H				8	2.0	13	<0.1	5.0	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
89	22RN150	DH	RN-22	H				26	1.9	14	0.5	3.0	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
90	22RN160Fe*	DH	RN-22	H				55	1.7	18	<0.1	18.0	<3	<10	12		<0.1
91	22RN270Fe*	DH	RN-22	H				22	2.0	14	0.1	<3	<3	20.0	8.8		<0.1
92	22RN350Fe*	DH	RN-22	H				15	1.9	18	<0.1	<3	<3	30.0	<0.5		<0.1
93	22RN449	DH	RN-22	H				11	2.0	15	<0.1	<3	<3	10.0	<0.5		<0.1
94	22RN570	DH	RN-22	H				7	1.3	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	9.5		<0.1
95	22RN618	DH	RN-22	H				7	1.3	9	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5		<0.1
96	RN10-2014-660	DH	RN-10	H				9	0.9	39	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Th ppm	Sc ppm	Y ppm	Zr ppm	Nb ppm	Hf ppm	Ta ppm	La ppm	Ce ppm	Pr ppm	Nd ppm	Sm ppm	Eu ppm
65	RN22-2007-12	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
66	RN22-2007-11	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.6	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
67	RN22-2007-10	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.1	<0.1
68	HP4_11RN3_07	dnstr on OP	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.4	0.7	0.08	0.3	<0.1	<0.05
69	RN13B-2014-3	upstr	RN-13B	L	<0.1	<0.1	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
70	LP8_15RN1-07	upstr	RN-15	L	0.2	0.4	<2	<1	<1	0.2	0.1	1	1.5	0.19	0.6	<0.1	<0.05
71	RN12-2014-11	upstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	2.2	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
72	RN26-2014-5	upstr	RN-26	H	<0.1	2.3	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
73	RN28-2014-1	upstr	RN-28	H	0.2	1.2	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	10	<0.2	1.7	1.4	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
74	HP9_23RN1-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<1	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.1	0.3	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<1	<1	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<0.05	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
76	RN23-2014-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	5	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
77	RN23-2014-1	upstr	RN-23	H	0.1	2.9	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.5	1	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
78	RN23-2007-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	3.3	0.4	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
79	RN14B-2014-1	upstr	RN-14B	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.3	<2.4	<2.4	20	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
80	HP2_11RN1-07	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.4	0.6	0.06	0.2	<0.1	<0.05
81	HP7_22RN5-07	upstr	RN-22	H	0.4	<0.1	<2	<4	<1	0.5	0.1	1.3	2.8	0.28	1	<0.1	0.07
82	HP18_14RN1-07	upstr	RN-14	H	<0.1	<0.1	<2	<1	<1	<0.2	<0.1	0.3	0.9	0.09	0.4	<0.1	<0.05
83	RN11-2014-3	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	<2.4	<2.4	20	<0.2	0.6	<0.8	<0.1	0.5	<0.1	<0.1
84	RN10-2006-1	upstr	RN-10	H	<0.1	8.9	4.6	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	3	0.4	<0.4	0.3	0.2
85	RN12-2014-1	WH	RN-12	M	<0.1	4.8	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
86	HP1_11RN5T_02G	WH	RN-11	H	<0.1	0.6	<1	<4	1	<0.2	-0.1	0.7	0.5	0.12	0.3	<0.1	<0.05
87	RN10-2014-1	WH	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
88	22RN141	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	1.6	0.5	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
89	22RN150	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	1.3	0.5	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
90	22RN160Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	1.6	0.8	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	0.1	<0.1
91	22RN270Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<2.4	<2.4	3	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
92	22RN350Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	1.9	0.6	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
93	22RN449	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	0.6	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
94	22RN570	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
95	22RN618	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2	<2.4	<2.4	<1	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
96	RN10-2014-660	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	5.7	4	<2.4	<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	3.1	0.4	<0.4	0.3	0.2

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Gd ppm	Tb ppm	Dy ppm	Ho ppm	Er ppm	Tm ppm	Yb ppm	Lu ppm
65	RN22-2007-12	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.15
66	RN22-2007-11	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
67	RN22-2007-10	dnstr on OP	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1
68	HP4_11RN3_07	dnstr on OP	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
69	RN13B-2014-3	upstr	RN-13B	L	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
70	LP8_15RN1-07	upstr	RN-15	L	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
71	RN12-2014-11	upstr	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
72	RN26-2014-5	upstr	RN-26	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.2
73	RN28-2014-1	upstr	RN-28	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
74	HP9_23RN1-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
75	HP12_23RN3D-07	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
76	RN23-2014-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
77	RN23-2014-1	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
78	RN23-2007-2	upstr	RN-23	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
79	RN14B-2014-1	upstr	RN-14B	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
80	HP2_11RN1-07	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
81	HP7_22RN5-07	upstr	RN-22	H	0.1	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	2.1	<0.04
82	HP18_14RN1-07	upstr	RN-14	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
83	RN11-2014-3	upstr	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
84	RN10-2006-1	upstr	RN-10	H	0.7	0.1	0.7	<0.2	0.5	<0.1	0.4	<0.05
85	RN12-2014-1	WH	RN-12	M	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
86	HP1_11RN5T_02G	WH	RN-11	H	<0.1	<0.0	<0.1	<0.0	<0.1	<0.05	<0.2	<0.04
87	RN10-2014-1	WH	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
88	22RN141	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
89	22RN150	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
90	22RN160Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
91	22RN270Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
92	22RN350Fe*	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
93	22RN449	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
94	22RN570	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
95	22RN618	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
96	RN10-2014-660	DH	RN-10	H	0.6	0.1	0.6	<0.2	0.4	<0.1	0.3	<0.05

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Source	Sampling location	Location/well	Year taken	Group	DH depth (m)	Pbar	WP	SiO2 wt.%	Al2O3 wt.%	CaO wt.%	Na2O wt.%	K2O wt.%	MnO wt.%	MgO wt.%	TiO2 wt.%	P2O3 wt.%	
97	22RN669	2	DH	RN-22	2009	3	669	-52	H	<0.02	0.9	0.13	0.38	<0.12	0.05	1.2			
98	RN10-2014-835	7	DH	RN-10	2014	3	835		H	5.22	1.57	1.26	0.58	<0.12	0.15	0.71	0.03		
99	RN10-2014-870	7	DH	RN-10	2014	3	870		H	7.34	1.95	1.27	0.32	<0.12	0.16	1.21	0.07		
100	RN10-2014-904	7	DH	RN-10	2014	3	904		H	12.15	4.40	3.75	0.58	<0.12	0.20	1.79	0.17		
101	RN10-2014-1085	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1085		H	9.43	1.81	0.87	0.70	<0.12	0.21	1.48	0.05		
102	RN10-2014-1095A	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1095		H	20.02	4.06	2.35	0.90	0.12	0.21	3.66	0.17		
103	RN10-2014-1097A	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1097		H	24.39	6.07	4.52	1.04	0.12	0.21	4.28	0.37		
104	RN10-2014-1098A	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1098		H	23.96	6.10	4.78	0.96	<0.12	0.19	4.15	0.40		
105	RN10-2014-1099	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1099		H	26.31	6.52	4.28	1.13	<0.12	0.21	4.28	0.50		
106	RN10-2014-1120	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1120		H	28.02	6.71	4.84	1.40	0.12	0.20	4.71	0.45		
107	RN10-2014-1136	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1136		H	19.85	4.57	3.16	1.08	0.12	0.19	3.35	0.27		
108	RN10-2014-1148	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1148		H	12.79	2.91	2.21	0.82	<0.12	0.19	2.14	0.18		
109	RN10-2014-1168	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1168		H	5.69	0.87	0.62	0.44	<0.12	0.12	0.65	0.05		
110	RN10-2014-1198	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1198		H	13.35	2.93	2.27	0.74	<0.12	0.25	1.86	0.18		
111	RN10-2014-1245	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1245		H	10.57	2.23	1.79	0.81	<0.12	0.23	1.54	0.13		
112	RN10-2014-1504	7	DH	RN-10	2014	2	1504		H	17.26	3.72	1.90	0.90	0.12	0.15	4.46	0.17		
113	RN10-2014-1575	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1575		H	11.30	2.08	0.83	0.44	<0.12	0.09	3.27	0.02		
114	RN10-2014-1668	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1668		H	15.04	3.33	1.73	0.69	<0.12	0.11	3.95	0.10		
115	RN10-2014-1680	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1680		H	12.51	2.32	0.80	0.71	<0.12	0.09	3.68	0.05		
116	RN10-2014-1737	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1737		H	15.51	3.14	1.16	0.77	0.12	0.10	4.36	0.12		
117	RN10-2014-1792A	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1792		H	12.47	2.42	0.92	0.69	0.12	0.09	3.61	0.03		
118	RN10-2014-1800	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1800		H	12.24	2.66	1.36	0.77	<0.12	0.10	2.92	0.13		
119	RN10-2014-1828	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1828		H	13.63	2.89	1.40	0.77	<0.12	0.10	3.45	0.13		
120	RN10-2014-1832	7	DH	RN-10	2014	1	1832		H	14.29	2.97	1.39	0.74	0.12	0.12	3.43	0.13		
121	RN-17_2700m	S1	DH	RN-17B	2011	1	2700		-	26.6	2.26	3.3	0.64	0.16	0.548	8.39	0.078	0.07	
122	RN22-2013-1051	7	DH	RN-22	2013	2	1051		H	16.47	2.72	0.52	0.05	<0.12	0.74	4.26	0.02		
123	RN22-2013-1064A	7	DH	RN-22	2013	2	1064		H	3.32	0.47	0.11	0.01	<0.12	>1	0.65	0.03		
124	RN22-2013-1088	7	DH	RN-22	2013	2	1088		H	12.99	2.36	0.32	0.04	<0.12	0.81	3.78	0.03		
125	RN22-2013-1636	7	DH	RN-22	2013	1	1636		H	23.53	6.29	4.07	0.70	<0.12	0.22	4.78	0.55		
126	RN22-2013-1638A	7	DH	RN-22	2013	1	1638		H	36.37	11.51	9.07	1.93	<0.12	0.34	5.87	1.35		
127	RN22-2013-1638B	7	DH	RN-22	2013	1	1638		H	12.54	2.66	1.66	0.28	<0.12	0.23	2.65	0.22		
128	RN22-2013-1642	7	DH	RN-22	2013	1	1642		H	21.22	5.91	3.57	0.92	<0.12	0.17	4.64	0.48		
129	RN22-2013-1646	7	DH	RN-22	2013	1	1646		H	23.96	6.65	3.93	1.06	0.12	0.19	5.69	0.52		

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	C Total wt. %	LOI wt. %	Cu wt. %	Zn wt. %	Pb wt. %	Fe wt. %	S wt. %	Au ppm	Ag ppm	As ppm	Sb ppm	Tl ppm	Hg ppm	Cd ppm
97	22RN669	DH	RN-22	H			3.5	44.8	0.003	7.0	28.6	89	35	<0.5	<0.1	0.1	13	> 5000
98	RN10-2014-835	DH	RN-10	H			4.1	42.7	0.006	9.91	> 25.0	126	151	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	2760
99	RN10-2014-870	DH	RN-10	H			3.89	39.4	0.006	12	24.6	118	151	6.9	<0.1	<0.1	<1	2510
100	RN10-2014-904	DH	RN-10	H			2.52	31	0.008	13.5	19	na	185	14	1.8	0.2	<1	2020
101	RN10-2014-1085	DH	RN-10	H			4.39	18.4	0.008	28	14.1	80.5	101	26.2	4	<0.1	<1	1440
102	RN10-2014-1095A	DH	RN-10	H			6.55	14.8	0.002	17.1	14.6	78.4	84	2.6	0.3	<0.1	<1	1060
103	RN10-2014-1097A	DH	RN-10	H			4.5	9.97	0.006	14.9	9.71	61.4	85	5.7	0.6	<0.1	<1	831
104	RN10-2014-1098A	DH	RN-10	H			4.89	15.7	0.003	16.5	13.4	72.5	117	10.8	0.9	<0.1	<1	1230
105	RN10-2014-1099	DH	RN-10	H			5.66	13.9	0.003	15.7	13.1	66	105	2	0.7	<0.1	<1	983
106	RN10-2014-1120	DH	RN-10	H			5.18	11.1	0.002	15.6	11.1	57.9	124	10.1	1.1	<0.1	<1	865
107	RN10-2014-1136	DH	RN-10	H			6.06	21.4	0.002	14.8	17	83.2	124	<0.5	0.6	<0.1	<1	1370
108	RN10-2014-1148	DH	RN-10	H			5.89	26.5	0.004	16.6	19.6	103	160	14.2	1.1	<0.1	<1	1730
109	RN10-2014-1168	DH	RN-10	H			7.93	34	0.008	15.2	23.8	141	350	17.7	2.3	<0.1	<1	2480
110	RN10-2014-1198	DH	RN-10	H			6.08	27.4	0.005	15.6	18.5	106	222	16.6	2.2	<0.1	<1	1960
111	RN10-2014-1245	DH	RN-10	H			6.07	27.4	0.005	17	18.7	112	238	20.2	2	<0.1	<1	1980
112	RN10-2014-1504	DH	RN-10	H			1.92	28.9	0.004	12.8	16.7	44.7	98	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	2770
113	RN10-2014-1575	DH	RN-10	H			0.708	45.2	0.001	7.05	24.2	2.03	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	4960
114	RN10-2014-1668	DH	RN-10	H			0.785	38.7	0.002	8.66	20.9	2.17	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	4080
115	RN10-2014-1680	DH	RN-10	H			2.01	37.1	0.001	8.14	22.5	1.15	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	3820
116	RN10-2014-1737	DH	RN-10	H			1.4	34.8	0.001	8.18	20.3	0.986	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	4010
117	RN10-2014-1792A	DH	RN-10	H			1.58	38.8	0.001	7.89	22.3	1.05	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	4150
118	RN10-2014-1800	DH	RN-10	H			1.6	37.8	0.001	7.95	22	1.86	<5	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	3950
119	RN10-2014-1828	DH	RN-10	H			1.66	37.4	0.002	8.32	21.6	1.67	53	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	4150
120	RN10-2014-1832	DH	RN-10	H			2.27	35.6	0.003	8.61	20.9	2.61	79	<0.5	<0.1	<0.1	<1	3900
121	RN-17_2700m	DH	RN-17B	-		11.28	0.077	3.14		28.7	10.5	40.9	24.4	32.9	1.2	0.2	<1	699
122	RN22-2013-1051	DH	RN-22	H			0.117	5.55	0.026	38.5	8.46	1.31	<5	43.4	4	<0.1	<1	4720
123	RN22-2013-1064A	DH	RN-22	H			0.171	0.562	0.003	74.3	0.78	0.858	<5	83.5	12.5	<0.1	<1	449
124	RN22-2013-1088	DH	RN-22	H			0.149	0.33	0.022	45.5	7.11	246	75	58.4	5.6	<0.1	<1	169
125	RN22-2013-1636	DH	RN-22	H			2.79	9.06	0.014	19	11.2	156	65	16.1	1.1	<0.1	<1	3710
126	RN22-2013-1638A	DH	RN-22	H			0.0922	2.01	0.271	17.6	2.13	1.48	194	24.5	2	<0.1	<1	132
127	RN22-2013-1638B	DH	RN-22	H			0.888	15.4	0.017	30.5	12.2	214	<5	33.6	4.4	<0.1	<1	5750
128	RN22-2013-1642	DH	RN-22	H			1.07	27.3	0.005	7.48	15.5	240	<5	3.2	<0.1	<0.1	<1	12000
129	RN22-2013-1646	DH	RN-22	H			2.25	18	0.012	11.7	12.1	251	108	<0.5	0.5	<0.1	<1	6620

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	In ppm	Bi ppm	Ge ppm	Ga ppm	Mo ppm	V ppm	Sn ppm	W ppm	Ni ppm	Cr ppm	Co ppm	Te ppm	Se ppm	Ir ppm
97	22RN669	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	13	<1	192	6.9	<0.7	20	<5	226	17.0	1600	<5
98	RN10-2014-835	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	10.6	18	23	2.3	<0.7	30	54	123	<6	197	<5
99	RN10-2014-870	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	11.2	34	45	3.9	<0.7	50	120	142	<6	197	<5
100	RN10-2014-904	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	11.5	58	81	6.3	<0.7	90	190	112	<6	157	<5
101	RN10-2014-1085	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	12.2	177	47	19.6	2.7	180	367	133	<6	183	<5
102	RN10-2014-1095A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	15.6	38	88	4.6	11.6	70	133	107	<6	176	<5
103	RN10-2014-1097A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	16.9	23	123	2.9	6.7	70	172	95.7	<6	137	<5
104	RN10-2014-1098A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	12.9	39	111	3.8	77.8	80	190	173	8	222	<5
105	RN10-2014-1099	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	14.7	28	119	2.8	2.8	70	161	110	<6	123	<5
106	RN10-2014-1120	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	15.2	14	126	1	30.1	70	160	104	<6	88	<5
107	RN10-2014-1136	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	11.4	29	108	2.3	297	70	103	145	<6	174	<5
108	RN10-2014-1148	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	9.1	51	74	5.4	191	120	180	214	<6	246	<5
109	RN10-2014-1168	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	4	54	25	5.7	23.4	60	150	219	13	302	<5
110	RN10-2014-1198	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	7.9	66	65	6.8	477	220	175	266	10	252	<5
111	RN10-2014-1245	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	6.8	64	59	5.8	2700	150	184	363	9	254	<5
112	RN10-2014-1504	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	9.3	32	122	2.9	15.7	50	136	399	29	409	<5
113	RN10-2014-1575	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	2	<0.7	6.8	2	103	<0.5	3	20	<5	614	62	787	<5
114	RN10-2014-1668	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	8.4	10	111	<0.5	5.8	30	<5	549	51	684	<5
115	RN10-2014-1680	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	5.7	<1	85	<0.5	0.7	20	<5	560	74	842	<5
116	RN10-2014-1737	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	7.2	<1	130	<0.5	6.3	20	<5	605	78	782	<5
117	RN10-2014-1792A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	6.1	<1	103	<0.5	6.8	20	<5	622	79	840	<5
118	RN10-2014-1800	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	6.4	4	93	<0.5	34.2	40	<5	548	67	751	<5
119	RN10-2014-1828	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	7.1	<1	112	<0.5	1.2	30	<5	580	72	756	<5
120	RN10-2014-1832	DH	RN-10	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	8	1	114	10.2	3	20	<5	524	61	662	<5
121	RN-17_2700m	DH	RN-17B	-	<0.1	0.21	0.5	13.9	70	82	13	7.8	456	754	214	0.4	17.8	<5
122	RN22-2013-1051	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	18.9	57	111	66.4	8.1	390	278	52.9	<6	86	<5
123	RN22-2013-1064A	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	3.5	15.5	144	<5	77.7	51.2	1030	1230	98.9	<6	<3	<5
124	RN22-2013-1088	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	22.8	126	195	53.5	9.8	840	588	70.4	<6	<3	<5
125	RN22-2013-1636	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	15.8	58	257	20.8	8.3	510	372	104	<6	241	<5
126	RN22-2013-1638A	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	21.7	79	348	14.8	1.1	200	395	60.7	<6	35	<5
127	RN22-2013-1638B	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	19.5	141	411	49.6	15.6	910	759	153	<6	392	<5
128	RN22-2013-1642	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	22.2	13	331	12.6	2.5	170	130	199	<6	669	<5
129	RN22-2013-1646	DH	RN-22	H	<0.2	<2	<0.7	18.9	7	396	20.9	2.4	170	197	154	<6	421	<5

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/well	WP	Pt	Pd	Re	Ba	Rb	Sr	Cs	Li	Be	B	Br	F	U
					ppb	ppb	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
97	22RN669	DH	RN-22	H				8	1.0	7	<0.1	3	<3	10	8		<0.1
98	RN10-2014-835	DH	RN-10	H				6	2.3	20	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	20.4	<0.01	<0.1
99	RN10-2014-870	DH	RN-10	H				9	2.1	21	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
100	RN10-2014-904	DH	RN-10	H				15	3.1	31	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	5.9	<0.01	<0.1
101	RN10-2014-1085	DH	RN-10	H				15	3.8	27	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	22.4	<0.01	<0.1
102	RN10-2014-1095A	DH	RN-10	H				12	4.5	40	0.1	<3	<3	<10	15.2	<0.01	<0.1
103	RN10-2014-1097A	DH	RN-10	H				22	4.1	67	0.1	<3	<3	<10	13.4	<0.01	<0.1
104	RN10-2014-1098A	DH	RN-10	H				16	3.4	55	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	5.2	<0.01	<0.1
105	RN10-2014-1099	DH	RN-10	H				22	3.6	67	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	11.7	<0.01	<0.1
106	RN10-2014-1120	DH	RN-10	H				20	4.5	63	0.1	<3	<3	<10	21.2	<0.01	<0.1
107	RN10-2014-1136	DH	RN-10	H				15	4.4	49	0.1	<3	<3	<10	16.8	<0.01	<0.1
108	RN10-2014-1148	DH	RN-10	H				10	3.2	36	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	18.2	<0.01	<0.1
109	RN10-2014-1168	DH	RN-10	H				8	1.7	4	<0.1	<3	<3	40	5.4	<0.01	<0.1
110	RN10-2014-1198	DH	RN-10	H				12	2.7	39	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	15.8	<0.01	<0.1
111	RN10-2014-1245	DH	RN-10	H				9	2.9	33	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	11.8	<0.01	<0.1
112	RN10-2014-1504	DH	RN-10	H				15	4	38	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	14.8	<0.01	<0.1
113	RN10-2014-1575	DH	RN-10	H				12	2.5	30	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
114	RN10-2014-1668	DH	RN-10	H				12	3.4	29	0.7	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
115	RN10-2014-1680	DH	RN-10	H				12	2.9	26	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	15.4	<0.01	0.2
116	RN10-2014-1737	DH	RN-10	H				10	2.6	32	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	14.2	<0.01	0.2
117	RN10-2014-1792A	DH	RN-10	H				5	3.1	27	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	4.3	<0.01	0.2
118	RN10-2014-1800	DH	RN-10	H				4	2	28	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	15.3	<0.01	0.2
119	RN10-2014-1828	DH	RN-10	H				8	2.4	35	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	5.2	<0.01	<0.1
120	RN10-2014-1832	DH	RN-10	H				10	2.7	31	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	4.5	<0.01	0.1
121	RN-17_2700m	DH	RN-17B	-			0.037	42	4.4	62.6	0.8	14.3	0.3		15.4		<0.1
122	RN22-2013-1051	DH	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	29	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.2
123	RN22-2013-1064A	DH	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	13	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	<0.1
124	RN22-2013-1088	DH	RN-22	H				<3	<0.4	20	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.2
125	RN22-2013-1636	DH	RN-22	H				44	1.2	86	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.1
126	RN22-2013-1638A	DH	RN-22	H				25	0.9	209	<0.1	4	4	<10	4.5	<0.01	0.3
127	RN22-2013-1638B	DH	RN-22	H				25	1.2	43	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.1
128	RN22-2013-1642	DH	RN-22	H				33	1.1	94	<0.1	<3	<3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.2
129	RN22-2013-1646	DH	RN-22	H				44	3.1	98	<0.1	3	3	<10	<0.5	<0.01	0.1

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Th ppm	Sc ppm	Y ppm	Zr ppm	Nb ppm	Hf ppm	Ta ppm	La ppm	Ce ppm	Pr ppm	Nd ppm	Sm ppm	Eu ppm
97	22RN669	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2		<2.4	3	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
98	RN10-2014-835	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	2	0.9		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
99	RN10-2014-870	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	2.9	1.5		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	1.1	0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
100	RN10-2014-904	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	7.4	4.1		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	2.8	0.3	<0.4	0.2	0.2
101	RN10-2014-1085	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	6	0.7		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
102	RN10-2014-1095A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	5.4	3.1		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	2	0.3	<0.4	<0.1	0.1
103	RN10-2014-1097A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	11.4	7.3		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	5	0.7	1	0.7	0.4
104	RN10-2014-1098A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	11.1	6.9		2.8	<10	13.2	<0.4	4.2	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.3
105	RN10-2014-1099	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	10.7	7		3.1	<10	<0.2	<0.4	6	0.8	1.3	0.7	0.4
106	RN10-2014-1120	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	12.1	8		2.6	<10	0.2	<0.4	5.1	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.4
107	RN10-2014-1136	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	7.6	4.1		3.7	<10	23.7	<0.4	2.8	0.4	<0.4	0.2	0.2
108	RN10-2014-1148	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	5.6	3.2		2.7	<10	4.8	<0.4	2.9	0.3	<0.4	0.1	0.2
109	RN10-2014-1168	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	7.9	0.6		<2.4	<10	0.4	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	0.4	<0.1	<0.1
110	RN10-2014-1198	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	5.8	3.4		3.8	<10	16.3	<0.4	2.5	0.3	<0.4	0.1	0.2
111	RN10-2014-1245	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	7.7	2.3		9.6	<10	221	<0.4	2	0.2	<0.4	<0.1	0.1
112	RN10-2014-1504	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	4.6	2.7		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	2.4	0.3	<0.4	<0.1	0.1
113	RN10-2014-1575	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	0.8	0.6		<2.4	10	<0.2	1.5	3.3	0.2	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
114	RN10-2014-1668	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	2.8	2		<2.4	<10	<0.2	<0.4	1.7	0.2	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
115	RN10-2014-1680	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	0.7	0.8		<2.4	20	<0.2	0.5	0.9	<0.1	0.5	<0.1	<0.1
116	RN10-2014-1737	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	2	1.9		<2.4	10	<0.2	0.9	1.9	0.2	1.5	<0.1	0.1
117	RN10-2014-1792A	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	0.6	0.7		<2.4	10	<0.2	0.9	1.2	<0.1	1	<0.1	<0.1
118	RN10-2014-1800	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	3.2	1.9		<2.4	<10	1.2	0.8	1.7	0.2	1.3	<0.1	<0.1
119	RN10-2014-1828	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	3.5	2		<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.8	1.9	0.2	1.4	<0.1	<0.1
120	RN10-2014-1832	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	3.4	2.1		<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.8	1.9	0.2	1.3	<0.1	<0.1
121	RN-17_2700m	DH	RN-17B	-	<0.1	2.2	1.6	7	1.4	0.2	<0.1	0.6	1.4	0.2	0.7	0.2	0.06
122	RN22-2013-1051	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	0.8	0.5		<2.4	20	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	0.5	<0.1	<0.1
123	RN22-2013-1064A	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	0.2		<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
124	RN22-2013-1088	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	0.7	0.5		<2.4	10	<0.2	<0.4	<0.8	<0.1	<0.4	<0.1	<0.1
125	RN22-2013-1636	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	15.4	10.4		8.4	<10	<0.2	3	8	1.1	5.7	1.5	0.6
126	RN22-2013-1638A	DH	RN-22	H	0.3	27.5	26		11.3	10	0.5	9.1	24.1	3.2	17.9	4.6	1.7
127	RN22-2013-1638B	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	5.2	3.6		<2.4	<10	<0.2	0.9	2.8	0.4	2	0.4	0.2
128	RN22-2013-1642	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	13.1	9.2		4.5	<10	<0.2	2.8	7.4	1	5.3	1.3	0.6
129	RN22-2013-1646	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	14.8	10.6		2.9	<10	<0.2	2.9	8	1	5.8	1.5	0.7

Appendix B1 cont. All bulk geochemical data for scale samples from the Reykjanes geothermal field

ID #	Sample ID	Sampling location	Location/ well	WP	Gd ppm	Tb ppm	Dy ppm	Ho ppm	Er ppm	Tm ppm	Yb ppm	Lu ppm
97	22RN669	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
98	RN10-2014-835	DH	RN-10	H	0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
99	RN10-2014-870	DH	RN-10	H	0.2	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	0.2	<0.1	0.1	<0.05
100	RN10-2014-904	DH	RN-10	H	0.6	0.1	0.6	<0.2	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.05
101	RN10-2014-1085	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.16
102	RN10-2014-1095A	DH	RN-10	H	0.5	<0.1	0.6	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
103	RN10-2014-1097A	DH	RN-10	H	1.1	0.2	1.4	0.3	0.8	0.1	0.7	0.11
104	RN10-2014-1098A	DH	RN-10	H	1	0.2	1.1	0.2	0.7	0.1	0.6	<0.05
105	RN10-2014-1099	DH	RN-10	H	1	0.2	1.2	0.2	0.8	0.1	0.6	<0.05
106	RN10-2014-1120	DH	RN-10	H	1	0.2	1.2	0.3	0.9	0.1	0.6	<0.05
107	RN10-2014-1136	DH	RN-10	H	0.6	0.1	0.7	<0.2	0.5	<0.1	0.4	<0.05
108	RN10-2014-1148	DH	RN-10	H	0.5	<0.1	0.5	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
109	RN10-2014-1168	DH	RN-10	H	0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.12
110	RN10-2014-1198	DH	RN-10	H	0.5	<0.1	0.6	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
111	RN10-2014-1245	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
112	RN10-2014-1504	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.5	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.3	<0.05
113	RN10-2014-1575	DH	RN-10	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
114	RN10-2014-1668	DH	RN-10	H	0.3	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	0.2	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
115	RN10-2014-1680	DH	RN-10	H	0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
116	RN10-2014-1737	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.2	<0.1	0.1	<0.05
117	RN10-2014-1792A	DH	RN-10	H	0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
118	RN10-2014-1800	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
119	RN10-2014-1828	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.3	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
120	RN10-2014-1832	DH	RN-10	H	0.4	<0.1	0.4	<0.2	0.2	<0.1	0.2	<0.05
121	RN-17_2700m	DH	RN-17B	-	0.2	<0.1	0.3	<0.1	0.2	<0.1	0.1	<0.05
122	RN22-2013-1051	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
123	RN22-2013-1064A	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.05
124	RN22-2013-1088	DH	RN-22	H	<0.1	<0.1	<0.3	<0.2	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.09
125	RN22-2013-1636	DH	RN-22	H	1.9	0.3	2	0.5	1.5	0.2	1.2	0.07
126	RN22-2013-1638A	DH	RN-22	H	5.3	0.9	5.3	1.2	3.6	0.5	2.8	0.1
127	RN22-2013-1638B	DH	RN-22	H	0.7	<0.1	0.7	<0.2	0.5	<0.1	0.4	<0.05
128	RN22-2013-1642	DH	RN-22	H	1.8	0.3	1.7	0.4	1.2	0.1	0.9	<0.05
129	RN22-2013-1646	DH	RN-22	H	1.9	0.3	2	0.5	1.4	0.2	1.1	<0.05

Appendix B2.1. Images of downhole RN-10 scale samples and the fragmented chip-like nature of the samples as received from ISOR.

1) Hemimorphic pyramidal wurtzite crystals (collected at various depths) field of view (FOV) 30 mm. 2) Chalcopyrite chips (1085 m) FOV 30 mm. 3) Bulk sample with platy sphalerite, chalcopyrite, Fe-oxide alteration and silicified volcanic chips (1085m) FOV 50mm. 4) Chalcopyrite in sphalerite chips, including 'spotted' chalcopyrite texture (1120 m) FOV 30 mm. 5) Illustration of special method used to dry samples in petri dishes after separation into individual separates and then washed (**Appendix B2.3** for method). Note the vials for individual separates to the right. 6) RN-10 samples laid out from along rows from left to right with increasing depth. Sample prep details are available in **Appendices B2.2** and **2.3**. Further images are presented in **Appendix B5**.

Appendix B2.2. Flow chart for initial sample cleaning and separation of sub-sample for downhole RN-10 scale samples.

Appendix B2.3.

Preparation method for RN-10 scales

1. Labelling

- 1.1. Label all separate parts of sample boxes with sample number (RN10-2014-### where ### is depth).

2. Sub-sampling

- 2.1. For each sample weigh and record sample original received weight (excluding box and lid).
- 2.2. In the original sample box, split the sample into two representative sub-samples, ensuring that if any small/large/potentially interesting chips are present that they are split evenly between the two samples. Avoid bias as much as possible.
- 2.3. Place sub-sample on left into a glass petri dish using scoop and/or spatula.
- 2.4. Weigh and record weights of both sub-samples (excluding box and lid).
- 2.5. Place second sub-sample into the fume hood and dry.
- 2.6. Store second sub-sample for any later analysis required.

3. Picking sample separates (while still wet)

- 3.1. Under the binocular microscope sort chips into types in the petri dish. Examples could include; volcanic chips, quartz (white grains), green grains, primarily pyrite, chalcopyrite etc.
- 3.2. Take a bulk representative sample for XRD.
- 3.3. Describe sample.
- 3.4. Pass a magnet over the sample to check for metal fragment/chips from pipes and remove if any present. If a significant component of sample, collect a magnetic separate.

4. Washing sub-sample

- 4.1. Place sorted chip-types into individual glass vials and label with a) sample number and b) chip description, for example; RN10-2014-##### py chips
- 4.2. Fill glass vial to close to full with Milli-Q water, put lid on and shake the sample carefully to ensure that chips do not break, but that the sample is well washed.
- 4.3. Leave to settle for 1 hour or more.
- 4.4. Decant clear liquid.

5. Drying sub-sample

- 5.1. Post-washing, spread chips as thinly as possible in labelled petri dish (ensuring no mixing of chip types) and dry in fumehood.
- 5.2. After drying, weigh separates and record.

6. Preparation for analytical methods

Samples needed for:

- XRD on bulk representative sample (pulverised) (PRIORITY 1)
- Reflected light microscopy (puck) (PRIORITY 1)
- SEM (direct mount) (PRIORITY 2)

- EMPA (puck) (PRIORITY 2)
- Selected separates for XRD e.g. magnetic portions (PRIORITY 3)

6.1. XRD bulk representative sample/separates

- 6.1.1. Using pestle and mortar grind sample until fine grained and no fragments are left (taking care to not damage crystal structure as much as possible or create too much heat).
- 6.1.2. Store in labeled glass vials pending pressing into XRD puck.

6.2. Reflected light microscopy/EMPA puck

Puck assembly:

- 6.2.1. Label the sample number on a microprobe puck ring.
- 6.2.2. Place double sided circular sticker into round aluminum tray (Figure #) and remove top sticker.
- 6.2.3. Decide which components to go into the puck based on sample notes.
- 6.2.4. Place puck onto double sided sticker in round aluminum tray.
- 6.2.5. Select representative chips from each chip-type and press onto double sided tape within ring (preferably with a flat side down).

Puck setting:

- 6.2.6. Once 5-6 pucks have been made, make epoxy mix using an epoxy such as Araldite.
 - 6.2.6.1. Set hotplate to between 70-75°C.
 - 6.2.6.2. In a new aluminum tray mix epoxy using proportions (for Araldite) of 1 ml of reagent A and 0.3 ml of reagent B per puck. Ensure that all no air bubbles are present in syringes after drawing reagents. It is advisable to make no more than 5-6 samples at one time as the epoxy begins to set.
 - 6.2.6.3. Add epoxy slowly to the aluminum tray containing the puck. Coat the chips individually before filling up the puck.
 - 6.2.6.4. Set in 50°C oven to dry overnight.

Polishing:

- 6.2.7. Remove tray and sticky plastic sticker from the puck. If the sticker cannot be fully removed then it will be removed during polishing in step 6.2.8.
- 6.2.8. Polish puck using ####um, ####um, ####um and ####um sandpaper in order of fineness, beginning with the most coarse (### um).
 - 6.2.8.1. Approximately 30-40 polishing sweeps per sandpaper fineness appears optimal.
 - 6.2.8.2. Ensure the samples are clean and dry when transferring to finer sandpaper.
- 6.2.9. Transfer samples to the Tegrapol polishing machine and polish for 5 minutes with 3 micron polishing fluid and finish with 3 minutes with 1 micron polishing fluid.
 - 6.2.9.1. If samples appear delicate or are at danger of being picked out of the epoxy during polishing, polish for one minute intervals and check the sample.
- 6.2.10. Clean samples and check polishing quality under a microscope. If necessary, increase polishing time on the Tegrapol.

Appendix B3.1. Major element EMP analyses for downhole RN-10 scale samples (data in wt.%).

Analysis	Sample ID	Mineral	Fe	S	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	Total
1	std	std	30.43	34.57	34.53	0	0.1405	0.0113	0.0109	99.69
2	std	std	0.0285	33.24	0.0244	67.05	0.0874	0.2408	0	100.67
3	std	std	0.0256	0.0037	0.1222	0	0	59.52	40.07	99.74
4	std	std	0	13.12	0.0037	0.0195	86.28	0	0	99.42
5	std	std	0.0128	0	0.1622	0	0	59.69	39.77	99.64
6	std	std	0.0074	0	0.1093	0.02	0	60.17	39.85	100.16
7	RN10-2014-660	el	2.06	23.58	1.66	29.62	20.03	1.29	0.1861	78.43
8	RN10-2014-660	el	2.16	27.06	1.57	43.18	9.55	1.51	0.199	85.23
9	RN10-2014-660	el	4.79	16.53	4.28	7.43	0.0189	0	0	33.05
10	RN10-2014-660	el	16.64	34.2	20.32	25.15	0.0988	0.0406	0.0692	96.52
11	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.18	33.33	1.23	62.36	0.024	0.2669	0.0391	100.43
12	RN10-2014-660	cpy	28.02	35.04	32.1	6.18	0.0896	0	0.0341	101.46
13	RN10-2014-660	el	5.81	28.6	9.13	30.43	0.0338	0.053	18.43	92.49
14	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.55	32.74	1.29	59.8	0.099	0.2823	0.2119	97.97
15	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.51	33.29	1.23	62.44	0.2106	0.1003	0.022	100.80
16	RN10-2014-660	sph	2.72	32.88	1.54	60.3	0.1394	0	0.1325	97.71
17	RN10-2014-660	soh	2.96	31.94	2.34	58.78	0.0465	0.193	0.2841	96.54
18	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.63	27.52	2.01	52.19	0.0626	0	0.1577	85.57
19	RN10-2014-660	cpy	29.08	34.87	33.7	2.48	0.0425	0	0.02	100.19
20	RN10-2014-660	cpy	29.11	34.88	33.43	2.85	0.0425	0.2698	0.0217	100.60
21	RN10-2014-660	cpy	16.22	34.26	17.53	34.11	0.1109	0.1566	0.0547	102.44
22	RN10-2014-660	cpy	29.46	34.93	33.81	2.32	0.0889	0.1501	0.0128	100.77
23	RN10-2014-660	cpy	23.81	25.87	27.38	9.1	0.0645	0.0038	0.0227	86.25
24	RN10-2014-660	cpy	30.82	34.78	34.76	0	0.1155	0.2134	0.082	100.77
25	RN10-2014-660	cpy	30.79	34.97	34.47	0	0.0268	0	0.1176	100.37
26	RN10-2014-660	sph	7.78	33.78	8.27	49.6	0.0998	0	0.1458	99.68
27	RN10-2014-660	sph	2.76	33.15	2.15	61.73	0.2756	0	0.6122	100.68
28	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.23	33.33	0.0582	63.81	0.0544	0	0.0109	100.49
29	RN10-2014-660	sph	3.62	33.44	0.0491	63.46	0.0766	0	0.0028	100.65
30	RN10-2014-1098A	el	26.68	33.01	31.24	4.5	0.0214	3.59	1.18	100.22
31	RN10-2014-1098A	el	11.53	12.26	9.23	17.5	0	2.27	0.6508	53.44
32	RN10-2014-1098A	el	3	0.6224	3.5	0.976	0	75.41	20.68	104.19
33	RN10-2014-1098A	el	2.91	0.707	3.58	0.8623	0	75.77	20.51	104.34
34	RN10-2014-1098A	el	1.23	0.3987	2.31	1.9	0	76.83	19.98	102.65
35	RN10-2014-1098A	el	1.42	0.9213	2.5	1.88	0	76.71	19.87	103.30
36	RN10-2014-1098A	cpy	30.75	35.08	34.3	0	0.0076	0	0.0271	100.16
37	RN10-2014-1098A	cpy	30.47	35.03	34.56	0	0.0918	0.2274	0.0279	100.41
38	RN10-2014-1098A	cpy	30.68	35.14	34.28	0	0.13	0.0485	0.019	100.30
39	RN10-2014-1098A	sph	3.53	33.45	0.4287	62.64	0	0.1919	0	100.24
40	RN10-2014-1098A	sph	3.64	33.48	0.3988	62.47	0.0542	0	0	100.04
41	RN10-2014-1098A	sph	3.42	33.48	0.3733	63.07	0.0904	0	0	100.43
42	std	std	30.38	34.94	34.64	0	0.0879	0.1193	0	100.17
43	std	std	0.0225	33.45	0.0127	67.07	0.1191	0.3938	0.0112	101.08
44	std	std	0.0168	0	0.2024	0.0335	0	79.73	19.83	99.81
45	std	std	30.54	34.76	34.79	0	0.1175	0.0151	0.014	100.24
46	std	std	0.0124	33.32	0.0195	67.3	0.0937	0.2303	0.0027	100.98
47	std	std	0.0285	0.004	0.1701	0.0233	0	79.04	19.9	99.17
48	RN10-2014-1098A	py	47.69	53.89	0.0025	0.0003	0.0497	0	0	101.63
49	RN10-2014-1098A	py	47.73	54.11	0.0026	0	0.1546	0.2573	0	102.25
50	RN10-2014-1098A	py	47.83	54.12	0	0	0.1492	0.1289	0.0007	102.23
51	RN10-2014-1668	sph	7.74	34.22	0.7678	57.03	0.1451	0.2242	0.0159	100.14
52	RN10-2014-1668	sph	6.83	33.86	0.9855	57.21	0.1149	0.0896	0	99.09
53	RN10-2014-1668	sph	7.73	34.03	0.8823	56.97	0	0	0.0116	99.62
54	RN10-2014-1668	cpy	30.71	35.21	34.18	0	0.1428	0.2747	0.0111	100.53
55	RN10-2014-1668	cpy	30.85	35.18	34.21	0	0.1738	0	0.0176	100.43
56	RN10-2014-1668	cpy	30.71	35.24	34.41	0	0.1102	0.0942	0	100.56
57	RN10-2014-1832	sph	3.76	33.69	0.0524	62.6	0.1055	0	0	100.21
58	RN10-2014-1832	sph	3.95	33.73	0.0372	62.26	0.0691	0.0672	0	100.11
59	RN10-2014-1832	sph	4.96	33.98	0.0269	61.21	0.1216	0.157	0.0008	100.46
60	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	31.08	35.38	33.91	0	0.1005	0.3957	0.0123	100.88

Appendix B3.1. cont. Major element EMP analyses for downhole RN-10 sulfide samples (data in wt.%).

Analysis	Sample ID	Mineral	Fe	S	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	Total
61	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	31.28	35.39	33.68	0	0.0888	0.1133	0	100.55
62	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	31.12	35.31	33.83	0	0.1874	0.1283	0.0013	100.58
63	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	30.92	34.89	33.52	0.0634	0.0116	0	0.0047	99.41
64	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	30.7	35.35	33.51	0.0574	0.0135	0	0.0102	99.64
65	RN10-2014-1832	cpy	30.55	35.3	33.53	0.4647	0.1335	0	0.0149	99.99
66	RN10-2014-1832	sph	5.78	33.8	0.7627	59.43	0.1236	0.1196	0.0012	100.02
67	RN10-2014-1832	sph	5.25	33.88	0.4634	60.32	0.1135	0.1009	0.0078	100.14
68	RN10-2014-1832	sph	5.52	33.77	0.5391	60.01	0	0.3252	0.0061	100.17
69	std	std	30.43	35.36	34.68	0	0.0465	0	0.0031	100.52
70	std	sph	0.0015	33.52	0.0031	67.25	0.0164	0.0074	0	100.80
71	std	std	0.0196	0.0166	0.1681	0.0252	0	79.98	20.04	100.25
72	RN10-2014-1832	bn	8.77	28	47.1	10.85	0.0596	0.0111	0.5361	95.33
73	RN10-2014-1832	py	45.07	52.11	1.53	0.5183	0.2138	0.0818	0.034	99.56
74	RN10-2014-1098A	bn	13.09	27.79	59.44	0	0.0317	0	0.1552	100.51
75	RN10-2014-1098A	bn	16.23	30	53.2	0	0.0748	0.1523	0.2537	99.91
76	RN10-2014-1098A	bn	14.38	31.27	52.13	0	0.1451	0	1.14	99.07

Appendix B3.2. Major element EMP analyses for selected silicates (mainly for identification) in downhole RN-10 scale samples (data in wt.%)

Analysis	Sample ID	Mineral	MgO	MnO	Cr2O3	Al2O3	TiO2	NiO	FeO	SiO2	Total
1	ilm std	std	0.3453	4.8	0.0252	0.0318	45.67	0.0108	46.59	0.0523	97.53
2	chm std	std	15.34	0.0633	60.82	9.89	0.1181	0.186	13.15	0.0468	99.61
3	an std	std	0.0397	0	0	33.73	0.0215	0.0018	0.4165	45.64	79.85
4	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.4144	0.2306	0.0301	0.039	0.0522	93.09	0.7129	94.57
5	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	1.0717	0.3562	0.0823	0.0372	0.1002	91.4	1.2113	94.26
6	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.9318	0.1941	0.1064	0.0133	0.1375	91.71	1.2337	94.33
7	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	1.2155	0.1983	0.0478	0.0245	0.1307	91.2	1.6259	94.44
8	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.9736	0.1595	0.0631	0.0164	0.1289	91.72	1.4355	94.50
9	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.0233	0.0648	0.0081	0.017	0.0109	94.76	0.0105	94.89
10	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.0506	0.0469	0	0.0167	0.009	94.57	0.0358	94.73
11	RN10-2014-660	mt	0	0.0444	0.0647	0	0.0142	0.0075	95.08	0.0389	95.25
12	RN10-2014-660	unk	0.0508	0.055	0.0581	0.0154	120.58	0	3.23	0.0038	123.99
13	rt std	std	0	0	0	0	99.83	0	0.0156	0	99.85
14	RN10-2014-660	rt	0	0	0	0	96.51	0	2.77	0	99.28

Appendix B4: The mineralogy of downhole geothermal scales from well RN-10, Reykjanes geothermal field, Iceland

Report produced by Hannah L. J. Grant
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Introduction

The objective of this study is to characterize the mineralogy of downhole scales from production well RN-10 located in the seawater-dominated Reykjanes high-temperature geothermal system.

Well RN-10 was completed in 1999 to a depth of 2046 metres (m) with a maximum temperature of 319°C measured at 1900 m depth. The most recent temperature and pressure profiles of well RN-10 are shown in Figures B4.1 and B4.2.

Methods

A total of 30 sample boxes were received (including duplicates) with 24 samples from various downhole depths used in this study (Table B4.1). Each sample box was subsampled following the procedures in Appendices 1 and 2. These samples consist of small, angular to sub-angular chips, with the majority of the sample <5 mm in size. Under a binocular microscope, each subsample was described, photographed (Figs. B4.3a-d), and individual chip separates picked into glass vials. These separates were washed with Milli-Q water to remove residual seawater as much as possible to prevent any later seawater evaporation, and hence the possibility of masking XRD analyses with a strong salt signal (Fig. B4.3e). The subsamples were left to dry for over a week before selection of chips for mounting into epoxy-filled pucks for reflected light petrography, microprobe and SEM analysis. As the samples were mounted in pucks, only reflected light microscopy was possible. Therefore, the petrological descriptions in the following sections are primarily for sulfides and other minerals identifiable under reflected light using a Zeiss petrographic microscope and incorporated digital camera. Electron microprobe analysis (EMPA) was conducted using a JEOL 8200 Superprobe with an acceleration voltage of 15 kV and a beam current of 50 nA. A range of natural and synthetic minerals were used as standards and are detailed in Supp. Info. B4.1. Back-scattered electron (BSE) images and spectra were also collected on the JEOL 8200 Superprobe. XRD analysis was performed on a finely-ground bulk representative powder on a Philips X-Ray diffractometer. The software package MacDiff (version 4.2.5) was used to manually identify mineral phases. All analyses were performed at GEOMAR.

Mineralogy of textures

The textures and minerals observed are detailed below for each individual sample from the specified downhole depth in well RN-10 (Fig. B4.3f). The depth of sampling is relative to the surface wellhead. Chip textures have been characterized into types and are described in the following section and illustrated in Figures B4.4 to B4.7. Table B4.2 indicates the abundance of minerals from hand specimens, Table B4.3 the abundance of individual minerals at a petrographic scale, and Table B4.4 shows the presence or absence of individual chip types.

Mineralogical and textural descriptions

Sphalerite/wurtzite

Sphalerite and wurtzite are the most common sulfides in well RN-10 and occur in a variety of textures. There are two distinct habits of wurtzite identified in hand specimen from well RN-10: a red-brown hemimorphic pyramidal habit (Fig. B4.3a) at depths of 0-660 m to 1245 m and a golden-brown, resinous bladed habit from 1136 m downwards. Apart from the two distinctive types of wurtzite, it is difficult to distinguish between sphalerite and wurtzite in hand specimen or through reflected light petrography. X-ray diffraction analyses on a bulk sample indicate that wurtzite is present at most depths (Supp. Info. B4.2), but there are some samples in which red-brown hemimorphic wurtzite was identified in hand specimen, but is not seen in XRD analyses. As described in the previous section, in hand specimen sphalerite/wurtzite occurs as banded chips often with a one-sided coating of chalcopyrite and as massive sphalerite/wurtzite chips with no obvious banding and which may contain 'spots' of chalcopyrite.

At the petrographic scale, the most common texture of sphalerite and/or wurtzite is that of type 1 chips (Figs. B4.1a and B4.1b), with fine-grained sphalerite and/or wurtzite with inclusions of earlier chalcopyrite with variable proportions of bornite and/or covellite (often in a sub-parallel alignment) giving a 'mottled' or 'blotchy' appearance to the sphalerite. Most chips with growth textures are ambiguous in terms of growth direction, but some are unambiguous and have a clear paragenesis. The majority of textures in type 1 chips also display a preferred alignment or growth direction (Figs. B4.1a and B4.1b), often through alignment of laths and dendrites or changes in grain size or porosity. It is however, difficult to distinguish between sphalerite and wurtzite in these samples. It is likely that the early nucleation textures are wurtzite (Fig. B4.4b), but this is not confirmed. This early nascent texture closely resembles Zn-S rich particulate 'smoke' from black smokers at the seafloor with the beginning of organization into the hexagonal mineral shape of sphalerite/wurtzite. The dendritic chalcopyrite within sphalerite is likely caused by rapid co-precipitation and chalcopyrite growing epitaxially on skeletal sphalerite or wurtzite crystals. This texture is observed at depths of 0-660 m, 870 m, 904 m and 1668 m. When sphalerite/wurtzite fully crystallizes, the chalcopyrite is manifested as blebs within the sphalerite and often shows no indication as to how it was formed (e.g., Fig. B4.5i). This is a common texture in type 1 chips (Fig. B4.4).

Type 4 chips consist of coarse-grained sphalerite/wurtzite that also has a 'mottled' appearance due to chalcopyrite, bornite, and/or covellite inclusions. As in chip type 1, the Cu-bearing sulfides are commonly aligned, but as crystal shapes become more developed, these inclusions are often sub-parallel to the crystal edges, or aligned in laths, such as in Figure B4.5j.

Chip type 5 is likely to be primarily wurtzite as the chips with this texture are either the red-brown hemimorphic wurtzite crystals, or the golden-brown bladed resinous wurtzite. The wurtzite in this chip type does not contain inclusions of chalcopyrite/bornite and unlike chip types 1 or 4, it is not 'mottled' or 'blotchy', but 'clean' and has strong internal red reflections (Fig. B4.5). As with type 4 chips, any chalcopyrite inclusions are aligned parallel or sub-parallel to the edge of the crystal. Other Cu-bearing minerals such as digenite or bornite are not observed in association with this chip type. At and below 1680 m depth, a distinctive texture of 'sawtooth' bladed sphalerite/wurtzite with coarse chalcopyrite is observed. Other similar chips below this depth indicate a progression from this texture to

the coarse-grained wurtzite of type 5 (Fig. B4.4h) and therefore it is considered that this ‘sawtooth’ bladed texture is likely wurtzite, and also a type 5 chip (Fig. B4.6g).

Chip type 7 is a hybrid combination of the fine-grained ‘mottled’ sphalerite (plus chalcopyrite) of chip type 1 which precipitated after earlier-formed coarse clasts of massive chalcopyrite, or more rarely sphalerite. This chip type primarily occurs between 0-660 m and 1245 m, but one chip is observed at 1832 m depth (Fig. B4.4j).

In addition to the textures described above, other rare but potentially important textures of sphalerite/wurtzite and chalcopyrite are observed. Chip type 8 is best described as ‘hopper’ crystals of sphalerite (Fig. B4.4k). This coarse, bulbous texture is indicative of supersaturated solutions where sphalerite is trying to crystallize rapidly and leaves porosity gaps between crystals. This is similar to the common ‘hopper’ texture that salt crystals develop when crystallizing from supersaturated solutions. Small inclusions of chalcopyrite occur aligned along growth planes(?), and is similar to the alignment of chalcopyrite inclusions in type 4 and 5 coarse-grained sphalerite/wurtzite. Limited chips from 1136 m and 1198 m also show nascent development of the ‘hopper’ sphalerite texture (Fig. B4.5k). A distinctive, but rare texture of sphalerite also includes a massive, colloform sphalerite and chalcopyrite chip from 1099 m depth; this texture is reminiscent of minerals forming at the modern seafloor (Fig. B4.5c).

Sphalerite at depths of 660, 1098, 1668, and 1832 metres were analyzed by EMPA (Table B4.5). All sphalerite contains <10% Fe with the highest Fe contents of 7.4 wt. % at 1668 m. Sphalerite from 660 m has the highest Cu contents (2.0 wt. %) and lower Zn (59.4 wt.%) compared to stoichiometric sphalerite (64.1 wt.%). At 1098 and 1832 metres depth, sphalerite is close to the stoichiometric composition and does not contain significant Cu or Ag. Analyses at these depths indicate that there is 1100-1300 ppm of Au, but these analyses are around the detection limit of 1267 ppm for Au in these samples.

Chalcopyrite

Chalcopyrite is abundant throughout the scales from well RN-10 and in hand specimen occurs as a single sided coating on sphalerite chips, as ‘spots’ in massive sphalerite and as coarse, monomineralic bladed chips. At the petrographic scale, chalcopyrite is most common as blebs both within, and interstitial to dendritic sphalerite laths (Type 1; Fig. B4.5a) with variable proportions of bornite, covellite and more rarely an association with digenite. As Figure B4.4a shows, both sphalerite and chalcopyrite can have distinct growth textures in type 1 chips, and chalcopyrite in particular is often observed to have discrete banding perpendicular to the alignment of sphalerite laths or dendrites (Fig. B4.5a). Chalcopyrite also occurs as interstitial and often coarser blebs in type 1 chips, and could be pre-, syn- or post-sphalerite formation. Chalcopyrite also occurs as coarse-grained, bladed, massive chips with or without sphalerite inclusions (Type 2; Fig. B4.4c). The amount of chalcopyrite generally increases downhole, but there are two distinct chalcopyrite-rich intervals in RN-10 from 1095-1168 m and 1737-1800 m, with these intervals containing a higher proportion of massive chalcopyrite chips (Table B4.4). In type 1 chips from the interval 1095-1168 m, bornite is more common than chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite also occurs as disseminations in type 6 silicified wall rock chips (Fig. B4.4i).

Chalcopyrite from depths of 660, 1098, 1668, and 1832 metres were analyzed by EMPA (Table B4.5). Chalcopyrite from 660 m depth contains on average 7.1 wt.% Zn and less Cu (30.9 wt.%) compared to the stoichiometric composition of 34.6 wt.% Cu. This could be a

Cu-Zn-Fe-S intermediate solid solution similar to that reported for sphalerite at Reykjanes by (Hardardóttir et al. 2010) or zincian chalcopyrite. More analyses are needed to investigate this. Chalcopyrite from 1098, 1668 and 1832 m does not contain significant Zn or Ag and is close to the stoichiometric composition of chalcopyrite. As with sphalerite, EMPA data indicates that chalcopyrite contains 1000-1200 ppm of Au, but these analyses are lower than the detection limit of 1267 ppm for Au in these samples.

Electrum

The highest abundance of electrum is observed in scales from 0-660 m depth and from 1095-1099 m and decreases in abundance downhole from approximately 1148 m depth, but is still present at 1832 m depth. Electrum is strongly correlated with the presence of chalcopyrite and is often in close spatial association with sphalerite.

Electrum is associated with four chip textures: 1) type 1 dendritic sphalerite and blebby chalcopyrite, 2) type 2 coarse-grained to massive chalcopyrite, 3) type 4 coarse-grained sphalerite and chalcopyrite, and 4) type 7 'hybrid' chips of coarse-grained chalcopyrite or sphalerite with later dendritic sphalerite and blebby chalcopyrite (Table B4.4). In chip type 1, electrum ranges from <0.5 to 3 microns in size and occurs either in chalcopyrite, at the grain boundary of chalcopyrite and sphalerite, or more rarely in sphalerite not directly touching chalcopyrite (Figs. B4.5a and B4.5e). The presence of electrum in type 1 chips is ubiquitous throughout well RN-10 (except for at 1680 m depth where no electrum was observed), but it does noticeably decrease in size and abundance downhole from approximately 1148 m. From 1668 m, electrum only occurs in type 1 fine-grained dendritic sphalerite and chalcopyrite. Type 1 chips which have the 'smoke' texture of Figure B4.6h contain electrum (~1 µm in size) at depths from 0-660 m to 904 m but not at deeper depths. This could be due to the lack of chips with this texture deeper than 904 m, but where this 'smoke' texture occurs at deeper depths (1668 m and 1800 m), electrum is not observed. Figure B4.7 is an SEM EDS image of the distribution of electrum grains in one sample from 660 m depth. As can be seen, there are multiple bright grains that are likely to be electrum. This is far more than is observed under the microscope by eye, even at 100x magnification.

Electrum is also associated with coarse, bladed chalcopyrite (e.g., Fig. B4.5g), where it occurs in close spatial association with small sphalerite inclusions in chalcopyrite, but often also within massive chalcopyrite where no sphalerite is present (Types 2, 4 and 7). This electrum is often larger (up to 8 µm in size) and more 'gold' in colour, especially from the interval 1095-1099 m (Figs. B4.5f and B4.5h). It is likely that there is more Au in the electrum grains within this interval. Due to the fine-grained nature of the majority of the electrum grains, it was difficult to analyze the composition of the electrum as the microprobe beam often incorporated surrounding chalcopyrite or sphalerite. However, analysis of a larger electrum grain from 1098 m indicated an approximate electrum composition of 76% Au and 20% Ag. The remainder of the analysis was composed of Fe, Cu, Zn and S, which is likely to be incorporation of the surrounding chalcopyrite and sphalerite (Table B4.5). It should be noted that this electrum grain was distinctly more 'Au' in colour than most other electrum in RN-10, but as this particular electrum was one of the largest observed, therefore it was the only electrum grain in the 4 samples probed which was conducive for analysis.

Electrum is never observed in type 5 chips where the coarse-grained 'clean' sphalerite or wurtzite only contains chalcopyrite inclusions along growth planes rather than as inclusions within the sphalerite, as compared to 'mottled' sphalerite from types 1, 2, 4 and 7. Electrum

is also rarely observed in disseminated chalcopyrite within heavily silicified wall rock(?) chips (type 6; Table B4.4). However, this could be sampling bias as sulfide-bearing chips were preferentially chosen for this study. Electrum is never observed in magnetite or the sphalerite ‘hopper’ crystals (type 8), only rarely in spatial association with fractured, rare pyrite within chalcopyrite (e.g., Fig. B4.6d), but is observed in the colloform sphalerite and chalcopyrite texture described from 1099 m depth.

Magnetite

Magnetite is common in well RN-10 and primarily occurs as monomineralic, massive chips which may or may not have distinct rhythmic banding (Figs. B4.4d, B4.4e and B4.6a). Magnetite chips are common from 0-660 m to 1504 m and contain exsolved rutile up to 10 μm in size (Fig. B4.6b). Small inclusions of chalcopyrite occur in the magnetite in addition to an unknown silver, high reflectance mineral in fractures, but this phase was too small to analyze with the microprobe. The magnetite chips are commonly banded and the individual bands are often of similar widths. The magnetite chips also have a blocky, banded texture that could result from unmixing of an amorphous Fe-Si-O phase and subsequent development of Leisegang texture. Leisegang texture produces a volume change that could explain the equally distributed blocky banding in Figure B4.6c, and the EMPA analyses of magnetite from 660 m, which contains 3000-7600 ppm Si (Table B4.6 and Fig. B4.8). Further work needs to be performed on magnetite as it is abundant in RN-10, and hence these more oxidized conditions may help in understanding how the Reykjanes hydrothermal fluids are so enriched in elements such as Cu and Au.

Magnetite chips from depths 1095-1245 m have a thick coating of Fe-oxide, potentially both goethite and hematite. Below 1504 m, massive magnetite chips are not present but fine-grained and minor disseminated magnetite is observed in highly silicified wall rock chips (Table B4.4).

Pyrite

Compared to the other sulfides described for well RN-10, pyrite is not common and is primarily observed as rare massive chips at limited depths between 0-660 m and 1245 m, but does not appear to be specifically associated with any depth interval. One chip from 0-660 m depth is unusual as it is highly fractured or sheared and is reminiscent of pyrite from porphyry environments (Fig. B4.4l). Below 1245 m, pyrite is generally observed as minor small (5-10 μm) cubes within heavily silicified and epidotized chips (type 6). Pyrite also occurs as small, often fractured inclusions within chalcopyrite (Fig. B4.6d), and more rarely in sphalerite. When observed as small inclusions in chalcopyrite in particular, pyrite appears to have an earlier paragenesis than chalcopyrite and potentially also sphalerite.

Microprobe analyses of pyrite from 1098 and 1832 m depth have trace Pb (1098 and 1832 m), trace Zn (1832 m) and 1.5 wt. % Cu at 1832 m (Table B4.5) and these analyses are close to stoichiometric pyrite.

Other Cu-bearing sulfides

Bornite

The bornite in well RN-10 scales appears to be primarily associated with chalcopyrite with the most abundance in chip types 1, 4 and 7 within ‘mottled’ sphalerite. Minor bornite plus covellite alteration of chalcopyrite is also observed in massive magnetite chips. Bornite is

most abundant between at 0-660 m and between 1095 m and 1198 m and is dominant over chalcopyrite in some type 1 chips at 1099, 1168 and 1198 metres depth (Fig. B4.5d).

Bornite was only analyzed by EMPA at 1098 m and has a non-stoichiometric composition of more S compared to stoichiometric bornite (29.7 wt.% versus 25.6 wt.%), less Cu (54.9 wt.% versus 63.3 wt.%) and more Fe (14.6 wt.% versus 11.1 wt.%). Bornite from this depth also contains 0.5 wt. % Ag (Table B4.5).

Covellite

Covellite occurs as a dark-blue alteration product of chalcopyrite in association with bornite (Fig. B4.6e). Covellite occurs in chip type 1, 4 and 7 as fine-grained replacement (plus bornite) of chalcopyrite blebs within sphalerite and gives the sphalerite in these chip types the 'mottled' or 'blotchy' texture described above. Covellite was not analyzed by EMPA. It is likely that more covellite is present in RN-10 than estimated in Table B4.3 as XRD interpretation suggests there is approximately 1 or more wt.% in many bulk samples as this is the lower level of sensitivity for the diffractometer at GEOMAR. It is possible that covellite occurs as a coating on chips and this may have been removed during the preparation and polishing of the puck. Covellite could account for some of the tarnished sulfides described in the next section.

Digenite

Digenite mainly occurs as an alteration product of sphalerite (Fig. B4.6f), or more rarely as digenite blebs associated with sphalerite (Fig. B4.6g). Minor alteration of sphalerite/wurtzite to digenite is common towards the top of well RN-10 with some sphalerite chips at 1095 m and 1120 m depths pervasively digenitized. Digenite noticeably decreases in abundance below 1136 m (Table B4.3). Digenite was not analyzed by EMPA.

Sample descriptions

RN10-2014-660 (depth 0-600 m)

Sample description

This sample consists primarily of quartz chips (likely amorphous silica), chalcopyrite, wurtzite, sphalerite and silicified chips with some red oxide coating. Ninety percent of the sample is <0.1 mm in size with most of the remaining chips between 0.1 - 0.5 mm in size. A few chips are larger than 10 mm and mainly consist of less altered fine-grained wall rock chips to highly altered dark green chips (chlorite?). A very fine-grained remnant coating on some chips is observed when the sample has dried and is likely a clay component. Chalcopyrite and/or pyrite in various stages of oxidation coat many sulfide chips, often on one surface only, especially when associated with finely banded sphalerite chips. Fine-grained chalcopyrite (and/or pyrite?) also occurs as coarse monomineralic bladed aggregates up to 0.3 mm in size but fine grained-sphalerite is more abundant. Large hemimorphic and pyramidal reddish-brown wurtzite crystals are observed up to 5 mm in size (Fig. B4.3a). When a magnet is passed through the sample¹ a significant proportion is magnetic, including a dark, banded, wavy plate-like mineral that is tentatively identified as magnetite. Minor purple/blue tarnish was identified associated with sulfides. A small non-

¹ For measurement of the magnetic component abundance, a magnet was passed slowly through the sample twice and the weight recorded. If any pipe material was present, this was discarded.

sulfide monomineralic component of quartz, an unknown blue-green mineral and small <0.1 mm yellow, green and red (a coating?) minerals are also observed. Rare epidote is associated with alteration of the wall rock chips and may contain small inclusions of pyrite or chalcopyrite. Fragments of what appear to be oxidized pipe material were removed when seen.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample is relatively clean and indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, magnetite, and trace isocubanite, wurtzite and bornite (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, spinel (ulvospinel), montmorillonite, kaolinite, and trace amounts of epidote, wollastonite and potentially diopside (Supp. Info. B4.2). Additional minerals identified in this sample from petrographic observation are: pyrite, digenite, covellite, electrum and rutile. The primary chip type at this depth is type 1 (Fig. B4.4a-b and Table B4.4). Aligned, and often banded lathy sphalerite/wurtzite with ‘mottling’ from chalcopyrite, bornite and covellite is the most common texture at this depth (e.g., Fig. B4.5a). This texture is often porous giving the ‘smoke’ like texture previously described and at this depth is at the highest abundance observed in well RN-10. An interesting texture is shown in Figure B4.6h where chalcopyrite is rimming what appears to be a rounded space. This texture could result from the presence of a gas bubble and subsequent precipitation of chalcopyrite. The type 7 ‘hybrid’ chip texture is also common, with type 1 lathy sphalerite/chalcopyrite/bornite enclosing an earlier coarse and often bladed chalcopyrite clast (e.g., Fig. B4.4c). Massive magnetite chips are also common at this depth. Magnetite may be banded or non-banded and consistently contains exsolved rutile up to 20 μm in size. It is rare to observe substantial pyrite anywhere in RN-10, but at this depth pyrite was noted as both a large, massive chip (fractured and infilled with chalcopyrite) and also as large euhedral cubes in silicified chips. Electrum is common in type 1 chips, particularly at the boundary of touching chalcopyrite and sphalerite crystals and is generally between 0.5 and 1 μm in size (Fig. B4.5e).

RN10-2014-835 (depth 835 m)

Sample description

This sample contains more rounded chips than the previous sample and has a smaller overall size distribution of 95% below 1 mm and approximately 5% between 1 mm and 5 mm. There were no chips larger than 5 mm. Compared to sample RN10-2014-660 up hole, the sample from 835 m depth contains more quartz/amorphous silica and significantly more fine-grained banded sphalerite and coarse reddish-brown wurtzite (up to 5 mm). Less chalcopyrite/pyrite is coating chips and rare monomineralic bladed chalcopyrite/pyrite is observed, but is significantly smaller than in the previous sample up hole, (~1 mm). Some red Fe-oxide alteration is seen associated with sulfides, especially on fine-grained banded sphalerite chips, which is the most abundant sulfide phase. Rare purple tarnish was also observed on sulfide chips, possibly those containing fine-grained chalcopyrite or pyrite. There is less of a non-sulfide monomineralic component to this sample with chiefly quartz/amorphous silica, epidote and rare yellow minerals observed. This sample also yields less of a magnetic component than sample RN10-2014-660.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample is relatively clean and indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, magnetite, bornite, and wurtzite, with trace isocubanite, covellite,

pyrite and bornite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, muscovite, kaolinite, garnet (almandine) and trace amounts of illite and epidote. Paragonite and calcite are also potentially present in very minor amounts. Two unknown XRD peaks at approximately 2 and 1.767 angstroms (Å) fitted well with native silver (Supp. Info. B4.2). This sample did not polish well, but minor electrum was noted at touching boundaries of coarse sphalerite/wurtzite and chalcopyrite (type 4). Table B4.4 lists other chip types observed.

RN10-2014-870 (depth 870 m)

Sample description

Seventy percent of the chips in this sample are <1 mm in size with the remaining chips mainly between 1 mm and 5 mm. Minor larger wall rock chips up to 15 mm in size were also recorded. Sphalerite is the most common sulfide phase and occurs as massive fine-grained, thinly banded chips. Pyramidal hemimorphic reddish-brown wurtzite crystals are only a minor component of this sample. Chalcopyrite/pyrite is observed to coat one side only of the banded sphalerite chips, but also occurs as bladed, coarse-grained monomineralic chips up to 3 mm in size. Fine-grained chalcopyrite has some minor Fe-oxide alteration but only one grain was heavily altered in the sample box when received. As a result of this, fine-grained Fe-oxide coated chips in the proximity of this one chip through movement of remnant water in the sample box during transport. Rare purple and blue tarnish was observed associated with sulfide phases (chalcopyrite?). Monomineralic non-sulfide phases include amorphous silica, clear quartz crystals <1 mm in size, an unknown pale yellow mineral and trace epidote. The larger wall rock chips contain fine-grained chlorite, epidote, amorphous silica and very rare fine-grained chalcopyrite/pyrite. There is a strong magnetic component to this sample, in particular wavy plates of what is likely to be magnetite.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample shows the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, magnetite, wurtzite and trace bornite (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, ulvospinel, montmorillonite, kaolinite, hornblende and trace amounts of epidote, wollastonite and nontronite (Na-Fe clay). It is likely that chlorite is also present, possibly a mix of chamosite (Fe) and clinocllore (Mg). An unknown peak is present at 4.8527Å. As with the previous sample, two unknown XRD peaks at approximately 2 and 1.767Å fitted well with native silver (Supp. Info. B4.2). Additional minerals identified by reflected light petrography are digenite (after sphalerite) and a rare unknown silver mineral in small fractures in magnetite (Ag?). Exsolution of rutile is also common in magnetite. Electrum occurs in chalcopyrite and near to, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in the majority of chip types at this depth. Table B4.4 shows chip textures seen at this depth with coarse type 4 sphalerite and chalcopyrite chips predominating. This type includes multiple chips with varying development of the ‘hopper’ sphalerite crystal texture (Fig. B4.4k).

RN10-2014-904 (depth 904 m)

Sample description

This sample was small in size compared to most other samples in this study and is similar to the sample described for RN10-2014-870, except for a slightly higher percentage of altered wall rock ships. Approximately 70% of the sample is below 1 mm with the remainder

between 1 and 5 mm in size. Sphalerite is the most abundant sulfide phases and occurs as massive, anhedral chips often finely-banded and with chalcopyrite coating one side only. Chalcopyrite occurs as 'spots' within the wall rock chips, often associated with epidote and amorphous silica. Small, coarsely bladed monomineralic chalcopyrite chips around 0.5 mm in size are also observed. Iron-oxide chips are present and as they are delicate and fragment easily, it is unknown what the Fe-oxide is replacing. Clear, anhedral quartz and epidote crystals less than 1 mm in size occur as a non-sulfide monomineralic component of the sample in addition to an trace unknown blue-green mineral also observed in other samples (Table B4.2). There is a magnetic component to this sample and contains the wavy, fine-grained magnetite plates observed in previous samples.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of magnetite, chalcopyrite, sphalerite, wurtzite, bornite, covellite, and trace pyrite (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, kaolinite, hornblende, chamosite/clinochlore chlorite mix and saponite (Ca-Mg clay). Paragonite and/or muscovite or corrensite (Na-Ca-K chlorite) may also be present. Two types of montmorillonite spectra fit the peaks best, particularly at low angstrom values: an illite-montmorillonite mix and solely montmorillonite (Supp. Info. B4.2). Rare digenite is also observed in reflected light petrography and is altering sphalerite, particularly on crystal edges. Massive magnetite chips are observed and contain exsolved rutile. Electrum occurs in massive chalcopyrite crystals and near to, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in the majority of chip types at this depth with type 1 sphalerite and chalcopyrite chips predominating (Table B4.4).

RN10-2014-1085 (depth 1085 m)

Sample description

This sample contains mainly angular chips with 60% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 20% between 1 and 5 mm. The 20% of chips above 5 mm are angular, altered wall rock chips. Sphalerite is the most common sulfide and as in previous samples up hole, it mainly occurs as massive, anhedral chips often finely-banded with chalcopyrite coating one side. Coarse-grained reddish-brown wurtzite with a hemimorphic pyramidal habit is also abundant. Chalcopyrite has rare coarse 'spots' within fine-grained sphalerite, in addition to occurring as small, coarsely-bladed chips around 0.2 mm in size. The Fe-oxide appears to be primarily associated with the fine-grained sphalerite in this sample, but some chalcopyrite has minor alteration. The altered wall rock chips contain epidote and appear strongly silicified at this depth. Clear quartz less than 1mm in size is observed as part of the non-sulfide monomineralic component, in addition to epidote, an unknown yellow-orange mineral and a blue-green resinous mineral. There is a strongly magnetite portion to this sample including wavy, fine-grained magnetite plates up to 2 mm in size.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of sphalerite, chalcopyrite, and magnetite, with trace bornite, covellite and wurtzite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, ulvospinel, illite-montmorillonite, kaolinite, hornblende, epidote and trace amounts of chlorite (chamosite-clinochlore mix?) and nontronite. Corrensite (Na-Ca-K chlorite) may also be present (Table B4.7). The XRD spectrum also indicates that trace Ag and Au may be present, even though Au and Ag have only been definitively identified in electrum during petrography (Supp. Info. B4.2). Additional minerals identified are digenite

(after sphalerite), trace pyrite and a rare unknown silver mineral in small fractures in magnetite (Ag?). Electrum is common in massive chalcopyrite crystals and near to, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in the majority of chip types at this depth. Coarse chalcopyrite (type 2) and massive magnetite (type 3) are the most commonly occurring chip types.

RN10-2014-1095A (depth 1095 m)

Sample description

The majority of chips from this sample are angular with 60% of the chips below 1 mm in size. Approximately 35% of the sample is between 1-5 mm, and a minor component of altered wall rock chips are above 5mm in size. Sphalerite is the most common sulfide and occurs primarily as fine-grained massive chips, but also as finely-banded chips often with a variably altered (to Fe-oxide) chalcopyrite coating on one side only. Coarse, monomineralic bladed chalcopyrite is less common than in previous samples but 'spots' of chalcopyrite in fine-grained sphalerite are common. Alteration of chalcopyrite and potentially fine-grained sphalerite to Fe-oxide is common as are purple/blue tarnished sulfides. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain trace epidote and fairly abundant chlorite. Trace cloudy quartz crystals less than 1 mm in size are seen within the monomineralic component of the sample alongside trace wurtzite, and an orange (altered?) mineral. There is a weakly magnetic component in this sample, including pipe material, which was discarded. On washing this sample there is a very fine-grained clay-like component that took a long time to settle out during washing and gave a fine-grained coating to many grains upon drying.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample shows peaks for magnetite, chalcopyrite, sphalerite, and trace covellite and bornite. No wurtzite peaks were present. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, epidote, illite-montmorillonite, hornblende, kaolinite, montmorillonite, and nontronite (Table B4.7). A trace chamosite-clinocllore chlorite mixture plus trace hematite is also present. This sample also has trace water (ice in Supp. Info. B4.2) in the spectrum indicating that in spite of the long drying time, the sample still retained some moisture. The XRD spectrum also indicates that trace Ag may be present (Supp. Info. B4.2). Additional minerals identified by reflected light petrography are trace pyrite and digenite (after sphalerite). Electrum is common at, or close to the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in the majority of chip types in this sample. Electrum is also seen within large, coarse chalcopyrite chips (chip type 2) and as with the previous sample, is often coarser (1-4 μm) compared to electrum in chip types 1, 4 or 7 (~1 μm). Coarse, massive chalcopyrite and sphalerite (type 4) and massive magnetite (plus exsolved rutile) chips are the most commonly occurring textures.

RN10-2014-1097A (depth 1097 m)

Sample description

The majority of chips from this sample are angular with 70% of the chips below 1 mm and 15% between 1 to 5 mm in size. Altered wall rock chips from 5 to 8 mm constitute the remainder of the sample. Sphalerite is the major sulfide phase but chalcopyrite is common, particularly as 'spots' in massive fine-grained sphalerite and coating one side of fine-grained banded sphalerite chips. In this sample, Fe-oxides loosely aggregate different chip types together and also alter fine-grained chalcopyrite and possibly fine-grained sphalerite chips. The coarse, bladed chalcopyrite described elsewhere is not observed at this depth, but

this could be picking bias due to Fe-oxide coating. The wall rock chips in this sample are noticeably more altered than samples described up hole as they are more silicified, contain trace epidote and chlorite, but also contain minor fine-grained pyrite banding within silicification. The non-sulfide monomineralic component of this sample consists of trace cloudy quartz crystals around 1mm in size, trace epidote, an unknown orange mineral and the resinous blue-green mineral observed in other samples up hole (Table B4.2). After washing, there was a fine-grained clay-like component that took a long time to settle out and gave a thin coating over the chips when dried. There is a significant magnetic component to this sample and appears to contain thin plates of magnetite up to 2 mm in size.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of bornite, chalcopyrite, sphalerite, magnetite and trace bornite, wurtzite and pyrite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, epidote, nontronite, montmorillonite, chamosite-clinochlore chlorite mix, an illite-montmorillonite mix, and trace hematite and water (Table B4.7). Silver peaks were also identified in the XRD spectrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). An unknown peak is present at 11.359Å. Digenite is also identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite. Electrum is commonly associated with large, bladed coarse chalcopyrite chips, but also as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Coarse chalcopyrite chips (type 2) are the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1098A (depth 1098 m)

Sample description

The majority of chips from this sample are angular with 80% of the chips below 1 mm and ~15% between 1 and 5 mm in size. A minor component of altered wall rock chips are greater than 5 mm in size. There is also a fine-grained sand-like fraction composed of sphalerite, chalcopyrite/pyrite(?) and quartz. As with all previous samples up hole, sphalerite is the dominant sulfide phase and occurs as massive, angular and blocky chips with variable alteration to Fe-oxide. Sphalerite is also observed as massive, finely-banded chips, sometimes coated with chalcopyrite on one surface, but these chip types are not as altered by Fe-oxides. Monomineralic, bladed chalcopyrite is observed, but compared to other samples up hole, these chips are rare and chalcopyrite is principally in direct association with sphalerite-rich chips. The wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain chlorite and trace epidote. The non-sulfide monomineralic portion of the sample consists of trace clear quartz crystals, trace epidote, an unknown orange mineral (could be Fe-stained?), and a blue-green resinous mineral. This sample has a fairly strong magnetite component and likely contains a significant proportion of magnetite as thin, wavy plates.

XRD and mineralogy

This sample appears distinctly more altered than samples up hole and has an abundance of alteration minerals. The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, pyrite, bornite, magnetite and trace wurtzite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, kaolinite, hornblende, epidote, illite-montmorillonite, nontronite, hematite, goethite and montmorillonite. Trace chlorite (chamosite-clinochlore) and water is also present. Digenite is identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite. This depth has the highest abundance of electrum in RN-10 and also the largest observed grain size (up to 8µm). Electrum is commonly associated with

large, bladed coarse chalcopyrite chips, but also as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Electrum from this sample is noticeably more 'gold' in colour than observed elsewhere in this well, and could indicate higher Au:Ag ratios of electrum. However, the XRD spectrum in Supp. Info. B4.2 for this depth does not have strong peaks for either Au or Ag. Coarse chalcopyrite chips (type 2) and banded type 1 chips are the most commonly occurring chip textures at this depth.

RN10-2014-1099 (depth 1099 m)

Sample description

Eighty percent of the chips in this sample are <1 mm in size with ~15% of the remaining chips between 1 mm and 5 mm in size. Minor larger chips up to 10 mm are present and consist of altered wall rock and massive sphalerite chips. Sphalerite is the most abundant sulfide and occurs as sub-angular to angular massive chips, and also as finely-banded massive sphalerite with a coating of chalcopyrite and varying amounts of Fe-oxide alteration. Hemimorphic pyramidal reddish-brown wurtzite is observed, but only as a trace component. Chalcopyrite also occurs as monomineralic coarsely-bladed chips 0.5 to 2 mm in size, as 'spots' in massive sphalerite, and also within fine-grained banded sphalerite chips. There is abundant Fe-oxide alteration in this sample and is cementing different chip-types together into multiple aggregates. The Fe-oxide alteration on individual chips appears to be chiefly associated with massive sphalerite chips as the chalcopyrite appears to be tarnished rather than heavily altered. The wall rock chips are heavily silicified with primary textures rarely visible, and epidote and dark-green chlorite are common. Some wall rock chips have a porphyroblastic texture with the porphyroblasts altered to a fine-grained white mineral. The majority of the non-sulfide monomineralic portion of this sample is cemented by Fe-oxide into aggregates, but there are rare clear quartz crystals, epidote, a trace unknown orange mineral and a resinous blue-green mineral as per other samples up hole. This sample does not have a large magnetic component and likely consists of small magnetite plates.

XRD and mineralogy

There are numerous alteration minerals at this depth. The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of sphalerite, chalcopyrite, bornite, magnetite and wurtzite with trace pyrite and covellite (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, illite-montmorillonite, hornblende, nontronite, montmorillonite, water and trace hematite, chamosite-clinochlore mix and kaolinite (nacrite?). A weak feldspar spectrum trace may be present at this depth, possibly an orthoclase-albite mix. Digenite is also identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite. The XRD spectrum also indicates that trace Au may be present (not Ag), even though Au has only been definitively identified in electrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). Electrum is commonly associated with large, bladed coarse chalcopyrite chips, but also typically as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Bornite is dominant over chalcopyrite in numerous chips in this sample. One noticeably different chip type at this depth is the banded, colloform chalcopyrite and sphalerite chip of Figure B4.5c. This is the only occurrence of this chip type, and unusually for RN-10 samples has a very low porosity. Coarse chalcopyrite chips (type 2) and radiating, banded type 1 chips are the most commonly occurring chip textures at this depth.

RN10-2014-1120 (depth 1120 m)

Sample description

This sample contains angular to sub-rounded chips with 80% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 20% between 1 and 5 mm. The dominant sulfide in this sample is sphalerite and it occurs as finely-banded chips with one surface coated with chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite occurs as massive, coarsely-bladed chips and as 'spots' in massive sphalerite. Rare blue and purple tarnished sulfides are associated with chalcopyrite. Iron-oxides are altering many sulfides, but is not cementing chips together. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain epidote, dark-green chlorite, and minor fine-grained pyrite. This sample has a strongly magnetic component and a significant proportion of this was pipe material, which was subsequently removed.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of sphalerite, magnetite, chalcopyrite, and bornite with trace covellite and pyrite. No obvious wurtzite peaks are present. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, saponite, epidote, chamosite, an illite-montmorillonite mix, and trace hematite and water. No clear Au or Ag peaks were identified in the XRD spectrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). Digenite is also identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite. Electrum is commonly associated with type 1 chips as small (~1 µm) blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Coarse chalcopyrite and chalcopyrite chips (type 4) are the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1136 (depth 1136 m)

Sample description

Eighty percent of the chips in this sample are <1 mm in size with ~10% of chips 1 to 5 mm in size. Approximately 10% of chips are above 5 mm in size and consist of altered wall rock chips up to 15 mm in size. Sphalerite is the dominant sulfide phase and occurs as sub-rounded massive chips containing 'spots' of chalcopyrite and as finely-banded massive sphalerite often coated on one side with chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite also is observed as trace bladed, coarse monomineralic chips. Tarnished sulfides are also common, including red, dark blue, purple and light blue colours, and appear to occur solely on chips containing chalcopyrite. Iron-oxide alteration is ubiquitous in this sample, and cements multiple chip-types together into fairly coherent aggregates. One chip aggregate was also observed to be cemented together by amorphous silica. The wall rock chips are heavily silicified and contain abundant epidote, chlorite and trace fine-grained rare chalcopyrite/pyrite. As with sample RN10-2014-1099, the protoliths of some altered wall rock chips appear to have been porphyroblastic in nature, but these porphyroblasts are now altered to a fine-grained white mass. Most of the non-sulfide monomineralic portion of this sample is cemented by Fe-oxide into aggregates, but there are trace cloudy and clear quartz crystals (<1 mm), epidote, and a resinous blue-green mineral. There is a very abundant magnetic component in this sample and likely consists chiefly of magnetite.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates chalcopyrite, wurtzite, sphalerite, bornite, covellite, magnetite and pyrite are present (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, an illite-montmorillonite mix, nontronite, kaolinite, epidote, water, and hematite and possibly trace stilbite (Ca-Na zeolite). Weak Ag peaks may be present in the XRD spectrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). An unknown peak is present at 1.7508Å but could be

tentatively identified as chloritoid. Rare digenite is also identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite. Electrum is commonly associated with large, bladed coarse chalcopyrite chips, but also as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. This depth marks the first occurrence of 'clean' sphalerite or wurtzite crystals that do not contain bornite (type 5). Coarse chalcopyrite chips are the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1148 (depth 1148 m)

Sample description

The majority of chips from this sample are angular with 85% of the chips below 1 mm and ~15% between 1 and 5 mm in size. A very minor component of altered wall rock chips are up to 10 mm in size. Extensive cementing of all chip-types by Fe-oxides give this sample a brecciated appearance and coats most chips whether they occur in aggregates or as individual chips. Sphalerite is the most abundance sulfide at this depth and mainly occurs as massive angular chips with 'spots' of chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite is observed to be coating one side of massive sphalerite chips, but due to the Fe-oxide coating it is unclear whether the sphalerite is finely-banded. Monomineralic, coarsely bladed chalcopyrite chips are present, and while they are coated with Fe-oxide, they appear tarnished rather than heavily altered. Blue and purple tarnished sulfides are observed, primarily in association with sphalerite. The wall rock chips are silicified, Fe-oxide stained/altered and contain epidote. This is a highly magnetic sample and also contains significant amounts of pipe material, which was removed and discarded.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, pyrite, and magnetite with trace bornite. No obvious wurtzite or covellite peaks were present. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, illite-montmorillonite, clinochlore and trace hematite and nontronite. No clear Au or Ag peaks were identified in the XRD spectrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). Digenite is also identified by reflected light petrography altering sphalerite but is noticeably less abundant than samples from up hole. Electrum is commonly associated with type 1 chips as small (~1 μm) blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals but is also less abundant than up hole. Magnetite has both banded and non-banded textures and there appears to be an equal abundance of chip types 1, 2, and 4 (this could however be sampling bias).

RN10-2014-1168 (depth 1168 m)

Sample description

This is a coarse sample with 60% of the chips smaller than 1 mm and 40% of the sample larger than 1 mm. The largest chips are up to ~10 mm in size. Iron-oxides are extensively cementing and coating all chip types which makes thorough identification problematic. Sphalerite is the most common sulfide phase and occurs as massive angular chips up to 10 mm in size. Chalcopyrite occurs as 'spots' within fine-grained sphalerite, coating one side of massive sphalerite chips, trace coarsely bladed chips, and has variable alteration to Fe-oxides. Blue tarnished sulfides are also associated with sphalerite. Altered wall rock chips are less abundant than up hole, but are silicified with rare epidote and contain minor fine-grained chalcopyrite/pyrite in association with the silicification. Due to the fine-grained Fe-oxide coating and aggregation of this sample, a non-sulfide monomineralic portion description was difficult to pick out, but cloudy quartz crystals were observed. This sample

also has a significant magnetic component, including pipe material, which was then removed.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample shows sphalerite, chalcopyrite, wurtzite and magnetite occur in this sample. No bornite peaks were observed despite reflected light petrography indicating a fair abundance (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica and montmorillonite. Trace covellite and pyrite were also identified by reflected light petrography. As with the majority of previous samples, electrum is chiefly associated with chalcopyrite, but mainly as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Bornite is dominant in many type 1 chips at this depth, in particular where the aligned laths of sphalerite are well developed and thick (e.g., Fig. B4.5i). Type 1 and type 7 ('hybrid') chips are the most commonly occurring textures at this depth.

RN10-2014-1198 (depth 1198 m)

Sample description

The majority of chips from this sample are angular with 80% of the chips below 1 mm, and 20% between 1 and 5 mm in size. Iron-oxides are extensively cementing and coating all chip types which makes thorough identification difficult. An unconsolidated silver coating is also associated with the Fe-oxide cemented aggregates. This could be associated with drilling, but is of unknown provenance. Sphalerite is the major sulfide phase and occurs as angular massive chips. It is often coated with fine-grained chalcopyrite on one side only. Blue tarnished sulfides are also associated with this chip type. Chalcopyrite also occurs as small coarsely bladed monomineralic chips as previously described up hole, but in this sample they are fragmented and highly altered by Fe-oxides. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and coated with Fe-oxides. Occurrence of epidote was not noted in this sample. There is a very abundant magnetic component in this sample and the magnet pass through the sample picked up whole Fe-oxide cemented chip aggregates. Pipe material was also noted in the magnetic fraction and was removed from the sample when seen.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, bornite, and magnetite, with trace wurtzite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, illite-montmorillonite, ulvospinel, garnet (almandine), zoisite and a chamosite-clinocllore mix. No distinct Au or Ag peaks are observed in the XRD spectrum (Supp. Info. B4.2). Unidentified peaks occur at 1.824 and 1.537Å. Rare covellite is also identified by reflected light petrography in association with bornite. One chip of massive pyrite is present in the microscope puck; this could indicate difficulties in sub-sampling a heterogeneous sample as no pyrite is noted in the XRD spectra. Electrum principally occurs at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. Nascent 'hopper' crystal formation of sphalerite is also seen in this sample. Type 1 banded chips are most common at this depth.

RN10-2014-1245 (depth 1245 m)

Sample description

This sample contains angular to sub-rounded chips with 75% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 20% between 1 and 5 mm. The remainder are larger (up to 10mm) silicified wall

rock chips. The dominant sulfide in this sample is sphalerite and it occurs as finely-banded chips with one surface coated with chalcopyrite. Resinous, golden-brown wurtzite is also present at this depth and occurs with fine-grained chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite also occurs as massive, coarsely-bladed chips and as 'spots' in massive sphalerite. Rare blue and purple tarnished sulfides are associated with both chalcopyrite and sphalerite. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain epidote and minor fine-grained pyrite/chalcopyrite. This sample is weakly magnetic.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, pyrite and magnetite with trace bornite and wurtzite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, an illite-montmorillonite mix, ulvospinel, chamosite-clinocllore and trace kaolinite, nontronite and hematite (Table B4.7). Trace covellite and digenite are also identified by reflected light petrography. As with the majority of previous samples, electrum is chiefly associated with chalcopyrite, but mainly as smaller blebs within chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals. As with the previous sample, bornite is dominant over chalcopyrite in many type 1 chips at this depth, in particular where the aligned laths of sphalerite are well developed with less porosity (e.g., Fig. B4.5i). Chip types 2, 4 and 5 chips are the most commonly occurring textures at this depth.

RN10-2014-1504 (depth 1504 m)

Sample description

This sample contains sub-angular chips with 40% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 60% between 1 and 5 mm. The dominant sulfide in this sample is sphalerite and it occurs as finely-banded chips with one surface coated with chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite occurs as massive, coarsely-bladed chips and as 'spots' in massive sphalerite. Rare blue and purple tarnished sulfides are with sphalerite. There is minimal Fe-oxide alteration in this sample compared to the samples above. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain epidote and minor fine-grained pyrite or chalcopyrite. This sample has a strongly magnetic component and a significant proportion of this was pipe material, which was subsequently removed.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, wurtzite, sphalerite, covellite and magnetite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, an illite-montmorillonite mix, saponite, enstatite and trace kaolinite and chamosite-clinocllore. Pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography. Electrum is distinctly reduced in abundance from this depth downwards compared to above this depth. It is mainly associated with chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals and is noticeably reduced in size compared to up hole (1 to <0.5 μm). Coarse sphalerite/wurtzite and chalcopyrite chips (type 5) are the most commonly occurring chip texture.

RN10-2014-1575 (depth 1575 m)

Sample description

This sample contains mainly sub-rounded chips with 70% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 30% between 1 and 5 mm. A fine-grained sand component made up of quartz, epidote and possible sulfides is present in this sample. The dominant sulfide in this sample is

resinous, golden-brown wurtzite and is associated with fine-grained sulfides. Fine-grained sphalerite is not as abundant as up hole and when observed it occurs as finely-banded chips with one surface coated with chalcopyrite and more rarely as fine-grained massive chips with 'spots' of chalcopyrite. Rare blue and purple tarnished sulfides are associated with chalcopyrite. Iron-oxides are altering some sulfides, but it is not pervasive. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain epidote and minor fine-grained pyrite. This sample only has a trace magnetic component and a significant proportion of this was pipe material, which was subsequently removed.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, wurtzite, covellite and trace pyrite, magnetite and bornite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, nontronite, enstatite and potentially biotite. Pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography. Magnetite is distinctly reduced in abundance compared to previous samples. Electrum is mainly associated with chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals and has a size of 1 to <0.5 μm . Coarse sphalerite/wurtzite and chalcopyrite chips (type 5) are the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1668 (depth 1668 m)

Sample description

This sample is small in size compared to most other samples in this study and therefore the subsample sizes are reduced (Table B4.1). Fifty percent of the chips in this sample are <1 mm in size with the remaining sub-angular chips primarily below 2 mm in size. Resinous, golden-brown wurtzite is the most common sulfide phase and occurs with massive, fine-grained sphalerite containing 'spots' of chalcopyrite. Angular, finely-banded sphalerite chips coated on one surface with chalcopyrite also occur and are slightly altered to Fe-oxides. Blue tarnished minerals are also associated with this fine-grained coating of chalcopyrite. The wall rock chips are variably altered: some chips are highly silicified and contain epidote and fine-grained pyrite/chalcopyrite, but other small chips are dark and fine-grained and are likely less-altered wall rock chips. Trace clear quartz crystals and epidote were collected for the non-sulfide monomineralic fraction. This sample only has a weakly magnetic component.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of sphalerite, chalcopyrite, covellite, bornite and wurtzite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, enstatite, saponite and trace chamosite-clinochlore (Table B4.7). Pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography and magnetite only occurs as disseminations in silicification. Electrum is mainly associated with chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips. Coarse sphalerite/wurtzite and chalcopyrite chips (type 5) are the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1680 (depth 1680 m)

Sample description

In this sample 70% of the chips are below 1 mm in size, with the remaining 30% between 1 and 5 mm. Sphalerite is the dominant sulfide and occurs as massive, angular chips with 'spots' of chalcopyrite and as finely-banded chips with a coating of chalcopyrite on one

surface. Chalcopyrite also occurs as coarsely bladed monomineralic chips. Trace resinous, golden-brown wurtzite is also observed. Iron-oxide is only present in trace amounts and appears to be associated chiefly with alteration of chalcopyrite ‘spots’ in sphalerite chips. Rare purple tarnished sulfides are associated with chalcopyrite coating sphalerite chips. The wall rock chips are heavily silicified and have a slight blue-gray tinge. Epidote is also associated with the most silicified chips. There is very little non-sulfide monomineralic or magnetic component in this sample.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates sphalerite, wurtzite, chalcopyrite, magnetite and trace bornite and covellite are present. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica and nontronite with trace wollastonite, chamosite, hornblende and possible biotite (Supp. Info. B4.2). Pyrite is also seen in reflected light petrography. Electrum is not observed in this sample even though Ag peaks may be present in the XRD spectrum; this could indicate a sampling bias. Only three chip types are present at this depth: type 1 sphalerite/chalcopyrite laths, type 5 bladed sphalerite/wurtzite, and silicified wall rock with rare sulfide disseminations (type 6).

RN10-2014-1737 (depth 1737 m)

Sample description

Fifty percent of the chips in this sample are <1 mm in size with the remaining chips primarily between 1 to 5 mm. Minor altered wall rock chips are up to 10 mm in size. This sample contains a fine-grained sand fraction made up of quartz, epidote and sulfides. Chalcopyrite is the dominant sulfide in this sample and mainly occurs as coarsely bladed monomineralic clusters, as ‘spots’ or as a coating on fine-grained sphalerite. Golden-brown bladed wurtzite is associated with chalcopyrite. This sample has minor Fe-oxidation alteration and rare purple tarnish, both chiefly associated with chalcopyrite. When observed, sphalerite occurs as finely-banded massive grains, often coated on one surface by chalcopyrite. The wall rock chips are highly silicified with little remaining of primary textures. Large phenocrysts of epidote up to 4 mm were observed on one silicified chip. There is very little non-sulfide monomineralic or magnetic component to this sample, but pipe material was observed and removed.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of sphalerite, chalcopyrite, and wurtzite with trace bornite and covellite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, montmorillonite, clinozoisite, hornblende and kaolinite with trace hematite (Table B4.7). Pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography and magnetite only occurs as rare disseminations in silicification. Electrum is rare, but is mainly associated with chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips and is <1 µm in size. Sphalerite ‘hopper’ crystals (type 8) are seen at this depth, but coarsely bladed chalcopyrite chips (type 2) are the most common chip type.

RN10-2014-1792A (depth 1792 m)

Sample description

This sample contains mainly angular chips with 50% of the sample below 1 mm in size and 50% between 1 and 5 mm. Golden-brown bladed wurtzite is the most common sulfide phase and occurs in association with chalcopyrite. Chalcopyrite chips have the coarsely bladed monomineralic habit previously described up hole and is also associated with fine-

grained sphalerite as ‘spots’ and coating one side of finely-banded sphalerite chips. Iron-oxide coating is uncommon, but some angular sphalerite chips have a coating on one side, so is likely alteration of chalcopyrite. There are more altered wall rock chips in this sample compared to sulfide chips and are highly silicified. Some altered wall rock chips contain very small (<0.01 mm) specks of chalcopyrite or pyrite. Epidote is fairly common within the altered wall rock chips with some crystals up to 1 mm in size. There is no significant non-sulfide monomineralic or magnetic component to this sample.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates chalcopyrite, sphalerite, bornite and trace covellite are present. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, saponite, epidote and wollastonite (Supp. Info. B4.2). Trace pyrite is also seen in reflected light petrography. Electrum is very rare, but when seen it occurs at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips and is <1 µm in size. Coarse bladed chalcopyrite chips (type 2) is the most commonly occurring chip texture at this depth.

RN10-2014-1800 (depth 1800 m)

Sample description

Eighty percent of the chips in this sample are below 1 mm in size with approximately 20% between 1 and 5 mm in size. Rare altered wall rock chips up to 10 mm in size are present. Sphalerite is the most abundant sulfide phase and occurs as fine-grained massive chips either with chalcopyrite ‘spots’, or with one surface coated by chalcopyrite. Golden-brown bladed wurtzite is also common in the sample and is associated with both sphalerite and chalcopyrite. Purple tarnished sulfides are associated with trace Fe-oxide coating and alteration, most likely of chalcopyrite. Wall rock chips are highly silicified and contain epidote and trace cubed pyrite crystals. Both cloudy, and clear quartz crystals are present as a fine-grained (<0.5 mm) non-sulfide monomineralic component in addition to epidote. There is no significant magnetic component in this sample.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of chalcopyrite, wurtzite, sphalerite, covellite, bornite, and trace isocubanite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, epidote, saponite, clinocllore and clinozoisite. Digenite and pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography. Trace electrum is also seen, but is mainly associated with chalcopyrite, or at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips and is <1 µm in size. Two unknown XRD peaks at 1.767 and 2.039Å match silver, but other peaks do not align (Supp. Info. B4.2). Only three chip types are present at this depth: type 1 sphalerite/chalcopyrite laths, type 5 bladed sphalerite/wurtzite, and silicified wall rock with rare sulfide disseminations (type 6).

RN10-2014-1828 (depth 1828 m)

Sample description

This sample contains a significant amount of silicified altered wall rock chips with 25% of the sample between 1 to 5 mm in size and 75% below 1 mm. Sphalerite and chalcopyrite and wurtzite appear to have roughly equal abundances. Sphalerite and chalcopyrite are associated in fine-grained sphalerite chips that contain either ‘spots’ of chalcopyrite or a coating on one surface. Bladed wurtzite is chiefly associated with chips containing slightly coarser chalcopyrite. Blue tarnished sulfides are associated with trace Fe-oxides, usually in

the vicinity of fine-grained chalcopyrite. Wall rock chips are highly silicified and also appear recrystallized in some chips by large (up to 7 mm) subhedral quartz and epidote crystals. Small pyrite cubes were also observed in the silicification. Epidote, cloudy and clear quartz crystals, and the unknown blue-green mineral observed towards the top of RN-10 are the main components of the non-sulfide monomineralic component of this sample. A weakly magnetic fraction was collected.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates wurtzite, chalcopyrite and sphalerite are present (Table B4.7). Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, epidote, saponite, clinocllore-chamosite, and trace muscovite (Supp. Info. B4.2). Trace pyrite, covellite and magnetite (disseminated in silicification) are also seen in reflected light petrography. Electrum is very rare, but when seen it occurs at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips and is $<0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in size. Bladed sphalerite and chalcopyrite chips (type 5) are the most commonly occurring chip texture.

RN10-2014-1832 (depth 1832 m)

Sample description

This sample contains a significant abundance of silicified altered wall rock chips compared to sulfide chips. Eighty percent of the chips are below 1 mm in size with 20% between 1 and 5 mm. Chalcopyrite, sphalerite and golden-brown bladed wurtzite all have roughly equal abundances. Wurtzite is associated chiefly with coarser chalcopyrite (including 'spots' in sphalerite chips), and with fine-grained and banded sphalerite coated by chalcopyrite on one surface only. Rare blue tarnished sulfides occur in conjunction with rare Fe-oxides, usually associated with alteration of chalcopyrite. The altered wall rock chips are highly silicified and have a slightly gray colour with no obvious primary features. Small euhedral pyrite cubes are observed in the silicification and have a close spatial association with coarse (~ 3 mm) epidote. Anhedral chunks of cloudy quartz are the chief component of the non-sulfide monomineralic fraction of this sample, along with rare epidote. A weakly magnetic component was collected, including fragments of pipe, which were then discarded.

XRD and mineralogy

The XRD spectrum for this sample indicates the presence of wurtzite, sphalerite, chalcopyrite and trace isocubanite. Other minerals identified by XRD are amorphous silica, epidote, saponite and montmorillonite. Weak peaks are observed for silver by XRD (Supp. Info. B4.2). Trace pyrite is also identified by reflected light petrography. Rare electrum is also seen, but only at the boundary of touching sphalerite and chalcopyrite crystals in type 1 chips and is $<0.5 \mu\text{m}$ in size. The most common texture at this depth is coarse, bladed chalcopyrite chips (type 2).

Summary

The majority of the fine-grained textures, such as the sphalerite and chalcopyrite textures in chip type 1, are likely to have formed almost instantaneously when conditions in the well changed as a response to temperature and pressure adjustments at surface. Multiple generations of sphalerite and chalcopyrite growth is induced by pressure and temperature changes within the well and multiple textures also indicate growth into open space. The chalcopyrite and sphalerite (and likely magnetite) banding is often of equal widths, thus indicating a ‘flash’ precipitation in response to changes in crystallization conditions.

There are distinct intervals in well RN-10 demarcated by mineralogical assemblages which roughly corresponds to the presence or absence of inflow aquifers or intrusions (Franzson et al. 2002):

- 0 – 660 m: A high abundance of chalcopyrite plus significant electrum and magnetite occurs in sample RN10-2014-660, but the actual defined depth of collection for this sample is more ambiguous compared to others.
- 1095 – 1245 m: In this interval there is a high abundance of chalcopyrite and magnetite plus increased alteration of sphalerite by digenite and bornite is dominant over chalcopyrite. The abundance of electrum is also higher than elsewhere in RN-10 in this interval, and when associated with coarse chalcopyrite (chip type 2) is distinctly coarser and more ‘Au’ in colour. Strong alteration of sulfides and magnetite by Fe-oxides is also common in this interval and wall rock chips are highly silicified with very few remnant textures remaining.
- Below 1504 m, there is a distinct change in mineralogy as bladed, coarse wurtzite becomes more common compared to sphalerite, Fe-oxide alteration reduces, and magnetite and electrum notably decrease in abundance and size.
- 1737 – 1800 m: An increase in chalcopyrite abundance is observed in this interval with a concomitant decrease in bornite and silicification.

It should also be noted that there is the distinct possibility that the provenance of chips may not be certain as scales could fall down the well shaft or be carried upwards. This could explain some of the ‘hybrid’ chips that are composed of coarse chalcopyrite with a later rim of type 1 lathy sphalerite and chalcopyrite (e.g., Fig. B4.4j).

Further work planned

- Sulphur isotope analyses to constrain potential sources of sulfide-forming fluids
- QEMSCAN to determine proportions of elements in RN-10 and produce a well profile. Also to estimate the amount of electrum in each sample and if there are further mineral phases hosting Au and Ag as Figure B4.7 shows a high abundance of bright phases (likely electrum) that was not observed in petrographic study. Coatings may also be removed during the polishing process; the abundance of covellite in XRD analyses versus the low abundance observed under the microscope is an example of this.
- Whole rock geochemistry on subsamples
- Further EMPA work on mineral compositions
- Comprehensive LA-ICP-MS work on sulfides and magnetite to analyze trace and critical metals
- Comparison with scales from surface pipes

References

- Franzson, H. et al., 2002. Reykjanes high-temperature field, SW-Iceland. Geology and hydrothermal alteration of well RN-10. Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh Workshop on Geothermal Reservoir Engineering. Stanford University, Stanford, California, pp. 1–9.
- Hardardóttir, V. et al., 2010. Cu-Rich Scales in the Reykjanes Geothermal System, Iceland. *Economic Geology*, 105, pp.1143–1155.

Figure B4.1. Temperature profile for well RN-10.

Figure B4.2. Pressure profile for well RN-10.

Figure B4.3. RN-10 sample preparation and sample images. a) Hemimorphic pyramidal wurtzite crystals (collected at various depths). Field of view (FOV) = 30 mm. b) Chalcopyrite chips (1085 m depth). FOV = 30 mm. c) Bulk sample with platy sphalerite, chalcopyrite, Fe-oxide alteration and silicified volcanic chips from 1085 m depth. FOV = 50 mm. d) Chalcopyrite in sphalerite chips, including ‘spotted’ chalcopyrite texture from 1120 m depth. FOV = 30 mm. e) Illustration of method used to dry samples in petri dishes after washing. note the vial for individual separates to the right. f) RN-10 samples laid out. Rows from left to right represent increasing depths.

Figure B4.4. Whole chip texture summary. a) Type 1 aligned laths of sphalerite (gray) with interstitial chalcopyrite (yellow), inclusions of chalcopyrite in laths, and discrete perpendicular chalcopyrite banding. 660 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. b) Type 1 banded chips indicating changes in temperature and/or pressure from changes in crystal size and porosity of sphalerite (gray) laths and chalcopyrite (yellow). 600 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. c) Type 2 coarse, bladed chalcopyrite (yellow) with minor gray sphalerite inclusions. 1097 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. d) Type 3 banded magnetite (light gray) with minor chalcopyrite inclusions in blocky Leisegang banding pits. 660 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. e) Type 2 banded magnetite with Leisegang banding texture. 660 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. f) Type 4 coarse gray sphalerite and coarse yellow chalcopyrite, with inclusions of chalcopyrite along growth planes in sphalerite. The sphalerite is 'mottled' with bornite and/or covellite, plus chalcopyrite similar to Type 1 (Fig. B4.5). 1120 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. g) Type 5 'sawtooth' texture of 'clean' sphalerite/wurtzite (gray) with coarse chalcopyrite (yellow). 1575 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. h) Type 5 coarse, 'clean' wurtzite associated with chalcopyrite blebs (yellow). 1800 m depth, FOV = 1.5 mm. i) Type 6 silicified wallrock with disseminated chalcopyrite (yellow) and sphalerite (gray). 1099 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. j) Type 7 'hybrid' chip with earlier coarse, bladed chalcopyrite (yellow) and later sphalerite (gray) laths and a final rim of chalcopyrite. Depth 1800 m, FOV = 3 mm. k) Type 8 sphalerite (gray) hopper crystal with minor inclusions of chalcopyrite (yellow). Depth 660 m, FOV = 3 mm. l) Type 9 massive pyrite chip (light yellow) with fractures or shears filled with later chalcopyrite (darker yellow). Depth 660 m, FOV = 3 mm.

Figure B4.5

Figure B4.5. Chalcopyrite, sphalerite, and electrum textures. a) ‘Blotchy’ chalcopyrite (yellow) in ‘mottled’ Type 1 aligned sphalerite (gray) laths from 660 m depth. Chalcopyrite is associated with bornite (pink) and minor covellite (blue). The white circle indicates a grain of electrum associated with sphalerite and bornite. FOV = 0.15 (150 microns). b) Type 1 highly-porous sphalerite (gray) laths with interstitial blebby chalcopyrite inclusions (yellow). 660 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. c) Type 10 colloform chalcopyrite (yellow) and sphalerite (gray) from 1099 m depth. FOV = 3 mm. d) Bornite (orange) associated with chalcopyrite in association with Type 3 magnetite. 1136 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. e) Type 1 ‘mottled’ sphalerite (gray) with bornite (pink) associated with chalcopyrite (yellow). The white circle indicates electrum (light yellow) at a touching boundary of chalcopyrite and sphalerite. 660 m depth, FOV = 0.3 mm. f) Electrum grains (bright) at a boundary of coarse, clean chalcopyrite (yellow) and sphalerite (gray) in a Type 7 hybrid chip. These grains are the largest observed in RN-10 and are up to 8 microns in size (1098 m), FOV = 0.3 mm. g) Electrum grain (bright) ~3 microns in size in Type 4 chalcopyrite (yellow) at 1120 m depth, FOV = 0.15 mm. h) Electrum grains (bright) at boundary of coarse chalcopyrite (yellow) and sphalerite (gray) in a Type 7 ‘hybrid’ chip. The largest electrum grain is ~6 microns in size. 1098 m depth, FOV = 0.3 mm. i) Well-developed thicker laths of Type 1 sphalerite chips (gray) with associated chalcopyrite (yellow). 1832 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. j) Aligned and porous Type 1 sphalerite (gray) with associated chalcopyrite (yellow) and high porosity (dark). 870 m depth, FOV = 0.3 mm. k) Nascent Type 8 sphalerite (gray) hopper crystals at 1136 m depth. FOV = 0.7 mm.

Figure B4.6

Figure B4.6. Other textures and minerals observed in RN-10. a) Type 3 massive magnetite chip. 660 m depth, FOV = 3 mm. b) Rutile (pink) in Type 3 massive magnetite. 1097 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. c) Leisegang texture of Type 3 massive, banded magnetite. 660 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. Sphalerite (gray), chalcopyrite (yellow) and fractured pyrite (light-yellow) in a fine-grained silica band in Type 6 silicified wallrock . 1575 m depth, FOV = 15 mm. e) Chalcopyrite (yellow) associated with bornite (pink) and covellite (blue) at the boundary of sphalerite (gray) in a Type 4 chip. 1168 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. f) Digenite (light-blue) alteration of sphalerite (gray) in a Type 4 chip. 1136 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. g) Digenite (light-blue) associated with sphalerite/wurtzite (gray with red reflections) in a Type 5 chip. 1136 m depth, FOV = 0.7 mm. h) Type 1 chip composed of highly-porous sphalerite (gray) with chalcopyrite (yellow) rimming a circular cavity, potentially a gas vesicle. 660 m depth, FOV = 0.3 mm.

Figure B4.7. SEM backscatter image of Type 1 sphalerite and chalcopyrite laths from 660 m depth. The light specks are electrum grains within the sphalerite and chalcopyrite.

Figure B4.8. SEM EDS spectra of magnetite. Note the small peak to the left of the spectrum indicating that Si is contained within the magnetite. Sample from 660 m depth.

Sample Information			Chip texture types									
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
No.	Sample ID	Depth (m)	Fine-grained 'mottled' sphalerite or wurzite with chalcopyrite (laths and dendrites)	Coarse chalcopyrite	Massive magnetite	Coarse-grained 'mottled' sphalerite or wurzite (+/- chalcopyrite) with 'mottling'	Coarse-grained sphalerite or wurzite (+/- chalcopyrite) with no 'mottling'	Silicified wallrock	Fine-grained magnetite in wallrock silicification	Hybrid coarse- and fine-grained chips	Sphalerite or wurzite 'hopper' crystal texture	Massive pyrite
1	RN10-2014-660	0-660	x	x	x			x		x		x
2	RN10-2014-835	835	x	x		x		x	x			
3	RN10-2014-870	870	x	x	x	x		x		x		
4	RN10-2014-904	904	x		x	x		x				
5	RN10-2014-1085	1085	x	x	x	x		x				
6	RN10-2014-1095A	1095	x	x	x	x		x		x		
7	RN10-2014-1097A	1097		x	x	x		x				
8	RN10-2014-1098A	1098	x	x	x	x		x		x		x
9	RN10-2014-1099	1099	x	x	x	x		x	x			
10	RN10-2014-1120	1120	x	x	x	x		x			x	
11	RN10-2014-1136	1136	x	x	x	x		x		x		
12	RN10-2014-1148	1148	x	x	x	x		x				
13	RN10-2014-1168	1168	x	x	x	x		x		x		
14	RN10-2014-1198	1198	x	x		x		x		x		x
15	RN10-2014-1245	1245	x	x	x	x		x		x		x
16	RN10-2014-1504	1504	x	x	x			x				
17	RN10-2014-1575	1575	x					x	x			
18	RN10-2014-1668	1668	x	x				x	x			
19	RN10-2014-1680	1680		x				x				
20	RN10-2014-1737	1737	x	x				x			x	
21	RN10-2014-1792A	1792	x	x				x				
22	RN10-2014-1800	1800	x	x				x				
23	RN10-2014-1828	1828	x	x				x	x			
24	RN10-2014-1832	1832	x	x				x		x		

Table B4.4. Individual chip types for scale samples from well RN-10. Red highlighting indicates that electrum occurs in a specific texture.

Depth (m)	Mineral	Number of analyses	Fe	S	Cu	Zn	Pb	Au	Ag	Total
660	sphalerite	10	3.7	32.5	2.0	59.4	0.11	0.08	0.16	98.1
	chalcopyrite	8	27.2	33.7	30.9	7.13	0.07	0.10	0.05	99.1
	bornite									
	pyrite									
	electrum									
1098	sphalerite	3	3.5	33.5	0.4	62.7	0.05	0	0.00	100.2
	chalcopyrite	3	30.6	35.1	34	0.00	0.08	0.09	0.02	100.3
	bornite	3	14.6	29.7	55	0.00	0.08	0.05	0.52	99.8
	pyrite	3	47.8	54	0.00	0.00	0.12	0	0.00	102.0
	electrum	4	2.14	0.7	3.0	1.40	0.0	76.2	20.3	103.6
1668	sphalerite	3	7.4	34.0	0.9	57.1	0.09	0.10	0.01	99.6
	chalcopyrite	3	30.8	35.2	34	0.00	0.14	0.12	0.01	100.5
	bornite									
	pyrite									
	electrum									
1832	sphalerite	3	4.9	33.8	0.31	61.0	0.09	0	0.00	100.2
	chalcopyrite	6	30.9	35.3	33.7	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.01	100.2
	bornite									
	pyrite	1	45.1	52.1	1.53	0.52	0.21	0.08	0.03	99.6
	electrum									

Table B4.5. Microprobe data for sulphides (wt.%). Grey shading indicates no analyses at that depth.

Depth (m)	Mg	Mn	Cr	Al	Ti	Ni	Fe	Si	O
660	0	0.32	0.16	0.02	0.02	0.04	72.4	0.33	21.3
	0	0.83	0.24	0.04	0.02	0.08	71.1	0.57	21.4
	0	0.72	0.13	0.06	0.01	0.11	71.3	0.58	21.4
	0	0.94	0.14	0.03	0.01	0.10	70.9	0.76	21.6
	0	0.75	0.11	0.03	0.01	0.10	71.3	0.67	21.5
1098	0	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.01	0.01	73.7	0.00	21.2
	0	0.04	0.03	0	0.01	0.01	73.5	0.02	21.1
	0	0.03	0.04	0	0.01	0.01	73.9	0.02	21.2

Table B4.6. Microprobe data for magnetite from 0-660 m and 1098 m. Data is in wt.%.

Program name	Calibrated element(s)	Standard	Compound measured
Sulfide II (sulfide phases)	Cu, Fe, S	Chalcopyrite	CuFeS ₂
	Zn	Sphalerite	ZnS
	Pb	Galena	PbS
	Au, Ag	Au-Ag alloy	Au ₆₀ Ag ₄₀
Spinel (magnetite)	Ti	Ilmenite	TiO ₂
	Fe	Ilmenite	FeO
	Al	Chromite	Al ₂ O ₃
	Cr	Chromite	Cr ₂ O ₃
	Si	Anorthite	SiO ₂
	Ni	NiO	NiO
	Mg	Chromite	MgO
	Mn	Ilmenite	MnO
Rutile (Ti-oxides)	Ti	Rutile	TiO ₂
	Fe	Ilmenite	FeO

Supp. Info. B4.1. Standards used during electron microprobe analysis of down-hole scale samples from well RN-10 in this study. Calibrated elements and compounds for each standard are indicated.

Supp. Info. B4.2. All XRD spectra for scale samples studied in this report from down-hole in well RN-10. As the manual interpretation program only allowed for 7 phases to be displayed on each spectra, the final interpretation for each sample (by depth; see Table B4.1) is split into individual spectra: 1) sulfides and magnetite, 2) Au and Ag, 3) other minerals. All spectra peaks have been corrected to silicon.

870, Obj.-tr.88

904, Obj.-tr.86

904, Obj.-tr.86

904, Obj.-tr.86

1099, Obj.-tr.80

1099, Obj.-tr.80

1099, Obj.-tr.80

1120, Obj.-tr.79

1120, Obj.-tr.79

1120, Obj.-tr.79

1136, Obj.-tr.78

1136, Obj.-tr.78

1136, Obj.-tr.78

1148, Obj.-tr.77

1148, Obj.-tr.77

1148, Obj.-tr.77

1198, Obj.-tr.75

1198, Obj.-tr.75

1245, Obj.-tr.74

1245, Obj.-tr.74

1245, Obj.-tr.74

1575, Obj.-tr.72

1575, Obj.-tr.72

1668, Obj.-tr.71

1668, Obj.-tr.71

1668, Obj.-tr.71

1680, Obj.-tr.70

1737, Obj.-tr.56

1792A, Obj.-tr.60

1800, Obj.-tr.59

1828, Obj.-tr.58

1832, Obj.-tr.57

Appendix B5: Calculations for Chapter 3

B5.1) Calculation of volume and metal content of scales deposited in downhole pipes of well RN-10 between cleaning in 2009 and 2014.

- Scales from 660 m depth (sample RN10-2014-660 in Appendix B1) represent scales in the production casing between the wellhead and 660 m depth. Accuracy of sample collection is +/- 50m (pers. comm. O. Sigurdsson, HS Orka, 2018). Downhole pipe accumulation only is calculated in this study as accumulations in surface pipes have already been calculated by Hardardóttir (2011).

B5.1. i) Assumptions:

1. A uniform scale thickness of 0.5 cm between 0 and 1832 m depths
 - This scale thickness was used as except for rare chip fragments up to 1 cm in size from 1099 m and 1168 m depths, scale samples at all sampling depths contain chip fragments up to, but not exceeding 0.5 cm in size (Appendix B4).
2. That the downhole pipe is constant in diameter. The pipe diameter of the slotted liner in RN-10 below 660 m is 9 5/8" (Sigurdsson, 2012) and the width of the liner is similar to the well liner in Hardardóttir (2011).

B5.1. ii) Calculation of sulfide volume in downhole RN-10 pipes:

Volume of whole pipe including slotted liner

height (h) = 1832 m

radius (r) = 0.1225 m

volume = 86.669 m³

Volume of inner 'empty' pipe (not scales)

height (h) = 1832 m

radius (r') = 0.1115 m

volume (inner') = 71.5525m³

Volume assuming a scale thickness of 0.5 cm

height (h) = 1832 m

radius (r'') = 0.1065 m (0.115-0.5)

volume (inner'') = 65.2791 m³

Volume of scales in downhole RN-10

volume (inner') – volume (inner'') = 6.27338 m³

B5.1. iii) Mass accumulation of primary minerals in RN-10

Mineral	Mineral densities (kg/m ³)	Mineral proportion in scales (%)
Sphalerite	4020	60
Chalcopyrite	4190	20
Bornite	5090	10
Galena	7600	0.2
Electrum (60:40 Au:Ag)	14000	0.05

Mass accumulation of scales:

Volume of mineral = 6.27338/100 * mineral proportion in scales

Sphalerite as example:

Volume of mineral (sphalerite) * density

6.27338 m³ * 4020 = 15131 kg/5 years

15131/5 = 303 kg/yr (0.303 t/yr)

Chalcopyrite = 105 kg/yr (0.105 t/yr)

Bornite = 64 kg/yr (0.064 t/yr)

Galena = 19 kg/yr (0.0191 t/yr)

Electrum = 8.78 kg/yr (0.00878 t/yr)

Total scale accumulation over 5 years = 23721 kg (24 t)

Sulfide scale accumulation per year in downhole RN-10 including sphalerite, chalcopyrite, galena, bornite, electrum = 23.721 t/5 = 4.744 t/yr

Total sulfide accumulation downhole RN-10 over 20,000 years (lifetime of system):

Example of sphalerite:

$0.303 * 20000 = 6060$ t over 20,000 years

Total volume of sulfide scales in downhole RN-10 over 20,000 years = 9998 t

Sphalerite = 6060 t

Chalcopyrite = 2100 t

Bornite = 1280 t

Galena = 382 t

Electrum = 176 t

B5.2) Calculation of metal fluxes for well RN-10 (t/yr)

This calculation calculates the estimated metal fluxes for well RN-10 and estimates total metal accumulations over 20,000 year (estimated lifetime of system).

Assumptions:

- The average composition of scales is representative of RN-10
- Average bulk geochemical data for all surface high-pressure (HP) wells (n = 59) is representative of the high-pressure RN-10 well (5 x surface RN-10 samples only)
- Fluxes are similar in high-pressure wells
- Surface mass accumulation rate of ~ 1 t/yr per high-pressure well as estimated by Hardardóttir (2011) is representative of the high-pressure well RN-10
- Hardardóttir (2011) estimated a sulfide mass accumulation of ~ 1 t/yr for surface pipes (surface pipes represent scales from the surface wellhead to the Grey Lagoon)
- This study estimates a downhole sulfide mass accumulation of ~ 4.7 t/yr for high-pressure well RN-10.

RN-10 metal fluxes:

Estimated flux of RN-10 = 4.7 (downhole) + 1.0 (surface) = 5.7 t/yr

Example of Zn:

(RN-10 downhole):

= $(4.7/100) * [\text{Average composition of bulk geochemistry (in. wt.\%)}]$

= $(4.7/100) * 29.22$

= 1.38 t/yr

(HP surface scales):

= $(1.0/100) * [\text{Average composition of bulk geochemistry (in. wt.\%)}]$

= $(1.0/100) * 35.9$

= 0.36 t/yr

Combined (total) RN-10 Zn flux: $1.38 + 0.36 = 1.74$ t/yr

All calculated metal fluxes for RN-10:

	t/yr		kg/yr		kg/yr		kg/yr
Zn	1.74	Ag	4.07	Li	0.05	Dy	0.004
S	1.09	Se	2.33	Be	0.05	Yb	0.003
Fe	0.68	Co	1.57	Sn	0.04	Th	0.003
Si	0.32	Cr	0.92	Sb	0.03	Gd	0.003
Cu	0.29	As	0.38	Sc	0.03	Er	0.002
Ca	0.08	Au	0.45	Bi	0.02	Sm	0.002
Mg	0.08	V	0.48	Nb	0.02	Cs	0.002
Al	0.08	Ni	0.36	Rb	0.02	Pr	0.002
Na	0.03	B	0.24	Y	0.02	Ho	0.001
Pb	0.02	Te	0.24	Ta	0.02	Eu	0.001
Cd	0.02	Mo	0.20	Ge	0.01	Tl	0.001
Zr	0.01	Sr	0.19	Ga	0.01	U	0.001
		Br	0.13	Hg	0.01	Tb	0.001
k/yr		P	0.09	La	0.01	Tm	0.001
Mn	7.46	Ba	0.08	Ce	0.01	Lu	0.001
K	4.72	W	0.07	Nd	0.006		
Ti	5.13	Hf	0.07	In	0.004		

Table B5a. Calculated metal fluxes (t/yr or kg/yr) for RN-10 in the Reykjanes geothermal field. Metals not included in this table were either not analyzed or have no data above detection.

B5.3) Calculation of the relative contribution to the total metal accumulation in surface versus downhole pipes in well RN-10.

Assumptions:

- Average scale composition is representative of downhole RN-10 scales
- Bulk geochemical data for all surface high-pressure wells (n = 59) is representative of the high-pressure RN-10 well (5 x surface RN-10 samples only)
- Flux has remained constant during 20,000 year lifetime of active system
- 20,000 year lifetime assumed (Hardardóttir, 2011 estimated 18,000-20,000 years; K. Saemundsson, Iceland Geosurvey, pers. comm, 2008)

NB: Surface pipes and downhole pipes are calculated separately in order to highlight P/T controls on contributions to locations of metal accumulation

Example of Zn in *surface pipe*:

Average 35.9 wt.%

1.0 t/yr total deposition

20000 year estimated active system

= ((1.0/100)*35.9)*20000

= 7172 t Zn

Example of Zn in *downhole pipe*:
Average 29.2 wt.%
4.7 t/yr total deposition
20000 year estimated active system
= $((4.7/100)*29.2)*20000$
= 27696 t Zn

TOTAL Zn deposited over 20,000 years in entire RN-10 profile = 34868 t Zn

Full RN-10 total accumulation calculation results for all elements in **Table 3.9**.

Appendix B6: Reykjanes sample location schematics

Year of collection

	2002
	2003
	2004
	2005
	2006
	2007
	2009
	2011
	2013
	2014

Sample detail

	Known location
	Approximate location
	Geochemistry
	Fluid sample

WELL: RN-10

COMMENTS:
 - x 45 samples
 - Downhole samples include duplicate boxes

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-11

- COMMENTS:
- x 24 samples
 - (including 2 on FFCV1 classed as one sample)
 - 4 x geochemistry available, but no sample for OP1 sample with geochem, only PTS

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-12

- COMMENTS:
- x 23 samples
 - 1 x unknown from surface pipe found below FFCV on opening
 - 1 x sample from sample holder, VH terms it 'garbage'

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-13

COMMENTS:
 - 5 x samples
 - 1 x basalt sample from unknown location

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-13B

COMMENTS:
- 3 x samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-14B

COMMENTS:
- 5 x samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-15

COMMENTS:
 - 11 x samples
 - Not many scales from 2007, likely 2007 upstr and dnstr samples close to OP1

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-17B

COMMENTS:

- 1 x samples
- Scale from fluid sampling on downhole container
- Thin section only, could be to 2770m depth.

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-18

COMMENTS:
- 2 x samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-19

COMMENTS:

- 5 x samples
- 1 x fluid from 1600m
- 4 x samples from downhole sampling only
 - 2 x 2007 from 0-1500m (including one host rock sample)
 - 2 x 2014 from 0-1600m (scales)

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-21

COMMENTS:

- 8 scale samples
- 3 x fluid samples downwell
- Possibly don't have small vial of 0-1350m scales which collected on sample holder (2007)

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-22

COMMENTS:
 - 38 samples
 - check diagrams on bags for dnstr OP locations
 - downhole scales x 8 between 1141-1444m depth

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-23

COMMENTS:
- 13 samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-24

COMMENTS:
- 5 samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-26

COMMENTS:
- 5 samples
- 1 x unknown (surface scale)

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-27

COMMENTS:
- 1 sample

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

WELL: RN-28

COMMENTS:
- 2 samples

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-29

COMMENTS:
- 6 samples
- TSS only

OP1 AND FFCV1

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

OP2 AND FFCV2

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNHOLE

WELL: RN-31

OP1 AND FFCV1

OP2 AND FFCV2

DOWNHOLE

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

UPSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

DOWNSTREAM OP VIEW

Appendix C

Supplementary information for Chapter 4

Appendix C1: Compilation of all LA-ICP-MS individual data points in this chapter.

This appendix is available online in the Zenodo scientific metadata repository (www.zenodo.org) for immediate and permanent access. Zenodo is hosted by CERN and is funded for at least the next 20 years by the European Commission via the FP7 and Horizon 2020 funded OpenAIRE project (codes 246686, 283595, 643410, 731011, 777541), CERN, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, and donations via the CERN & Society Foundation. The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC funded research. CERN, an OpenAIRE partner and pioneer in open source, open access and open data, provided this capability and Zenodo was launched in May 2013. Data files are citable by DOI.

Appendix C1 citation: 10.5281/zenodo.2550731

Appendix C1 link: [Zenodo record](#)

Appendix C2: Summary of bulk geochemical data available for individual SMS deposits discussed in this chapter.

Appendix C3: Summary of LA-ICP-MS statistics for pyrite from individual SMS deposits compiled in this chapter.

Appendix C4: Summary of LA-ICP-MS statistics for pyrite from individual VMS deposits compiled in this chapter.

Appendix C5: Summary statistics for minerals other than pyrite for data compiled in this chapter.

Appendix C6: Details of LA-ICP-MS laboratories for literature compiled in this chapter.

Appendix C2. Compilation of bulk geochemical data available for SMS deposits in this study

Group	Deposit	N	Cu wt. %	Zn wt. %	Pb wt. %	Fe wt. %	S wt. %	Ba wt. %	SiO ₂ wt. %	Ag ppm	As ppm	Au ppm	Bi ppm	Cd ppm	Co ppm
1	TAG	310	4.26	5.30	0.02	28.3	38.3	0.001	12.5	82	48	1.73	14	161	233
1	MIR	137	5.00	8.70	0.05	27.9	31.4	-	28.3	115	145	4.20	2.2	154	79
1	Turtle Pits (5°S)	7	2.98	3.18	0.02	35.8	1.92	0.22	0.001	4.8	65.5	85.4	-	-	12
1	Semenov-4	16	0.93	0.09	0.01	27.9	14.1	0.82	0.50	36	-	38	-	-	-
1	Lucky Strike	154	5.37	4.16	0.05	21.1	31.0	10.9	12.4	74	334	0.30	-	195	89
1	Snakepit	107	7.00	4.65	0.06	35.2	35.0	0.05	5.99	67	305	1.58	3.8	180	220
1	Menez Gwen	27	1.72	3.46	0.05	3.98	15.5	18.9	21.1	41	113	0.13	1	154	18
1	Broken Spur	76	4.88	3.71	0.05	32.6	-	0.05	-	33	210	1.64	9.9	120	180
1	MESO	15	5.86	0.40	0.05	30.2	-	2.94	11.1	30	334	0.88	-	470	336
1	EPR 9°50'N	29	7.89	6.33	0.07	33.4	-	-	-	-	154	-	-	246	-
1	Axial Seamount (CASM)	31	0.32	14.8	0.41	3.99	18.8	18.5	17.6	250	435	4.12	0.3	340	5
1	Axial Seamount (ASHES)	99	3.09	19.7	0.19	15.4	31.1	2.19	10.0	275	720	1.57	2.2	820	27
1	Logatchev-1	65	22.0	2.55	4.52	24.8	20.5	0.23	3.4	66	265	14.0	0.1	26	425
1	Semenov-1	1	0.05	0.07	-	27.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	Semenov-3	5	0.17	0.08	0.01	35.7	14.2	0.70	1.80	28	-	7.0	-	-	-
1	Rainbow	116	12.4	15.0	0.03	28.6	32.8	0.29	0.71	188	214	5.10	5	391	5086
1	Middle Valley	217	0.86	2.2	0.02	31.5	34.4	0.81	11.9	5	60	0.16	2.2	41	59
1	Vienna Woods	170	1.32	20.1	0.49	12.60	25.6	0.57	22.4	325	508	6.18	-	594	29
1	Hine Hina	39	4.35	12.6	0.48	32.88	-	2.06	1.77	321	3551	3.20	2.1	314	17
1	Kairei	23	17.3	4.83	0.03	16.4	24.0	0.004	19.5	52	85	4.02	1.3	95	308
2	Pacmanus	413	9.67	20.5	1.19	11.6	26.0	8.49	7.68	243	6191	13.8	14.2	692	10
2	Suzette	533	9.35	3.27	0.69	17.3	18.4	15.3	4.8	112	4560	11.1	11	238	151
2	Brothers Volcano	61	6.00	4.63	0.17	16.6	27.6	15.0	3.71	105.2	2221	8.63	229.2	377.5	68.2
2	Suiyo Seamount	38	6.11	16.9	0.63	9.22	23.9	6.06	11.6	410	2090	42.3	13.1	859	19
3	Hakurei	34	1.92	6.92	-	10.6	-	19.3	-	7688	3015	4.70	-	271	-

Appendix C2 cont. Compilation of bulk geochemical data available for SMS deposits in this study

Group	Deposit	Ga ppm	Ge ppm	Hg ppm	In ppm	Mn ppm	Mo ppm	Ni ppm	Sb ppm	Se ppm	Sn ppm	Te ppm	Tl ppm
1	TAG	45	6	4.3	2	180	81	13.7	19.6	31	4.8	0.02	5.8
1	MIR	45	31	4.6	-	2893	83	21	45	2	15	-	6
1	Turtle Pits (5°S)	-	0.1	-	17.5	0.08	16	0.5	2.3	0.7	-	-	0.9
1	Semenov-4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.7	-	-	-	-
1	Lucky Strike	-	17	-	1.0	275	79	10	28	110	1	-	-
1	Snakepit	10	34	2.7	-	-	41	33	20.3	145	22.6	4.2	21.5
1	Menez Gwen	16	11.3	20	0.2	88	121	10	58	97	1.1	-	7.3
1	Broken Spur	-	3	6	1.0	259	51	9	13	280	4	13.3	16.1
1	MESO	-	-	-	-	-	200	42.5	47.6	195	-	-	-
1	EPR 9°50'N	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	327	-	-	-
1	Axial Seamount (CASM)	22	18	21	0.1	-	24	8	230	3	15.6	0.2	72.7
1	Axial Seamount (ASHES)	51	-	15	6.7	-	71	13.4	210	230	8.9	1.0	17
1	Logatchev-1	-	7	14.4	0.7	390	20	120	22.3	668	298	-	-
1	Semenov-1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	Semenov-3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22.7	-	-	-	-
1	Rainbow	5	12	0.1	10.0	453	29	490	34	186	138	2.1	0.1
1	Middle Valley	-	4.3	25	-	378	36	15.2	8.8	50	17.9	-	3.8
1	Vienna Woods	14	16	3.0	14	1096	32	22	-	-	2	-	-
1	Hine Hina	4	-	1.2	0.4	47	21	21	24	29	11.3	-	22
1	Kairei	18	37	1.2	0.1	-	23	8	7	111	31	-	0.8
2	Pacmanus	94	46	14	61	219	54	7	792	14	10.4	6.4	64.3
2	Suzette	80	1	62	4.6	159	144	3	730	209	-	5.3	74.2
2	Brothers Volcano	115.9	19.3	33.5	14.4	5527	130.6	3.89	184.2	356.7	20.6	-	1.90
2	Suiyo Seamount	305	10	328	10.3	233	116	4	895	1	15	1.1	146
3	Hakurei	1380	-	22	-	733	-	-	11417	-	-	-	-

Compilation of bulk geochemical data available for SMS deposits in this study (see **Table 4.2**). References are detailed in the text (section 4.2). Deposits are classified by group following the description detailed in section 4.5. Bulk geochemical samples are mainly surface or shallow subsurface samples except for TAG, Middle Valley, and Pacmanus which are from deep surface ODP drilling legs. Data for Pacmanus includes the Solwara -4, -6, -7, and -8 deposits. Vienna Woods is also known as Solwara-1, and Suzette is also known as Solwara-2. '-' does not indicate that the deposit does not contain this element, but data are unavailable.

Appendix C3. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Stats	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg	
1	TAG hydrothermal field	TAG hydrothermal mound	MOR	Basalt-hosted	to 125 mbsf	Max	1893	21.3	7.18	152.2	301.3	1923	102.1	580.2	214.4	1190	6.29	-	
						Min	0.48	0.19	0.05	0.01	0.21	0.12	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.05	1.09	0.01
	N	183			79	82	171	220	223	155	229	163	239	158	-	-	-	-	-
	Mean	51.0			1.29	0.56	5.22	30.4	13.1	3.42	36.9	2.73	46.0	0.45	-	-	-	-	-
	Med	3.95			0.59	0.23	0.67	7.94	0.76	0.75	6.54	0.41	19.4	0.14	-	-	-	-	-
	Max	3755			5.58	-	-	119	249	11.6	243	7.61	284	1.04	-	-	-	-	-
	Min	1.39			0.13	-	-	0.07	0.15	0.03	0.08	0.04	0.22	0.02	-	-	-	-	-
	N	42			34	-	-	60	44	32	57	54	61	25	-	-	-	-	-
	Mean	219.1			0.65	-	-	15.9	14.5	1.87	42.0	1.55	60.9	0.22	-	-	-	-	-
	Med	22.2			0.24	-	-	3.17	1.15	0.34	19.1	0.93	37.6	0.06	-	-	-	-	-
	Max	365.3			0.71	-	-	70.9	16.5	2.02	254.1	3.16	211.0	0.44	-	-	-	-	-
	Min	2.74			0.02	-	-	1.27	1.13	0.01	0.13	0.28	5.96	0.07	-	-	-	-	-
	N	3			4	-	-	3	4	3	4	3	4	4	-	-	-	-	-
Mean	243.2	0.21	-	-	5.11	31.4	6.92	0.66	79.0	1.52	101.4	-	-	-	-	-			
Med	361.6	0.06	-	-	3.21	26.7	3.15	0.30	30.9	1.13	94.2	-	-	-	-	-			
Max	10515	21	-	-	115	70.9	26.5	877	68.4	1089	0.87	-	-	-	-	-			
Min	25.3	0.34	-	-	1.3	0.19	0.27	47.5	0.25	8.31	0.01	-	-	-	-	-			
N	26	27	-	-	27	27	24	27	67	66	6	-	-	-	-	-			
Mean	1605	4.60	-	-	31.7	27.7	6.47	221.0	5.68	264.9	0.29	-	-	-	-	-			
Med	935	2.76	-	-	30.7	24.1	4.12	176	2.8	186	0.07	-	-	-	-	-			
Max	8294	50.1	-	-	44.9	892	18.8	899	8.58	4517	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Min	3.82	0.18	-	-	0.32	0.35	0.06	0.38	0.45	96	-	-	-	-	-	-			
N	32	31	-	-	37	34	30	37	38	38	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Mean	1461	4.74	-	-	16.9	222.9	3.54	161.5	3.01	1045	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Med	1005	1.45	-	-	18	149	1.47	95.8	2.42	610	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Max	15858	95.1	-	-	102	192	30	2558	312	3982	6.2	-	-	-	-	-			
Min	1.78	0.08	-	-	0.04	0.16	0.03	0.02	0.03	2.66	0.01	-	-	-	-	-			
N	39	57	-	-	73	29	52	74	48	75	2	-	-	-	-	-			
Mean	2097	5.28	-	-	8.63	26.8	2.65	305.1	9.34	899.6	3.11	-	-	-	-	-			
Med	104	0.28	-	-	1.53	16.3	0.65	13.4	1.58	535	3.11	-	-	-	-	-			
Max	8892	20.4	-	-	112.9	42.4	18.2	101.6	51.2	920.8	45.0	-	-	-	-	-			
Min	16.4	0.04	-	-	0.07	2	0.03	0.82	0.10	11.1	0.001	-	-	-	-	-			
N	29	29	-	-	30	29	30	30	30	30	30	-	-	-	-	-			
Mean	1750	3.60	-	-	13.2	11.0	5.40	39.3	6.01	330.31	6.96	-	-	-	-	-			
Med	1237	2.25	-	-	4.58	6.29	2.60	36.0	2.55	270.65	2.05	-	-	-	-	-			

Appendix C3 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Stats	Cu	Sn	In	Co	Ni	Se	Te	Au	Ge	W	V	U
1	TAG hydrothermal field	TAG hydrothermal mound	MOR	Basalt-hosted	to 125 mbsf	Max	1900	4.79	3.05	6775	212.8	179.9	9.84	4.50	20.3	1.00	8.08	9.05
						Min	0.81	0.03	0.01	0.09	1.09	1.98	0.35	0.01	0.94	0.02	0.03	0.00
						N	252	72	70	241	101	145	76	85	80	63	163	164
						Mean	132.0	0.37	0.16	447.7	22.0	30.1	1.93	0.42	4.43	0.10	1.01	0.31
						Med	52.2	0.21	0.06	174.0	7.27	21.1	1.56	0.26	2.88	0.05	0.36	0.07
						Max	-	-	-	1809	24.2	291	0.31	1.11	-	0.2	10.5	-
						Min	-	-	-	0.04	0.16	0.77	0.11	0.03	-	0.03	0.03	-
						N	-	-	-	60	48	61	3	43	-	11	54	-
						Mean	-	-	-	268.9	2.28	43.4	0.21	0.23	-	0.07	1.76	-
						Med	-	-	-	65	0.66	33.7	0.20	0.14	-	0.05	1.40	-
	Max	390.8	0.37	-	404.7	1.54	289.1	-	0.5	-	-	2.31	0.53					
	Min	31.1	0.1	-	0.1	0.21	0.97	-	0.01	-	-	0.01	0.02					
	N	4	4	-	4	4	4	-	4	-	-	4	3					
	Mean	215.9	0.20	-	106.8	0.59	87.9	-	0.16	-	-	0.85	0.20					
	Med	220.9	0.17	-	11.1	0.3	30.7	-	0.07	-	-	0.54	0.06					
	Max	-	-	-	9439	4.37	267	9.38	1.83	-	0.22	1.61	-					
	Min	-	-	-	37.6	0.24	1	0.1	0.02	-	0.02	0.49	-					
	N	-	-	-	27	27	39	21	62	-	4	27	-					
	Mean	-	-	-	1170	1.39	34.7	2.95	0.3	-	0.09	0.97	-					
	Med	-	-	-	527	1.27	11	1.84	0.23	-	0.05	0.9	-					
Max	-	-	-	97.4	1.78	204	0.26	3.16	-	0.4	10.2	-						
Min	-	-	-	0.02	0.2	0.2	0.08	0.03	-	0.01	0.45	-						
N	-	-	-	26	19	38	6	36	-	18	38	-						
Mean	-	-	-	13.3	0.73	40.5	0.12	0.34	-	0.10	3.90	-						
Med	-	-	-	0.95	0.63	14.1	0.1	0.14	-	0.07	4.05	-						
Max	-	-	-	2799	7.77	2280	15	3.95	-	1.32	12.1	-						
Min	-	-	-	0.02	0.14	0.92	0.07	0.02	-	0.02	0.02	-						
N	-	-	-	74	25	75	40	48	-	11	73	-						
Mean	-	-	-	397.4	1.39	687.3	4.35	0.89	-	0.44	0.58	-						
Med	-	-	-	145	1.06	477	2.64	0.47	-	0.12	0.17	-						
Max	5263	7.46	2.5	3831	36.2	332.5	-	16.3	-	-	28.2	0.183						
Min	14.3	0.01	0.01	23.9	1.28	1.94	-	0.03	-	-	0.02	0.001						
N	30	30	27	30	24	30	-	30	-	-	30	28						
Mean	1212	2.32	0.43	961.9	11.5	56.4	-	1.27	-	-	2.77	0.03						
Med	631.3	1.78	0.18	775.2	8.22	26.3	-	0.8	-	-	0.66	0.02						

Appendix C3 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Stats	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg
1	Wocan hydrothermal field	Wocan-1	MOR	Basalt-hosted	Surface	Max	23880	90.8	5.52	196.0	181.4	4451	1100	2809	7.17	511.9	1.02	-
						Min	1839	3.36	0.18	12.7	44.9	227.0	15.9	173.9	0.69	66.6	0.01	-
						N	7	7	6	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	5
		Mean				9139	21.4	1.37	102.5	84.3	1451	363.7	1055	3.28	185.6	0.22	-	
		Med				5994	8.92	0.61	87.9	77.7	1391	155	700.4	2.23	112.9	0.02	-	
		Max				2025	4.51	0.48	13.5	112.9	18.4	134.6	224.4	23.6	1323	58.4	-	
	Min	2.48	0.73	0.07	0.05	0.17	0.50	0.27	2.73	0.20	8.90	0.02	-					
	N	12	9	5	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	-				
	Mean	342.3	1.71	0.26	4.41	24.0	6.43	14.6	87.2	4.27	246.5	10.1	-					
	Med	167.8	1.27	0.17	3.24	10.6	3.65	3.11	55.6	2.28	83.1	1.69	-					
	Max	1158	3.39	-	33.8	1283	338.4	17.6	95.2	14.9	1044	-	2.57					
	Min	5.24	0.02	-	1.81	0.02	1.63	0.01	0.02	0.71	0.1	-	0.58					
	N	5	5	-	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	-	5					
	Mean	465.2	0.78	-	14.3	286.5	71.2	8.41	40.5	8.19	270.8	-	1.64					
	Med	380.3	0.06	-	5.07	65.5	4.75	10.9	40.1	8.59	93.2	-	2.06					
Max	2867	3.99	-	40.9	695.9	490.0	333.4	771.7	32.4	1140	13.2	16.1						
Min	0.004	0.01	-	0.001	0.003	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.004	2.96	0.0003	13.1						
N	24	23	-	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24	21	3					
Mean	790.2	1.08	-	8.61	55.9	121.7	39.5	156.2	3.79	245.5	1.32	14.3						
Med	126.1	0.39	-	7.80	7.95	62.3	5.75	42.0	1.79	145.4	0.23	13.6						
Max	2072	5.93	-	20.1	2904	59	879	190	1544	0.1	-	-						
Min	3.22	0.1	-	0.07	0.5	0.02	0.84	0.02	0.12	0.01	-	-						
N	34	19	-	26	34	18	33	44	45	3	-	-						
Mean	124.9	0.83	-	4.28	565.5	7.16	122.0	12.2	191.9	0.05	-	-						
Med	30.7	0.31	-	0.34	34.0	1.39	11.4	1.21	15	0.05	-	-						
Max	1511	0.68	-	367	3264	228	355	8.94	534	8.64	-	-						
Min	2.58	0.12	-	0.01	2.25	0.06	0.1	0.07	0.26	0.03	-	-						
N	37	29	-	37	39	21	39	39	39	12	-	-						
Mean	90.5	0.26	-	66.5	165.7	29.0	35.0	1.89	178.5	1.34	-	-						
Med	17.5	0.21	-	12	10.1	0.84	6.89	0.79	154	0.29	-	-						
Max	850	1.23	-	70.8	946	156	2632	45.8	279	4.91	-	-						
Min	0.99	0.09	-	0.02	0.1	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.52	0.01	-	-						
N	40	46	-	109	83	106	109	98	108	98	-	-						
Mean	37.4	0.22	-	6.24	16.3	7.30	47.2	1.41	27.0	0.51	-	-						
Med	7.33	0.18	-	3.5	0.74	1.50	6.18	0.38	13.7	0.30	-	-						
			BAB oceanic spreading	Basalt-hosted														
1	Hine Hina	Hine Hina	BAB oceanic spreading	Basalt-hosted														

Appendix C3 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Stats	Cu	Sn	In	Co	Ni	Se	Te	Au	Ge	W	V	U
1	Wocan hydrothermal field	Wocan-1	MOR	Basalt-hosted	Surface	Max	26071	0.92	0.42	9.07	15.2	13.7	1.24	2.26	43.9	-	17.9	2.54
						Min	530.3	0.04	0.03	0.22	3.55	2.17	1.23	0.18	2.97	-	3.21	0.00
						N	7	3	6	4	7	3	2	7	7	-	7	7
						Mean	10271	0.35	0.20	2.46	9.5	6.36	1.24	0.94	11.0	-	8.89	0.82
		Med				11019	0.08	0.15	0.27	8.83	3.22	1.24	0.90	6.19	-	5.45	0.21	
		Max				1450	6.66	4.54	582.0	137.9	532.9	9.87	0.96	1.58	-	4.90	1.31	
		Min				7.60	0.09	0.02	1.65	0.61	2.23	0.61	0.01	0.75	-	0.07	0.01	
		N				12	7	6	12	11	9	5	8	6	-	11	11	
	Mean	314.5	1.18	0.84	173.4	14.3	74.8	4.83	0.20	1.16	-	1.14	0.21					
	Med	212.7	0.36	0.10	104.4	1.45	12.7	3.16	0.06	1.14	-	0.84	0.08					
	Max	1831	8.89	-	13.67	1.32	4.14	-	1.44	-	-	21.5	11.1					
	Min	0.13	0.06	-	0.01	0.01	0.58	-	0.1	-	-	0.11	0.08					
	N	5	5	-	4	5	5	-	4	-	-	5	4					
	Mean	433.7	2.53	-	3.51	0.70	1.57	-	0.61	-	-	4.92	4.46					
	Med	49.1	0.26	-	0.18	0.87	0.87	-	0.44	-	-	0.8	3.32					
	Max	12913	20.2	-	1445	375.4	481.2	5.81	10.8	-	1.33	5.99	2.24					
Min	1.02	0.05	-	0.17	0.05	2.65	0.01	0.003	-	0.002	0.004	0.0004						
N	24	24	-	24	24	24	21	24	-	21	24	24						
Mean	1601	1.99	-	129.9	31.4	123.8	1.22	0.86	-	0.34	1.10	0.74						
Med	431.8	0.37	-	15.0	8.51	68.5	0.57	0.14	-	0.25	0.86	0.28						
Max	-	-	-	1135	422	114	5.35	9.07	-	2.15	9.42	-						
Min	-	-	-	0.69	0.25	0.03	0.13	0.11	-	0.02	0.07	-						
N	-	-	-	34	28	41	12	45	-	27	34	-						
Mean	-	-	-	101.8	19.3	13.8	1.22	2.74	-	0.49	1.57	-						
Med	-	-	-	40.9	1.77	3.8	0.28	2.52	-	0.19	0.87	-						
Max	-	-	-	2127	143	758	10.8	103	-	0.36	9.98	-						
Min	-	-	-	1.35	0.24	0.93	0.13	0.02	-	0.04	0.32	-						
N	-	-	-	39	37	39	15	26	-	4	39	-						
Mean	-	-	-	278.6	22.2	81.3	1.37	6.18	-	0.13	4.29	-						
Med	-	-	-	178	12.7	11.3	0.25	0.26	-	0.05	3.7	-						
Max	-	-	-	4552	486	121	10.5	2.26	-	0.07	50.3	-						
Min	-	-	-	0.02	0.12	1.39	0.15	0.02	-	0.01	0.02	-						
N	-	-	-	84	62	109	102	65	-	7	97	-						
Mean	-	-	-	138.9	16.2	26.7	1.95	0.45	-	0.03	3.09	-						
Med	-	-	-	7.88	3.28	19.4	0.99	0.33	-	0.03	0.39	-						
1	Hine Hina	Hine Hina	BAB oceanic spreading	Basalt-hosted		Max	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
						Min	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
						N	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Appendix C3 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Status	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg	
2	Brothers	Brothers	Volcanic Arc	Arc volcano	Surface	Max	294	0.95	-	-	221	1818	4.43	999	51.1	5109	98.5	-	
						Min	1.6	0.08	-	-	0.02	0.22	0.02	0.04	0.03	1.28	0.01	-	
						N	29	39	-	-	66	40	42	66	61	68	40	-	
						Mean	46.1	0.25	-	-	25.3	99.5	0.61	86.4	2.97	896.2	7.23	-	
						Med	11.5	0.2	-	-	2.91	7.02	0.15	9.11	0.6	408	3.11	-	
	Volcano 19	Volcano 20					Max	477	2.07	-	-	1434	425	220	12542	858	20323	0.01	-
							Min	4.5	0.1	-	-	0.13	3.91	51.4	253	2.5	199	0.01	-
							N	45	27	-	-	46	46	18	45	46	46	2	-
							Mean	72.0	0.50	-	-	398.0	136.8	112	1789	379.5	9769	0.01	-
							Med	25.2	0.29	-	-	396.5	137.5	90.7	1466	479.5	9716	0.01	-
Roman Ruins		PACMANUS	Transitional Arc	Rifted back arc (in old arc crust)	Surface	Max	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2728	8197	-	-	
						Min	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.55	39.6	-	-
Satanic Mills						N	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	56	58	-	
						Mean	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	194.3	2635	-	-
						Med	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	35.8	2270	-	-
						Max	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	125	18606	-	-
Izena Cauldron		JADE	BAB-IC	Rifted arc (intra-continental back arc rift)		Max	7348	138	-	0	404	648	430	6707	242	4373	633	-	
						Min	3.66	0.12	-	0	0.03	0.16	0.12	0.55	0.18	0.44	0.02	-	
						N	61	70	-	0	76	68	70	76	75	76	56	-	
						Mean	492.5	7.66	-	-	37.2	69.9	49.3	762.0	18.0	687.6	25.8	-	
						Med	17.5	0.40	-	-	1.65	9.14	19.7	199.5	7.7	371	1.09	-	

Appendix C3 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from SMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Host rock	Sample location	Stats	Cu	Sn	In	Co	Ni	Se	Te	Au	Ge	W	V	U
2	Brothers	Brothers	Volcanic Arc	Arc volcano	Surface	Max	-	-	-	1710	20	4102	1032	2.69	-	1.03	13.6	-
						Min	-	-	0.03	0.19	0.03	0.13	0.02	-	0.03	0.02	-	
						N	-	-	61	38	68	44	50	-	29	66	-	
						Mean	-	-	209.7	2.42	424.4	87.7	0.36	-	0.18	1.06	-	
		Volcano 19	Volcano 20			Med	-	-	57.2	0.69	24.3	10.8	0.17	-	0.11	0.51	-	
	Max					-	-	60.1	12.2	20.9	0.33	30.5	-	0.05	3.65	-		
		Roman Ruins	Pacmanus	Transitional Arc	Rifted back arc (in old arc crust)	Min	-	-	-	0.08	0.15	3.15	0.33	0.12	-	0.05	0.02	-
	N					-	-	46	36	46	1	46	-	1	27	-		
	Mean					-	-	7.11	2.54	9.23	0.33	5.93	-	0.05	0.39	-		
	Med					-	-	1.29	1.61	8.61	0.33	2.04	-	0.05	0.04	-		
		Satanic Mills				Max	-	-	-	-	-	119	9.94	85.4	-	-	-	-
	Min					-	-	-	-	-	3.81	2.38	0.04	-	-	-		
	N					-	-	-	-	-	27	9	56	-	-	-		
	Mean					-	-	-	-	-	15.9	7.10	7.99	-	-	-		
	Izena Cauldron	JADE	BAB-IC	Rifted arc (intra-continental back arc rift)	Med	-	-	-	-	-	7.11	7.29	3.23	-	-	-	-	
Max					-	-	30.7	18.3	277	0.28	11.6	-	18.5	7.65	-			
Min					-	-	0.02	0.19	1.06	0.17	0.02	-	0.03	0.05	-			
N					-	-	47	52	76	4	73	-	58	72	-			
	3				Mean	-	-	2.22	2.84	44.9	0.21	0.73	-	2.17	0.72	-		
Med					-	-	0.41	1.70	27.5	0.20	0.27	-	1.06	0.45	-			

Statistical summary of all pyrite LA-ICP-MS data from SMS deposits in this study. Deposit groups are described in section 4.5 and tectonic setting classifications are taken from Monecke et al. (2016). Abbreviations: mbsf = meters below seafloor, MOR = mid-ocean ridge, BAB = back-arc basin, IC = intra-continental, max = maximum, min = minimum, med = median. Elements are ordered according to the principal component analyses in **Table 4.2**. ‘.’ = no data are available.

Appendix C4. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from VMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Deposit Type	Age	Stats	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg		
1	Troodos	Skouriotissa	Ophiolite	1 - Mafic	Late Cretaceous	Max	2599	53	-	-	37.9	984	86.4	350	36.4	1405	4.35	-		
						Min	4.17	0.17	-	-	0.12	0.19	0.02	0.07	0.13	0.51	0.01	-		
						N	55	124	-	-	95	117	101	117	69	121	84	-		
						Mean	279.5	2.03	-	-	10.4	33.15	2.59	41.47	3.26	101.8	0.51	-		
						Med	82.2	0.67	-	-	7.05	5.99	0.73	25.9	0.78	43.9	0.12	-		
	Northern Cape	Salt River	BAB	Meso-Proterozoic	Max	69821	-	-	-	-	43.6	2070	42.5	37906	7.9	19.7	-	0.94		
					Min	29.5	-	-	-	1.61	2.22	0.14	0.36	0.1	1.67	-	0.45			
					N	7	-	-	-	4	9	9	9	8	9	-	3			
					Mean	12003	-	-	-	16.9	318.4	8.29	4481	2.38	6.47	-	0.77			
					Med	1610	-	-	-	11.2	47.1	1.17	80	0.86	4.62	-	0.91			
2	Turkey	Cayeli		2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Cretaceous	Max	28423	148.6	-	337.8	214.0	1553	832.9	12636	269.4	12114	729	-		
						Min	6	0.09	-	0.01	1.28	1.29	1.34	5	0.27	293.3	0.33	-		
						N	19	19	-	19	18	18	19	18	19	19	18	-		
						Mean	7326	41.0	-	73.6	44.6	352.5	178.2	2549	58.4	3337	147.7	-		
						Med	4730	25.9	-	10.3	24.7	156.0	81.4	1435	35	2914	51.5	-		
Ketchikan Mining District	Khayyam	Stumble-On	Volcanic Arc	2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	12.5	-	-	0.44	2.16	-	-	1.02	0.07	-	64.7	-	0.09	
						Min	12.5	-	-	0.44	2.16	-	-	-	-	-	0.31	127	-	0.31
						N	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	2	1	-	1	-	1
						Mean	12.5	-	-	0.44	2.16	-	-	-	0.66	127	-	0.31		
						Med	12.5	-	-	0.44	2.16	-	-	-	0.66	127	-	0.31		
						Max	5.4	-	-	-	0.15	-	1.02	0.07	-	64.7	-	0.09		
	Min	5.4	-	-	-	0.15	-	1.02	0.07	-	64.7	-	0.09							
	N	1	-	-	-	1	-	1	1	-	1	-	1							
	Mean	5.4	-	-	-	0.15	-	1.02	0.07	-	64.7	-	0.09							
	Med	5.4	-	-	-	0.15	-	1.02	0.07	-	64.7	-	0.09							
	Big Harbor East	Ruby Tuesday	Big Harbor East		2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	7.66	3.82	-	0.46	-	0.29	-	3.2	-	813	0.15	0.33	
							Min	7.66	3.82	-	0.46	-	0.29	-	3.2	-	813	0.15	0.33	
							N	1	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	1	1	
Mean							7.66	3.82	-	0.46	-	0.29	-	3.2	-	813	0.15	0.33		
Med							7.66	3.82	-	0.46	-	0.29	-	3.2	-	813	0.15	0.33		
Ruby Tuesday	Ruby Tuesday	Ruby Tuesday		2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	0.85	3.91	-	-	0.78	-	-	0.31	0.91	360	-	-		
						Min	0.85	3.91	-	-	0.78	-	-	0.31	0.91	360	-	-		
						N	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	-		
						Mean	0.85	3.91	-	-	0.78	-	-	0.31	0.91	360	-	-		
						Med	0.85	3.91	-	-	0.78	-	-	0.31	0.91	360	-	-		

Appendix C4 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from VMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Deposit Type	Age	Stats	Cu	Sn	In	Co	Ni	Se	Te	Au	Ge	W	V	U		
1	Troodos	Skouriotissa	Ophiolite	1 - Mafic	Late Cretaceous	Max	21761	-	-	5833	7244	1886	50.9	4.8	-	0.58	29	-		
						Min	1.83	-	-	0.04	0.2	1.61	0.24	0.03	-	0.03	0.08	-		
						N	126	-	-	120	113	53	52	84	-	74	105	-		
						Mean	775.1	-	-	294.4	290.2	360.6	5.64	0.50	-	0.19	1.49	-		
						Med	35.6	-	-	35.2	23.2	66.1	2.92	0.315	-	0.16	0.89	-		
	Northern Cape	Salt River	BAB		Meso-Proterozoic	Max	6074	-	-	-	23.9	-	4.06	0.25	-	-	-	-	-	
						Min	6.42	-	-	-	9.18	-	0.9	0.11	-	-	-	-		
						N	8	-	-	-	5	-	4	3	-	-	-	-		
						Mean	1547	-	-	-	15.1	-	2.06	0.2	-	-	-	-		
						Med	126.5	-	-	-	11.5	-	1.65	0.24	-	-	-	-		
2	Turkey	Cayeli			Upper Cretaceous	Max	68437	27.8	-	58.6	615.3	197.7	344.5	6.112	-	1.34	11.0	0.25		
						Min	1523	0.08	-	0.81	0.58	2.52	2	0.29	-	0.01	0.07	0.003		
						N	19	18	-	19	19	18	18	19	-	17	18	12		
						Mean	19962	2.50	-	12.7	117.6	39.3	58.2	1.64	-	0.18	2.36	0.05		
						Med	10777	0.57	-	6.53	55.7	12.1	12.6	0.73	-	0.08	1.31	0.01		
	Ketchikan Mining District	Khayyam	Stumble-On	Volcanic Arc	2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	9.64	3.87	-	698	271	38.9	6.89	-	-	-	-	-	-
							Min	9.64	1.01	-	3.46	6.65	38.9	5.47	-	-	-	-	-	
							N	1	2	-	2	2	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	
							Mean	9.64	2.44	-	350.7	138.8	38.9	6.18	-	-	-	-	-	
							Med	9.64	2.44	-	350.7	138.8	38.9	6.18	-	-	-	-	-	
Ketchikan Mining District	Big Harbor East					Max	4.01	1.49	-	2060	1.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Min	4.01	1.49	-	2060	1.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						N	1	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Mean	4.01	1.49	-	2060	1.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Med	4.01	1.49	-	2060	1.22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Ketchikan Mining District	Ruby Tuesday					Max	2.9	2.3	0.74	104	55.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Min	2.9	2.3	0.74	104	55.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						N	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Mean	2.9	2.3	0.74	104	55.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
						Med	2.9	2.3	0.74	104	55.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		

Appendix C4 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from VMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Deposit Type	Age	Stats	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg
2	Ketchikan Mining District	Copper City	Volcanic Arc	2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	8.3	0.51	-	-	-	0.85	0.09	-	1.08	28.8	0.01	0.64
						Min	8.3	0.51	-	-	-	0.85	0.09	-	1.08	28.8	0.01	0.64
						N	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	1	1	1
		Mean				8.3	0.51	-	-	-	0.85	0.09	-	1.08	28.8	0.01	0.64	
		Med				8.3	0.51	-	-	-	0.85	0.09	-	1.08	28.8	0.01	0.64	
		Max				8.61	-	-	-	1.25	1.03	2.02	0.22	0.87	30.1	-	0.5	
		Min				6.29	-	-	-	0.42	0.38	0.62	0.22	0.14	9.68	-	0.5	
		N				2	-	-	-	2	2	2	1	2	2	-	1	
		Mean				7.45	-	-	-	0.84	0.71	1.32	0.22	0.51	19.9	-	0.5	
	Med	7.45	-	-	-	0.84	0.71	1.32	0.22	0.51	19.9	-	0.5					
	Max	18.3	2.07	-	-	-	-	0.69	0	0.94	1.42	-	-					
	Min	18.3	2.07	-	-	-	-	0.69	0	0.94	1.42	-	-					
	N	1	1	-	-	-	-	1	0	1	1	-	-					
	Mean	18.3	2.07	-	-	-	-	0.69	-	0.94	1.42	-	-					
	Med	18.3	2.07	-	-	-	-	0.69	-	0.94	1.42	-	-					
	Max	3.22	2.6	-	-	-	1.1	2.9	-	0.02	-	2.9	-	0.02	-	28.1	-	-
	Min	3.22	2.6	-	-	-	1.1	2.9	-	0.02	-	2.9	-	0.02	-	28.1	-	-
	N	1	1	-	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	1	-	-
	Mean	3.22	2.6	-	-	-	1.1	2.9	-	0.02	-	2.9	-	0.02	-	28.1	-	-
	Med	3.22	2.6	-	-	-	1.1	2.9	-	0.02	-	2.9	-	0.02	-	28.1	-	-
	Max	-	-	-	-	0.29	3.18	2.02	2.29	0.27	1.36	1.92	-	0.51				
	Min	-	-	-	-	0.29	3.18	2.02	2.29	0.27	1.36	1.92	-	0.51				
	N	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	1				
	Mean	-	-	-	-	0.29	3.18	2.02	2.29	0.27	1.36	1.92	-	0.51				
Med	-	-	-	-	0.29	3.18	2.02	2.29	0.27	1.36	1.92	-	0.51					
Max	18.1	1.42	-	0.1	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	8.16	0.02	-	-	-	
Min	18.1	1.42	-	0.1	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	8.16	0.02	-	-	-	
N	1	1	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	-	
Mean	18.1	1.42	-	0.1	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	8.16	0.02	-	-	-	
Med	18.1	1.42	-	0.1	-	-	2.01	-	-	-	-	-	8.16	0.02	-	-	-	
Max	58.7	-	-	212	2.4	3550	4.67	3.23	154	4800	-	3.61						
Min	58.7	-	-	212	2.4	3550	4.67	3.23	154	4800	-	3.61						
N	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	1						
Mean	58.7	-	-	212	2.4	3550	4.67	3.23	154	4800	-	3.61						
Med	58.7	-	-	212	2.4	3550	4.67	3.23	154	4800	-	3.61						

Appendix C4 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from VMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Deposit Type	Age	Stats	Cu	Sn	In	Co	Ni	Se	Te	Au	Ge	W	V	U				
2	Ketchikan Mining District	Copper City		2 - Mafic Bimodal	Upper Proterozoic-Cambrian	Max	-	1.59	0.1	0.96	35	-	0.58	-	-	-	-	-				
						Min	-	1.59	0.1	0.96	35	-	0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
						N	-	1	1	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
						Mean	-	1.59	0.1	0.96	35	-	0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
						Med	-	1.59	0.1	0.96	35	-	0.58	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Corbin			Volcanic Arc			Max	1.58	2.77	0.14	96.5	29.5	24.2	1.89	-	-	-	-	-		
								Min	1.58	2.77	0.13	37.7	22.2	8.81	0.62	-	-	-	-	-		
								N	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	-	-	-	-	-		
								Mean	1.58	2.77	0.14	67.1	25.9	16.5	1.26	-	-	-	-	-		
								Med	1.58	2.77	0.14	67.1	25.9	16.5	1.26	-	-	-	-	-		
		Keete Inlet						Max	3.65	-	-	1.67	5	-	1.34	-	-	-	-	-		
								Min	3.65	-	-	1.67	5	-	1.34	-	-	-	-	-		
								N	1	-	-	1	1	-	1	-	-	-	-	-		
								Mean	3.65	-	-	1.67	5	-	1.34	-	-	-	-	-		
								Med	3.65	-	-	1.67	5	-	1.34	-	-	-	-	-		
		Lookout Mountain		Niblack		4 - Bimodal Felsic	Silurian-Ordovician	Max	1.52	-	0.05	1.25	12.4	42.3	-	-	-	-	-	-		
								Min	1.52	-	0.05	1.25	12.4	42.3	-	-	-	-	-	-		
								N	1	-	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Mean	1.52							-	0.05	1.25	12.4	42.3	-	-	-	-	-	-				
Med	1.52							-	0.05	1.25	12.4	42.3	-	-	-	-	-	-				
Max	8.66			-				-	152	4600	24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Min	8.66			-				-	152	4600	24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
N	1			-				-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Mean	8.66			-				-	152	4600	24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Med	8.66			-				-	152	4600	24	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		
Moira Copper			Primitive arc			Max	8.57	-	-	8.34	131	40.4	1.5	-	-	-	-					
						Min	8.57	-	-	8.34	131	40.4	1.5	-	-	-	-					
						N	1	-	-	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-					
						Mean	8.57	-	-	8.34	131	40.4	1.5	-	-	-	-					
						Med	8.57	-	-	8.34	131	40.4	1.5	-	-	-	-					
Barrier Islands						Max	56.4	1.25	0.12	62.1	32.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
						Min	56.4	1.25	0.12	62.1	32.3	-	-	-	-	-	-					
						N	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-					
						Mean	56.4	1.25	0.12	62.1	32.3	-	-	-	-	-	-					
						Med	56.4	1.25	0.12	62.1	32.3	-	-	-	-	-	-					

Appendix C4 cont. Summary of LA-ICP-MS data for pyrite from VMS deposits compiled in this study. Data in ppm.

Group	District	Deposit	Tectonic setting	Deposit Type	Age	Stats	Zn	Cd	Ga	Tl	Mo	Mn	Ag	Pb	Sb	As	Bi	Hg
3	Bonnifield District	WTF	BAB	5 - Felsic Siliciclastic	Late Devonian- Lower Carboniferous	Max	-	121	0.53	12.4	11.6	103	19.1	-	-	5032	0.47	9.94
						Min	-	0.70	0.10	0.05	0.51	1.12	1.11	-	-	151	0.06	2.75
						N	-	10	9	12	5	15	15	-	-	15	7	15
						Mean	-	22.8	0.26	1.19	3.36	28.0	8.07	-	-	1337	0.20	5.54
						Med	-	1.54	0.19	0.18	1.29	11.9	7.82	-	-	911	0.16	4.97
		Max				-	29	21.4	1148	2336	1534	472	-	-	12086	509	45.8	
		Min				-	0.61	0.10	0.29	2.41	3.24	0.81	-	-	53	0.07	1.05	
		N				-	9	11	16	15	16	15	-	-	16	15	14	
		Mean				-	7.21	5.19	314.0	185.2	358.9	98.7	-	-	4096	85.8	10.3	
		Med				-	3.51	1.78	85.4	13.9	136	34.3	-	-	4570	44.7	5.52	
		Max				-	40.2	0.48	0.15	9.8	7.93	177	-	-	481	391	4.39	
	Min	-	0.76	0.10	0.03	0.29	0.49	0.14	-	-	1.22	0.03	0.90					
	N	-	11	8	15	14	17	17	-	-	23	25	18					
	Mean	-	6.01	0.30	0.07	1.89	2.47	11.4	-	-	76.9	18.9	2.21					
	Med	-	1.89	0.3	0.06	0.61	1.03	0.68	-	-	31.5	0.43	2.18					
	Max	-	8.2	0.61	15.5	68.2	121	8.99	-	-	1077	0.30	2.37					
	Min	-	0.71	0.10	0.04	0.46	0.91	0.21	-	-	3	0.04	1.3					
	N	-	7	11	14	9	19	16	-	-	22	12	11					
	Mean	-	3.29	0.31	2.18	14.1	13.6	2.16	-	-	365.6	0.12	1.65					
	Med	-	1.99	0.26	0.13	2.55	4.36	1.45	-	-	288.5	0.09	1.54					
	Max	69000	199	20	1174	73	1780	4730	88800	2970	19400	712	68					
	Min	0.29	0.08	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.67	0.06	0.09	0.13	0.84	0.03	0.14					
	N	159	71	69	228	101	188	240	255	244	253	246	39					
Mean	1643	10.2	1.18	29.0	4.40	69.2	60.5	2330	162.6	1959	53.1	4.58						
Med	5	0.54	0.48	0.79	1.13	6.45	3.12	161	32	1100	19.4	0.82						
Max	44000	87	4.3	200.9	12.8	342	82	22700	1449	5710	319	15.1						
Min	0.62	0.09	0.14	0.01	0.2	0.79	0.07	0.05	0.22	4.1	0.03	0.20						
N	54	23	15	69	37	52	67	72	69	75	71	17						
Mean	1189	5.53	1.07	20.6	2.09	48.7	12.1	1266	102.5	1196	51.7	1.77						
Med	7.75	0.41	0.61	2.07	1.06	11.2	5.2	235.5	40.9	840	21.8	0.38						
Max	10.2	0.55	2.3	8.76	1.34	16.6	4.79	1180	228.7	7970	107.6	1.2						
Min	0.7	0.22	0.3	0.01	0.35	0.84	0.09	0.07	0.24	2.45	0.24	1.2						
N	6	4	3	28	5	12	23	30	28	30	27	1						
Mean	3.25	0.37	0.99	1.07	0.73	3.31	1.48	114.6	21.5	1274	33.5	1.2						
Med	1.63	0.35	0.37	0.08	0.78	1.42	0.9	25.4	4.40	113.7	27.4	1.2						
			Volcanic arc and back-arc		Middle Ordovician													
	Bathurst Mining District	Brunswick No. 6																
		Heath Steele B zone																

Statistical summary of all pyrite LA-ICP-MS data from VMS deposits in this study. Deposit groups are described in section 4.5 and deposit type classifications are from Barrie and Hannington (1999). Abbreviations: BAB = back-arc basin, max = maximum, min = minimum, med = median. ‘-’ = no data available. Elements are ordered according to the principal component analyses in **Figure 4.6**. Data references for each deposit are in **Table 4.3**.

Appendix C5 cont. Mineral summary statistics for LA-ICP-MS data compiled in this chapter and Chapter 2. Pyrite is not included.

GROUP 1 - Mafic-dominated cont.

Hematite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	-	54.6	5927	16.1	53.4	-	0.31	6532	3.86	108.0	78.3	41.4	-	23.0	7.25	0.42	5.68	0.13	871.0	819.0	-	-	1.27	22606	11955
Min.	-	0.46	0.22	0.22	0.10	-	0.03	621.0	0.12	6.33	0.79	2.08	-	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.34	0.02	8.74	4.75	-	-	0.04	0.07	10.0
Mean	-	8.12	861.2	6.14	26.0	-	0.10	2222	0.59	51.6	30.5	12.3	-	4.01	0.57	0.18	2.74	0.09	37.8	23.2	-	-	0.14	477.6	5747
Median	-	3.44	0.38	5.94	25.2	-	0.04	1719	0.33	52.2	26.4	9.79	-	0.20	0.17	0.16	2.57	0.11	17.0	6.97	-	-	0.12	18.4	5565
N	-	51	19	59	59	-	7	57	54	60	59	57	-	18	56	46	58	4	60	60	-	-	57	56	60
Isocubanite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	475319	13700	86.0	5.00	2.00	82.0	37.1	0.79	194.0	43.0	4.00	4.00	0.04	-	196.0	0.04	22.3	330.0	0.48	12.0	474.0	228.0	0.31	220000	36.0
Min.	305000	7135	40.0	0.60	0.23	3.74	0.03	0.01	2.28	3.00	4.00	4.00	0.04	-	86.0	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.48	0.22	140.0	47.6	0.01	153037	9.00
Mean	383691	9353	55.2	2.12	1.01	16.2	5.84	0.40	35.0	26.6	4.00	4.00	0.04	-	136.6	0.03	6.53	110.0	0.48	3.20	248.8	114.4	0.08	171647	20.0
Median	400000	7801	45.0	1.00	1.00	8.75	1.50	0.40	18.8	29.0	4.00	4.00	0.04	-	112.0	0.02	6.39	0.06	0.48	0.28	176.0	101.0	0.02	160096	11.0
N	5	5	5	5	5	15	14	2	12	5	1	1	1	-	5	3	14	3	1	4	5	10	5	5	5
Marcasite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	467775	1338	8.53	1.50	0.28	3.53	0.62	0.31	245.6	899.2	5.38	5.38	2.52	9.77	175.5	1006	15.2	221.6	22.0	78.3	671.9	81.9	0.56	410.1	0.89
Min.	467775	1.41	0.04	0.24	0.02	0.46	0.01	0.04	1.02	0.34	0.14	0.14	0.002	3.17	0.09	0.21	0.06	0.65	0.03	0.17	0.01	0.49	0.02	0.98	0.06
Mean	467775	199.2	1.52	0.62	0.09	2.17	0.38	0.16	40.5	41.6	2.29	2.29	0.23	5.38	9.65	72.1	2.01	76.8	8.84	12.2	77.4	14.2	0.24	79.0	0.39
Median	467775	28.3	1.03	0.38	0.09	2.35	0.45	0.13	15.4	4.01	2.11	2.11	0.07	3.21	1.29	17.6	1.34	82.5	7.46	4.40	3.09	6.01	0.10	21.2	0.33
N	28	24	15	9	8	4	10	8	29	29	28	28	25	3	22	28	24	29	25	10	25	12	8	29	8
Sphalerite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	154203	782528	9600	1135	566.0	4.40	11.0	0.39	1489	4111	33.3	1.08	1.08	900.2	335.9	5594	677.6	1901	2.57	18.9	113.8	253.0	0.71	29307	38.2
Min.	917.0	559000	326.0	0.50	0.02	0.07	0.04	0.01	0.33	3.08	0.10	0.001	0.001	2.11	1.38	0.30	0.04	0.28	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.62	0.01	119.0	0.04
Mean	62630	682082	5109	128.9	102.0	1.62	0.95	0.13	227.9	1096	2.29	2.29	0.14	110.7	30.3	434.6	47.6	65.1	0.37	3.89	6.18	18.7	0.09	2609	4.36
Median	40994	653056	4771	54.7	34.5	1.43	0.28	0.08	79.1	148.0	0.95	0.95	0.01	15.8	7.09	17.8	3.18	3.35	0.14	0.39	0.63	2.15	0.04	532.1	3.72
N	72	34	72	72	61	25	61	5	79	95	26	22	22	72	97	72	122	38	59	33	52	41	42	72	57

Appendix C5 cont. Mineral summary statistics for LA-ICP-MS data compiled in this chapter and Chapter 2. Pyrite is not included.

GROUP 2 - Bimodal cont.

Tennantite-tetrahedrite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.32	11.7	-	137917	-	-	-	-	-	-	7178	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Min.	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.84	6.97	-	70977	-	-	-	-	-	-	61.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Mean	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.08	8.88	-	93653	-	-	-	-	-	-	4720	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Median	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.08	7.98	-	72064	-	-	-	-	-	-	6920	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
N	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

GROUP 3 - Felsic-dominated

Marcasite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	659000	7480	14.2	4.86	9.18	11.6	4.58	2.22	1367	6780	-	-	-	2.69	898.0	40600	2460	16.0	86.0	1107	1545	34.7	640.0	903.0	230.0
Min.	513000	0.49	0.13	0.72	0.01	1.95	0.04	0.02	1.17	5.09	-	-	-	1.13	7.14	91.7	20.4	0.31	4.37	5.80	1.03	7.10	0.06	10.8	0.33
Mean	580786	864.1	3.29	2.76	1.24	5.60	1.31	0.49	245.3	971.0	-	-	-	1.97	182.1	7144	660.9	2.53	27.9	359.9	393.7	21.9	106.2	177.1	20.2
Median	570500	5.49	0.24	2.51	0.06	5.07	0.19	0.24	28.4	59.7	-	-	-	2.09	52.4	672.0	268.5	0.96	18.7	270.5	264.0	28.8	8.86	73.3	2.14
N	14	13	7	8	14	5	7	12	13	13	-	-	-	3	14	14	14	12	14	14	14	5	14	14	14

Sphalerite		Fe	Zn	Cd	Ga	In	Te	Au	W	As	Mn	V	U	Ge	Ag	Pb	Sb	Mo	Tl	Ni	Co	Se	Bi	Cu	Sn
Max.	132451	-	2931	175.0	240.0	20.4	1.7	-	241.0	767.0	57.5	-	-	10.5	61.4	-	-	27.8	3.81	16.4	32.0	302.0	159.0	8217	4237
Min.	28460	-	1290	0.18	3.40	1.73	0.11	-	2.73	12.9	0.27	-	-	2.70	4.29	-	-	0.43	0.03	1.20	0.22	11.1	0.03	9.72	0.76
Mean	47114	-	2001	35.1	47.2	7.85	0.57	-	72.4	220.0	6.12	-	-	5.54	19.3	-	-	6.44	0.49	4.22	3.83	49.1	15.4	969.7	340.1
Median	40360	-	1822	23.0	14.0	5.33	0.38	-	34.4	51.6	2.20	-	-	6.02	15.3	-	-	3.78	0.30	3.03	0.82	33.0	0.96	158.0	16.9
N	29	-	29	25	29	11	18	-	17	29	19	-	-	9	29	-	-	21	24	13	21	15	26	29	29

Data for all minerals (except pyrite) compiled from literature in this chapter. ‘-’ = no data available, N = number of analyses. Groups are discussed in section 4.5.

Appendix C6. LA-ICP-MS laboratories for data utilized in this study

Reference	Laser Wavelength	Laboratory (if available)
Halbach et al. (1998)	266 nm	n/a
Leistel et al. (1998)	n/a	n/a
Butler and Nesbitt (1999)	266 nm	n/a
Houghton et al. (2004)	266 nm	n/a
Slack et al. (2005)	213 nm	USGS Denver, USA
Bogdanov et al. (2008)	n/a	CODES, Australia
Cook et al. (2009)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Maslennikov et al. (2009)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
McClenaghan et al. (2009)	213 nm	Memorial University, Canada
Lein et al. (2010)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Dusel-Bacon et al. (2011)	266 nm	USGS Denver, USA
Ye et al. (2011)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Li et al. (2012)	n/a	CODES, Australia
Melekestseva et al. (2012)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Maslennikov et al. (2013)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Lockington et al. (2014)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Melekestseva et al. (2014)	213 nm	Adelaide Microscopy, University of Adelaide, Australia
Revan et al. (2014)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Wohlgemuth-Ueberwasser et al. (2014)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Genna and Gabourey (2015)	193/213 nm	University of Johannesberg
George et al. (2015)	213 nm	LaMaTer, Université de Québec à Chicoutimi
Wohlgemuth-Ueberwasser et al. (2015)	213 nm	Adelaide Microscopy, University of Adelaide
Belousov et al. (2016)	213 nm	University of Johannesberg
Keith et al. (2016b)	193 nm	CODES, Australia
Keith et al. (2016a)	193 nm	Geozentrum Nordbayern, Germany
Maslennikov et al. (2017)	n/a	Geozentrum Nordbayern, Germany
Melekestseva et al. (2017)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Wang et al. (2017)	213 nm	CODES, Australia
Dehnavi et al. (2018)	193nm	GEOMAR Centre for Ocean Research, Germany
Dekov et al. (2018)	193nm	University of New Brunswick, Canada
Grant et al. (2018)	193 nm	n/a
Martin et al. (2018)	213 nm	GEOMAR Centre for Ocean Research, Germany
Yuan et al. (2018)	213 nm	Cardiff University, UK
	193 nm	National Research Centre of Geoanalysis, Beijing, China

Appendix D

Reports and posters related to this thesis

Appendix D1: Critical metals in seafloor massive sulfide deposits. Poster presented during GEOMAR FB4 SAB review, May 2014.

Appendix D2: Presentations for Future Ocean, 2015.

D2.1. Sulphide mineralization in Icelandic geothermal pipes. Poster presented during Future Ocean Retreat, October 2015.

D2.2. Annual report for Future Ocean, 2015.

Appendix D3: Presentations for Future Ocean, 2016.

D3.1. Application of LA-ICPMS to seafloor massive sulfides. Poster presented during Future Ocean Retreat, October 2016.

D3.2. Annual report for Future Ocean, 2016.

Appendix D4: Presentations for Future Ocean, 2017.

D4.1. Critical elements in seafloor massive sulfide deposits. Poster presented during Future Ocean Retreat, 2017.

D4.2. Annual report for Future Ocean, October 2017.

Appendix D5: Trace element distribution and behaviour in seafloor massive sulphide deposits. Poster presented during the Marine Minerals: A New Resource for the 21st Century conference. Geological Society of London, October 2018.

Critical metals in seafloor massive sulfide deposits.

Hannah L. J. Grant* and Mark D. Hannington

Introduction

The discovery of black smokers, massive sulfides and vent biota at the crest of the East Pacific Rise (EPR) at 21°N, 103°W confirmed that the formation of metallic mineral deposits by seafloor spreading is intimately related to the formation of oceanic crust at the seafloor¹. More than 300 sites of seafloor hydrothermal activity are now known in a variety of tectonic settings (Fig. 1), primarily at mid-ocean ridges (MOR) (65%), but also in back-arc basins and submarine volcanic arcs⁵.

Figure 1

Locations of known hydrothermal vent sites and seafloor massive sulfide (SMS) deposits. From InterRidge Database Version 2.1.²

Critical Metals and SMS deposits

Raw materials are essential for the efficient functioning of the global economy and the essential role of non-energy materials such as minerals and metals has recently been highlighted. This demand is driven by the growth of developing economies and new emerging technologies, but the availability of certain metals is increasingly under pressure. A primary example of multi-national concern over strategic metal supply is the European Union (EU). The EU currently consumes 25-30% of all metals produced globally but is only responsible for 3% of global production, with many metals not produced in Europe at all³. In 2010 the EU identified a list of critical elements (Fig. 2), of which a number are found in SMS deposits.

Figure 2

Elements grouped by economic importance vs. supply risk. The High-Tech metals falling within the top right cluster of the above diagram are deemed as critical due to their high relative economic importance and high relative supply risk. Modified from the EU report on Critical Raw Materials⁴.

SMS Global Database: Critical Metals and PTEs

A state-of-the-art database of global SMS deposits under development at GEOMAR is beginning to provide information about the distribution, size and nature of SMS deposits.

Preliminary assessment of this database indicates that SMS deposits have the potential to become an important long-term source of four critical EU metals: Gallium (Ga), Germanium (Ge), Indium (In) and Antimony (Sb) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3

The range of selected critical elements in SMS deposits. Data for manganese nodules and crusts⁹ is shown for comparison. The data display range is from the maximum to the median value. SMS deposit data is from the SMS global database being developed at GEOMAR.

Figure 4

The range of selected PTEs in SMS deposits. Data for manganese nodules and crusts⁹ is shown for comparison. The data display range is from the maximum to the median value. SMS deposit data is from the SMS global database being developed at GEOMAR.

The current database is highly skewed towards major and base metal analyses. Many trace elements were not historically available in analytical packages due to poor resolution or a lack of interest in trace elements. To increase the amount and quality of the SMS data, relevant samples from archives are being analysed for a comprehensive suite of trace elements, including critical metals and PTEs (potentially toxic elements; Fig. 4).

Estimation of SMS Metal Content

Using a subset of the best-studied SMS deposits and comparison to land-based sulfide deposits formed by similar processes, Hannington et al. (2011) estimated the undiscovered mineral potential in the neovolcanic zones of the global oceans at 600 million tonnes (Mt) with the largest 10% of deposits containing ~400 Mt and by far the largest of this resource is located at slow-spreading ridges⁴. At the present time, the total amount of massive sulfide contained in the known SMS deposits is estimated to be ~50 million tons (Mt). Using a number of independent datasets and spatial analysis of known deposits, it is estimated that there is likely a maximum of ~900 significant SMS occurrences with only about 5% of submerged plate boundaries currently explored in detail⁴.

Using the estimation of 600 Mt of massive sulfide accumulation and data from the global SMS database, an estimation of contained critical and trace elements in SMS deposits can be made. Table 1 illustrates that for at least four of the EU critical metals there is a potential long term source in SMS deposits.

Table 1

Element	2013 global production (metric tonnes)	SMS mean (ppm)	Total potential metal in SMS deposits (metric tonnes)	Potential metal supply (years)
Antimony	163	505	303180	1860
Gallium	280	69	41580	149
Germanium	118	26	15420	131
Indium	770	18	10620	14

Amount of potential contained metal in SMS deposits based on current consumption and the tonnage estimation was made using the geometric mean. Global production figures are used as a proxy for world demand¹¹.

LA-ICP-MS: a Trace Analytical Method

At GEOMAR, state-of-the-art analytical facilities, including conventional and multi-collector ICP-MS, laser ablation ICP-MS, and EPMA will be used to explore the distribution of trace metals (and heavy metal isotopes) in different sample types as fingerprints of different processes that influence metal distribution in the crust and in SMS deposits (Fig. 5).

To assess the mineralogical siting of critical metals in different deposits, laser ablation ICP-MS (LA-ICP-MS) will allow direct and spatially resolved analysis of multi-element suites to a high degree of precision and accuracy and detection limits of parts per trillion. Recent advances in laser imaging techniques for trace elements in sulfides (e.g., pyrite) provide a powerful analytical tool for understanding sulfide paragenesis and possible controls on the distribution of trace and ultratrace metals.

Figure 5

GEOLAS 193 nm excimer laser and Magnetic sector ICP-MS laboratory at GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel

Recent modelling of MOR hydrothermal systems at GEOMAR and other institutions has found that overall metal mass balances are strongly influenced by temperature and processes such as brine generation and sub-seafloor metal precipitation^{1,6,8}. Data from deep drillholes is also revealing unexpectedly high concentrations of metals at depth in some ore-forming systems⁷, with important implications for the distribution of metals in the oceanic crust and the genesis of large ore deposits.

Laser Ablation ICP-MS (LA-ICP-MS) analysis of metals locked in disseminated sulfides in ODP drill core and from dredges of oceanic fault zones will therefore be used to track the behavior of these different metals in the MOR crust and to understand metal enrichment or depletion.

Potential Sample Locations

- TAG Hydrothermal Field, Mid-Atlantic Ridge
- East Pacific Rise/Galapagos Rift
- Indian Ocean MOR Ridges
- Reykjanes Ridge, Iceland

Anticipated Outcomes

- Improved geochemical database for critical metals and PTEs in SMS deposits
- Characterization of geometallurgical properties, mineralogical siting and critical and trace metal inventories of multiple mid-ocean ridge SMS deposits
- Constraints on the origins and behaviour of metals in the reaction zones of mid-ocean ridge seafloor hydrothermal systems
- Prove the application of LA-ICP-MS in the complete characterization and "fingerprinting" of SMS deposits

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SULPHIDE MINERALIZATION IN ICELANDIC GEOTHERMAL PIPES

An analogue for formation of seafloor massive sulphide deposits?

Introduction

The Mid-Atlantic Ridge surfaces on the Reykjanes Peninsula, SW Iceland. The Reykjanes geothermal system is located on the tip of the peninsula, surrounded on three sides by ocean. The reservoir hydrothermal liquid is seawater-dominated and reacts with surrounding basalts at temperatures up to 340°C. As the fluid is drawn up pipes for geothermal energy, abrupt (artificial) temperature and pressure changes cause sulphide precipitation as mm to cm thick scaling in both downhole and surface pipes, and contains abundant trace metals orders of magnitude higher than in seafloor deposits.

Figure 1. Geological map of Iceland showing the location of the Reykjanes geothermal field.

Figure 2. Panorama of Reykjanes geothermal site showing potential sampling locations. Primary locations (numbered) for sampling are downhole (from wellhead), upstream (of wellhead), orifice plate, fluid control valve (FFCV), and variable locations downstream (of orifice plate). Additional samples are available from the separator station, vent house, and Grey Lagoon discharge pond (sinters).

Scale Composition

1. Downhole	2. Upstream	3. Orifice plate/FFCV	4. Downstream
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple, fine-grained banded growth textures common - Mineralogy: chalcopyrite, sphalerite, Au-Ag (electrum), bornite, magnetite, digenite, pyrite 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fine grained banding common - Mineralogy: sphalerite, bornite, galena, digenite, chalcopyrite, amorphous silica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Massive sulphides cm's thick - Mineralogy: sphalerite, bornite, galena, digenite, chalcopyrite, gold and silver 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can be cm's thick - Mineralogy: sphalerite, chalcopyrite, traces of: galena, bornite and amorphous silica
<p>super-saturated metal-rich end-member fluid</p>	<p>RN-09 Zn = 18 wt% Fe = 17 wt% Cu = 21 wt% Pb = 1 wt% S = 30 wt% 121 ppm Au 667 ppm Ag</p>	<p>RN-12 Zn = 20 wt% Fe = 9 wt% Cu = 23 wt% Pb = 15 wt% S = 22 wt% 570 ppm Au 9200 ppm Ag</p> <p><i>300°C in well, downhole 24°C, depth 112 bars, Cd</i></p>	<p>RN-23 Zn = 45 wt% Fe = 3 wt% Cu = 14 wt% Pb = 0.1 wt% S = 31 wt% 1670 ppm Au 116 ppm Ag</p>
<p>evolution of hydrothermal fluid and metal precipitation</p>			

Why study the scaling?

Distinct zoning of elements is present in scales precipitated from a super-saturated downhole fluid to a metal-deficient surface fluid from evolution of the hydrothermal fluid and metal precipitation from physiochemical changes. The Reykjanes geothermal seawater-dominated system is a unique analogue to seafloor hydrothermal systems as each stage of precipitation resembles processes occurring at the modern seafloor.

The aims of this project are to:

- Quantify amount of metals in end-member super-saturated fluid, specifically critical and trace metals
- What minerals do critical and trace metals occur in?
- What are the sources of the metals?
- Apply results to modern seafloor hydrothermal systems to understand what processes occur deep below the seafloor but cannot normally be quantified.

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Mineralogical and geochemical assessment of seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposits

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Abstract

Over the past three decades, a large number of seafloor hydrothermal vent sites and associated sulphide deposits have been discovered in the world's oceans. Geochemical analysis of samples collected from vent sites worldwide suggests that seafloor sulphide deposits may contain significant trace metal concentrations. As seafloor sulphide deposits are now being evaluated as potential future metal resources, quantifiable models of resource formation, geological characterisation, and composition are crucial to enable sustainable exploitation.

The global economy is dependent on specialty metals used in high-tech applications, the so-called 'critical metals'. This project provides the first estimate of the global critical metal endowment of these deposits, including elevated concentrations of gallium, germanium, antimony and indium. Seafloor massive sulphide accumulations are also found to contain elevated concentrations of the rare elements bismuth, cadmium, mercury, molybdenum, selenium, tellurium, and thallium.

Introduction

Since the discovery of the first hydrothermal venting on the seafloor in 1977, more than 300 sites of active and inactive seafloor hydrothermal sites and associated seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposits have been discovered in the world's oceans in a variety of tectonic settings (Fig. D2.1). Geochemical analysis of samples collected from vent sites suggests that seafloor sulphide deposits may contain significant metal concentrations.

The global economy is increasingly dependent on specialty metals used in high-tech applications, with demand growing as new technologies emerge. These so-called 'critical metals' are generally sourced only as low-tonnage by-products of large ore deposits. The European Union (EU) is particularly concerned about its strategic supply of critical metals as it consumes 25-30% of global production, but produces only 3% of the supply, with many important metals not produced in Europe at all. In 2014, the EU listed 19 critical raw materials deemed essential to economic growth, but the supply of which are at risk (EU Commission 2014). This project is initially focused on the global distribution of critical metals in seafloor massive sulphide deposits, which are now targeted for exploration for base and precious metals.

Available data is now sufficient to allow an initial assessment of the global seafloor sulphide potential, with this project also investigating the factors controlling critical and trace element enrichment in seafloor hydrothermal systems.

Research Questions

- What is the global trace and critical metal endowment of seafloor sulphide deposits?
- Where do trace and critical metals occur in seafloor sulphide deposits?
- What are the controls on the distribution of trace and critical metals in seafloor sulphide deposits?
- What is the source of trace and critical metals in seafloor deposits?

Methodology

Estimation of global endowment

Using a global geochemical database of SMS deposits held at GEOMAR, the first aim of this project was to estimate the critical metal resource potential of seafloor massive sulphide deposits. Using the average critical and trace metal concentrations from this database

for over 4,900 sulphide samples from the modern seafloor, and an estimated total tonnage of ~600 Mt of massive sulphides (Hannington et al 2010), the global critical and trace metal resource contained in seafloor sulphide deposits can then be inferred.

Sample selection

Only 6 seafloor sulphide deposits have been identified exceeding 2 million tonnes (Mt) with the 2.7 Mt TAG deposit on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge chosen for starting the investigations in this project. The TAG deposit was selected as it was drilled by the Oceanic Drilling Program (ODP) in 1994, giving a detailed 3D model to 100m below the seafloor surface (Humphris et al., 1995).

In addition to TAG and other mid-ocean ridge deposits, this project is using a unique proxy to quantify the end-member trace and critical metal content of mid-ocean ridge type hydrothermal fluids before precipitation. Recent fluid data from >2km depth in the Reykjanes geothermal wells on Iceland indicates unexpectedly high concentrations of metals. As the super-saturated metal-rich liquid ascends, the decrease in pressure causes boiling and rapid precipitation of metal-rich sulphide scales within the well pipes (similar to mechanisms of precipitation under the seafloor). As the Reykjanes geothermal site is located on the sub-aerial expression of the mid-Atlantic Ridge, these scales are potentially a true indicator to the end-member metal content of mid-ocean ridge hydrothermal fluids. These samples may provide direct evidence of the processes occurring in the feeder zones of seafloor sulphide deposits (far below the deepest drillhole drilled into a seafloor deposit) prior to discharge on the seafloor, as the end-member metal content of deep hydrothermal fluids cannot be directly measured. Boiling and deposition of metals at TAG is unlikely to occur below the seafloor due to a ~3.6 km water depth, however the samples from the Reykjanes geothermal wells boil during ascent and directly precipitate metals. Samples from Reykjanes and TAG therefore represent the two end-members of mid-ocean-ridge seawater-dominated hydrothermal environments and direct comparisons of trace and critical metal distributions and behaviour can be made.

Location, controls on, and sources of critical and trace metals

Experimental work is currently ongoing to investigate the distribution of critical and trace elements in sulphides from TAG using laser-ablation inductively coupled mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) facilities at GEOMAR. This high precision technique allows direct, quick and spatially resolved analysis of multi-element suites with very low detection limits (to parts per trillion making it a powerful analytical tool for understanding of the paragenesis, concentration and evolution of critical and trace metal enrichments or depletions in seafloor sulphide deposits).

Preliminary Results

Results indicate that four critical metals (indium, germanium, gallium and antimony) are present at concentrations that could be important to a revenue stream if the deposits are mined. Gallium, germanium, antimony and indium average 62 ppm, 29 ppm, 498 ppm and 21 ppm respectively in global seafloor sulphide deposits (Fig. D2.2) with concentrations varying by orders of magnitude between different tectonic settings. This reflects a combination of diverse host rock lithologies, spreading rates, magma supply, crustal thickness, magma composition and volatile flux. In 2014, the world's refinery production (a proxy for demand) of these critical metals was estimated to be 440 t gallium, 165 t germanium, 820 t indium, and 160,000 t antimony (U.S. Mineral Commodity Summaries 2015). Comparison of these production figures with the estimated global metal endowment of seafloor sulphide deposits shows that seafloor sulphide occurrences forming around active hydrothermal vents may represent a significant repository for selected critical metals, especially gallium and antimony (Fig. D2.2). However, these elements are unlikely to be exploited as a primary resource, or replace land-based sources at the current time.

Outlook

- Continue critical and trace element analysis of both TAG sulphide samples and Reykjanes scale samples
- Compare preliminary results with new database compiled of all LA-ICP-MS data for sulphides in seafloor deposits from the scientific literature
- Begin to produce geochemical models for the distribution and controls on critical and trace elements in sulphides

Other aspects

Networking and research visits

- Data sharing and potential project crossover with a Bristol University (UK) project on the environmental impact of the weathering of seafloor sulphide deposits
- Visits to Iceland to work with the Icelandic GeoSurvey (ISOR) in November 2014 and August 2015 to collect sample suites of geothermal sulphide scales
- Scientific research cruise POS483 onboard R/V Poseidon to the Palinuro hydrothermal site, Mediterranean Sea (March-April 2015)

Conferences

- Oral presentation accepted for GeoBerlin 2015 conference (October 4-7) in the Marine Ore Deposits session entitled “The Critical Metal Potential of Seafloor Massive Sulphide Deposits”

Publications

- Grant, H.L.J., Monecke, T., Petersen, S., Hannington, M.D., Critical Metal Potential of Seafloor Massive Sulphide Deposits (2015) GeoBerlin Conference, Berlin, Germany, 4-7 October. Conference abstract (accepted).

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- U.S. Mineral Commodity Summaries (2015) Accessible at <http://minerals.usgs.gov/minerals/pubs/mcs/>. Produced by the U.S. Geological Survey.

Figure captions:

Figure D2.1. Global distribution of seafloor hydrothermal vent sites with associated sulphide deposits. The locations of the TAG deposit and Reykjanes geothermal site are marked by white stars.

Figure D2.2. Box and whisker plot representing the abundance of critical and trace elements in over 4,900 seafloor sulphide samples from modern hydrothermal vent sites. The box encloses the interquartile range with the median as a horizontal line. The vertical lines represent the maximum and minimum values. The red diamonds highlight the average concentrations. The horizontal grey line indicates an arbitrary cutoff for potentially economic concentrations of above 50 ppm.

Figure D2.1.

Figure D2.2.

APPLICATION OF LASER ABLATION-ICPMS TO SEAFLOOR MASSIVE SULPHIDES

An example of the TAG hydrothermal deposit

Introduction

Laser ablation inductively-coupled mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) is a sensitive analytical method for trace element and isotopic ratio determination.

The application of LA-ICP-MS in geological sciences is an ideal tool to investigate the distribution and zonation of trace metals in sulphide minerals as it allows the in situ analysis over a large (wt%-ppb) concentration range of individual minerals in any solid-sample matrix. This technique produces sensitive, spatially resolved measurements that are otherwise not possible by traditional solution and/or bulk methods of geochemical analysis.

TAG seafloor massive sulphide deposit

The greatest resource potential in seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposits is in the largest deposits. So far, only 6 deposits have been identified that exceed 2 million tonnes (Mt) in size. The large 2.7 Mt TAG deposit on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge was selected for detailed study because of the availability of drill core from the Oceanic Drilling Program (ODP).

During ODP Leg 158 in 1994, samples were obtained to a depth of more than 100m below the seafloor providing a unique opportunity to assess the 3D distribution of trace and critical metals in this deposit (Fig. 2).

In this project, laser ablation ICP-MS was performed for the first time on the major sulphide minerals below the seafloor (pyrite, sphalerite, marcasite and chalcopyrite), in order to investigate important controls on critical metal distribution.

Figure 3. Laser ablation transect showing change in selected element concentrations across a zoned pyrite from 78m depth in the TAG deposit. The core of the pyrite grain at 1 is assumed to be the oldest pyrite and spot 10 the youngest in the transect. The laser spot size ranges from 24 to 44 microns in width. The transect is approximately 500 microns (0.5 mm) long.

Preliminary results

Strongly zoned pyrite (Fig. 3) reveals dramatic zoning of trace metal concentrations with respect to paragenetic stage, from early high-temperature growth to later lower-temperature growth and very different trace element enrichments.

Aims of this project

- Quantify critical metal concentrations in a significant seafloor massive sulphide deposit
- Determine mineralogical residency of critical metals
- Establish how metal concentrations vary and apply predictions to other less-well characterised SMS deposits

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Mineralogical and geochemical assessment of seafloor massive sulphide (SMS) deposits

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Abstract

Over the past three decades, a large number of seafloor hydrothermal vent sites and associated sulphide deposits have been discovered in the oceans. Geochemical analysis of samples collected from sites worldwide indicate that the deposits contain a number of important trace metals. As seafloor sulphide deposits are now being evaluated as potential future metal sources, quantifiable models of their formation, geological characterisation, and composition are crucial.

The global economy is dependent on specialty metals used in high-tech applications. Many are subject to fluctuations in supply and have been labeled ‘critical metals’. This project is focused on the global distribution of these metals in mid-ocean ridge seafloor massive sulphide deposits, and in particular on the metal sources, their behavior in seafloor hydrothermal systems, and the causes of their enrichment. Data collected so far indicate potentially important concentrations of the critical metals gallium, germanium, antimony, and indium in different deposits. The concentrations of these elements varies systematically across different geodynamic settings and also according to the temperature of sulphide formation. The latter appears the most important control on the distribution of the critical elements at a deposit scale.

Introduction

In 2014, the European Union (EU) listed 19 critical raw materials deemed essential to economic growth but the supplies of which are at risk (EU Commission 2014). The ‘critical metals’ are generally sourced only as low-tonnage by-products of large ore deposits. EU countries are particularly concerned about the strategic supply of these metals as they consumes 25-30% of global production and produces only 3% of the amount required. Many of the important metals are not produced in Europe at all. Several EU countries, including Germany are looking to seafloor massive sulphide deposits as a possible source of some of those metals.

Since the discovery of the first hydrothermal venting on the seafloor in 1977, more than 330 sites of active and inactive seafloor massive sulphides have been discovered in a wide range of tectonic settings. However, it remains unclear whether these deposits, if mined, could be a new source of critical metals. This study is addressing 4 key questions concerning the mineralogical and geochemical enrichment of the critical metals in seafloor massive sulphides.

Research Questions

- (1) What is the global critical metal endowment of seafloor sulphide deposits and which deposits are enriched?
- (2) Where do trace and critical metals occur in seafloor sulphide deposits?
- (3) What are the controls on the distribution of the metals in different deposits?
- (4) What is the source of the metals in different seafloor hydrothermal systems?

Methodology

Objective 1

A global geochemical database of over 4,200 seafloor massive sulphide samples (GEOMAR unpublished data) is being examined to determine the critical and trace metal resource potential of more than 300 known deposits. From these data the global critical metal resource endowment of seafloor deposits can be inferred and areas of potential enrichment identified. We have published preliminary results of this study in Monecke et al. (2016).

Objective 2

The greatest resource potential is in the largest deposits. So far, only 6 seafloor sulphide deposits have been identified that exceed 2 million tonnes (Mt) in size. The 2.7 Mt TAG deposit on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge was selected for detailed study because of the availability of drill core from the Oceanic Drilling Program (ODP). Samples were obtained from the deposit to a depth of more than 100m below the seafloor providing a unique opportunity to assess the 3D distribution of trace metals in the deposit. High-resolution laser-ablation inductively coupled mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) is being carried out on the samples at GEOMAR to precisely map their distribution.

Objective 3

Data collected in Objective 2 is being used to produce the first geochemical model of the behaviour of critical trace metals in a large seafloor massive sulphide deposit. A key question is the degree to which different mineral phases sequester different metals and the conditions under which those minerals form. Future extraction techniques may be targeted to specific mineral phases that contain the highest concentrations of the critical metals.

Objective 4

We are exploring a number of active hydrothermal systems to address the question of the sources of the critical metals. This includes analysis of the source rocks and the hydrothermal fluids themselves. One proxy that is being used for mid-ocean ridge type hydrothermal fluids is the active geothermal system on the Reykjanes Peninsula of Iceland. Fluids and mineral scales from >2 kilometres depth in the Reykjanes geothermal wells on Iceland indicates unexpectedly high concentrations of most trace metals (e.g. Hannington et al, 2016), and modelling is underway to address the particular fluid properties responsible for that enrichment. These data will be compared to a growing database of trace metal data in fluids from other active seafloor hydrothermal systems.

Preliminary Results

Objectives 1 and 2

Preliminary results indicate that significant concentrations of the critical metals gallium, germanium, antimony, and indium are present in global seafloor sulphide deposits (Fig. D3.1). Tectonic setting is a primary control on the distribution of critical metals in the deposits and reflects a combination of diverse host rock lithologies, spreading rates, magma supply, crustal thickness, magma composition and volatile inputs (Monecke et al., 2016). However, critical metal enrichment can also vary significantly within the same area. An example is the Pacmanus and SuSu deposits in the Manus Basin, which are only separated by 40 kilometres but have dramatically different germanium and particularly indium concentrations. On a deposit-scale, the temperature of sulphide formation dictates the distribution of the critical metals, but difference between neighbouring deposits likely reflect other variables.

Objective 3 and 4

Initial LA-ICP-MS results from the TAG deposit indicate that in all cases sphalerite is the main repository of the elements gallium, antimony and germanium. The highest indium concentrations from TAG is observed in chalcopyrite between 15 and 32 metres below the seafloor.

Compilation of currently available bulk geochemical data from Reykjanes indicates that the most abundant critical metal in the sulphide scales is antimony. Samples from sphalerite-rich scales from surface pipes are up to three orders of magnitude more concentrated in antimony than at TAG (Herzig et al., 1998). The maximum concentrations of gallium at Reykjanes are also located in sphalerite-rich surface scales. Data ranges for indium from TAG are broadly similar to Reykjanes and germanium was not analysed for TAG samples (Herzig et al., 1998). The bulk geochemistry compilation for Reykjanes is currently biased towards samples collected from surface pipes, but geochemical analysis of a suite of samples including

samples from two downhole geothermal pipes to 1832 metres depth is currently in progress.

Outlook

- Contribution to a first publication on global trace metal distributions (Monecke et al., 2016)
- First publication in preparation on LA-ICP-MS analyses of TAG sulphide samples
- New analyses by raster LA-ICP-MS elemental mapping using new facilities at GEOMAR
- Comprehensive modelling of spatial and temporal metal distribution in the Reykjanes system

Other aspects

Networking and research collaborations

- Future Ocean Retreat October 2015
- Data sharing and potential project crossover with a Bristol University (UK) project on the environmental impact of the weathering of seafloor sulphide deposits
- Doctoral Research Profile in ISOS publication “Building Bridges In Marine Science Education”

Conferences

- Oral presentation at GeoBerlin 2015 conference (October 4-7, 2015) in the Marine Ore Deposits session entitled “The Critical Metal Potential of Seafloor Massive Sulphide Deposits”

Publications

- Monecke, T., Petersen, S., Hannington, M.D., **Grant, H.L.J.**, Samson, I. (2016) The Minor Element Endowment of Modern Sea-floor Massive Sulfides and Comparison with Deposits Hosted in Ancient Volcanic Successions. *Reviews in Economic Geology*, v. 18, pp. 245-306.
- **Grant, H.L.J.**, Monecke, T., Petersen, S., Hannington, M.D., Critical Metal Potential of Seafloor Massive Sulphide Deposits (2015) GeoBerlin Conference, Berlin, Germany, 4-7 October. Conference abstract.

Other information

Please note that I took full-time maternity leave from 29th March to 15th September 2016 and I am working at 50% of contracted hours until January 2017.

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- European Commission, 2014. Report on Critical Raw Materials for the EU. Report of the Ad hoc Working Group on defining critical raw materials. European Union, Brussels.
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Figure D3.1. Diagram showing global enrichment factors for seafloor massive sulphide deposits enriched in the critical metals antimony (Sb), indium (In), gallium (Ga) and germanium (Ge). Enrichment factors were calculated by dividing the deposit average (unpublished GEOMAR data) by the median abundance of each critical metal from seafloor massive sulphide deposits in all tectonic settings (unpublished GEOMAR data and Monecke et al., 2016). Enrichment factors were then grouped into four categories. Coloured circle rims indicate different tectonic settings: **basalt-hosted mid-ocean ridges**, **ultramafic-hosted mid-ocean ridges**, **sedimented mid-ocean ridges**, **volcanic arcs**, back-arc basins, **rifted volcanic arcs**. The base map shows locations of known high-temperature seafloor hydrothermal systems and associated sulphide deposits (Petersen et al., 2016). Red triangles indicate occurrences with economically interesting concentrations (average grades either 5 wt% Cu, >15 wt% Zn or >5 ppm Au). Large triangles indicate occurrences above 1 million tonnes. Note that geochemical analyses are commonly only available for surface samples that are not representative of an entire deposit.

CRITICAL ELEMENTS IN SEAFLOOR MASSIVE SULFIDE DEPOSITS

What are the critical elements?

Critical elements have crucial societal impact for developing technologies, environmentally-friendly energy production and strategic national stockpiles.

Virtually all critical trace elements are extracted from mineral deposits as by-products (Fig. 1); fluctuating metal prices, geopolitical risks and limited recycling means that governments and organisations have begun to consider the 'criticality' of many trace elements.

There is very limited information about mineralogical sequestration of critical elements in seafloor massive sulfide deposits. Now that these deposits are considered to be commercially viable, more detailed work on the fundamental controls on ore genesis and overall trace and critical element inventories is crucial.

Fig. 1. The metal wheel by Reuter et al. (2005) illustrating interdependencies of metal cycles by summarising the chemical and physical linkages between metals in sulfide and oxide ores. Critical elements are highlighted in bold and ores relevant to this project are outlined in red.

Mineralogical characterisation

The 2.7 Mt TAG deposit on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge is one of the largest known currently-forming seafloor massive sulfide deposits. Samples from a depth of more than 100m below the seafloor were analyzed by high-resolution laser ablation ICP-MS to assess the 3D distribution of critical elements.

Samples from ODP Leg 158

LA-ICP-MS on complex sulfide assemblages

Downhole element abundances

Fig. 5. 3D deposit-scale distribution of elements analyzed by LA-ICP-MS in this study for sulfides in the TAG deposit from downhole element abundance plots like Fig. 4. Critical elements are in bold and the blue line demarcates the seawater-hydrothermal mound interface. A and B indicate the cross section in Fig. 2.

Critical element inventory

There is significant abundance of the critical elements As, Co, Ga, Ge, In, and Mo within one or more sulfide phases in the TAG deposit.

These elements generally occur as substitutions directly into mineral lattices, and due to the large overall pyrite-dominated tonnage of the TAG deposit, critical trace-elements wholly or partially hosted by pyrite (As, Co, Mo, and Sb) could be of significant economic interest.

Fig. 6. Summary of critical elements in TAG sulfides

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Mineralogical and geochemical assessment of seafloor massive sulfide (SMS) deposits

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Abstract

Geochemical analysis of samples collected from seafloor massive sulfide deposits indicate that these deposits contain a number of important trace metals. As they are now being evaluated as potential future metal sources, quantifiable models of their formation, detailed mineralogical studies, and investigation of trace element behaviour is crucial. In-situ high-resolution microanalytical data is becoming available for surface and near-surface sulfides in seafloor deposits but detailed interpretations of the behaviour and location of trace elements from the deposit surface into the deep subseafloor are lacking. Systematic enrichment and depletions of trace elements in sulfides under well-constrained conditions reflect mineralizing conditions at the time of deposition and can distinguish between primary and later secondary assemblages. This project documents the detailed distribution of trace metals in the sub-seafloor in one of the largest-known seafloor massive sulfide deposits with major implications for the controlling factors on metal sequestration in the deep subseafloor. This work contributes towards the development of a total inventory for potentially economic metals from the seafloor.

Introduction

There is an increasing amount of in-situ microanalytical data available for trace elements in sulfides from active seafloor deposits, but little interpretation of what the data can tell us about the behaviour of metals in actively-forming hydrothermal systems, and by inference, also ancient hydrothermal systems. This project is focused on the distribution of trace metals in mid-ocean ridge seafloor massive sulfide deposits, metal sources and behaviour in seafloor hydrothermal systems, and methods of enrichment. Of particular interest are the critical metals used in modern high-tech applications. Virtually all critical metals are extracted from mineral deposits as by-products; fluctuating metal prices, geopolitical risks, and limited recycling means that while many governments and organizations have begun to consider the ‘criticality’ of many trace elements (e.g.; European Commission, 2010), there is very limited information about the mineralogical sequestration of many non-sulfide forming critical and trace elements in seafloor massive sulfide deposits.

Since 2011, the International Seabed Authority has been issuing exploration licenses for seafloor massive sulfide exploration, and more detailed work on the fundamental controls on ore genesis and overall trace metal inventories is crucial now that these deposits are being evaluated as viable future economic resources. In order to determine whether seafloor massive sulfide deposits are a potentially viable resource for critical and trace metals, we have examined the behaviour and distribution of metals in the TAG seafloor massive sulfide deposit on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. The understanding of the detailed distribution of metals in seafloor massive sulfide deposits such as TAG has major implications for the controlling factors on metal sequestration in the deep subseafloor and development of a total inventory for potentially economic metals from the seafloor. This work addresses 4 key questions concerning the mineralogical and geochemical enrichment of the critical and trace metals in seafloor massive sulfides.

Research Questions

- (1) What is the global critical and trace metal endowment of seafloor sulfide deposits?
- (2) Where do critical and trace metals occur in seafloor sulfide deposits?
- (3) Are there systematic controls on the distribution of critical and trace metals?
- (4) What are the end-member concentrations of trace metals in seafloor hydrothermal systems?

Methodology

Objective 1

A global geochemical database of over 4,200 seafloor massive sulfide samples (GEOMAR unpublished data) was analyzed to determine the critical and trace metal resource potential of more than 340 known seafloor deposits. From these data the global critical metal resource endowment of seafloor deposits was inferred and areas of potential enrichment identified. We have published preliminary results in Monecke et al. (2016).

Objective 2

The 2.7 Mt TAG deposit was selected for detailed study as it is one of the largest known currently-forming seafloor massive sulfide deposits. Availability of samples from the Ocean Drilling Program (ODP) to a depth of more than 100m below the seafloor provided a unique opportunity to assess the 3D distribution of critical and trace metals. High-resolution laser-ablation inductively-coupled mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) was carried out on the samples at GEOMAR to precisely map the distribution of metals in the TAG deposit. Laser-ablation ICP-MS is a high-precision geological in-situ analytical technique providing elemental analyzes over a large mass and concentration range with limits of detection at or below single-digit parts per million (ppm) for most of the periodic table. In situ analyzes also enable the direct characterization of texturally complex and compositionally variable mineral grains from multiple periods of growth and dissolution. Laser-ablation-ICP-MS can distinguish between trace metals hosted directly in mineral lattices, as inclusions of other minerals, and potentially as nanoparticulate phases in individual minerals. If the LA-ICP-MS signal is relatively smooth, this indicates that the element may be homogeneously distributed in the mineral by lattice substitution (Fig. D4.1). Inclusions of other minerals yield a heterogeneous trace element enrichment seen in the raw time-resolved LA-ICP-MS signal as irregular spikes, often with co-enrichment of other elements also associated with the visible or micro-inclusion (Fig. D4.1). Recent high-resolution analytical work also suggests that nanoparticles host a variety of elements within sulfides and may be important carriers of trace elements; the presence of nanoparticles can be inferred from LA-ICP-MS data.

Objective 3

Precipitation of a mineral phase from a hydrothermal fluid is a primary process governed by temperature, pH, redox conditions, and fugacity of oxygen and sulfur. Secondary processes such as mineral recrystallization, mineral dissolution, and trace metal remobilization commonly overprint and alter initial element assemblages. We are investigating if primary processes can be distinguished from secondary processes in an active-seafloor deposit, and if there is systematic behaviour of trace and critical metals during these alteration and remobilization events. We are also addressing whether trace metal assemblages preserved in ancient seafloor deposits can be unambiguously classified as primary or secondary.

Objective 4

Using trace metal data in sulfides from Objective 2, we are testing whether we can quantify total critical and trace metal fluxes at mid-ocean ridges. Knowledge of metal thermodynamics and concomitant changes with known major elements (e.g. copper, iron, zinc and lead) previously analyzed in hydrothermal vent fluids may allow the first estimation for multiple critical and trace metals in subseafloor mid-ocean ridge hydrothermal fluids. Direct measurement of the trace metal contents of hydrothermal fluids in the subseafloor at mid-ocean ridges is not possible and to groundtruth our calculations, a proxy for mid-ocean ridge type hydrothermal fluids is needed. We have a unique sample suite of both fluid and sulfide samples from >2 kilometers depth in the active seawater-dominated geothermal system on the Reykjanes Peninsula of Iceland. These samples contain unexpectedly high concentrations of most trace metals (e.g. Hannington et al., 2016) and may reflect an original end member composition of mid-ocean ridge hydrothermal fluids. We aim to compare the estimated contents of trace metals in hydrothermal fluids at TAG to the Reykjanes hydrothermal fluids and sulfide scales directly precipitated from the deep end-member hydrothermal fluids in the

Reykjanes system to investigate if our method of estimating parent hydrothermal fluid compositions from in-situ mineralogical analyzes is valid.

Preliminary Results

Objective 1

Significant concentrations of the critical metals gallium, germanium, antimony, and indium are present in global seafloor sulfide deposits. Tectonic setting is a primary control on the distribution of critical metals in the deposits and reflects a combination of diverse host rock lithologies, spreading rates, magma supply, crustal thickness, magma composition and volatile inputs (Monecke et al., 2016). However, critical metal enrichment can also vary significantly within the same area. On a deposit-scale, the temperature of sulfide formation dictates the distribution of the critical metals, but differences between neighbouring deposits likely reflect other variables.

Objective 2

An element balance for TAG from LA-ICP-MS data shows the overall mineralogical residence for each trace element in the major minerals pyrite, marcasite, chalcopyrite and sphalerite (Fig. D4.2). Until now there was very limited information about the mineralogical sequestration of many non-sulfide forming critical and trace elements in subseafloor massive sulfide deposits. Our results show that there is significant abundance of the critical trace elements arsenic, cobalt, gallium, germanium, indium, and molybdenum within one or more sulfide phases in the TAG deposit. Detailed analysis of TAG sulfides indicate that the majority of metals are hosted in sulfides as either lattice-bound metals, as micro-inclusions of other minerals, or as by metal adsorption directly onto sulfides from the hydrothermal fluid. The co-enrichment of metals which commonly do not substitute into sulfide lattices, but also do not show irregular spikes in the raw LA-ICP-MS data also potentially indicates the presence of nanoparticles in TAG sulfides. To confirm the presence of nanoparticles and characterize micro-inclusions observed in TAG sulfides, high-resolution SEM imaging of selected samples is needed.

Objective 3

The refractory sulfide mineral pyrite is the most abundant sulfide in the TAG deposit and under certain conditions preserves the physio-chemical conditions at the time of deposition. Multiple generations of pyrite growth and associated thermodynamic constraints on trace metal contents can indicate changes in hydrothermal fluid evolution through time. In-situ LA-ICP-MS data under well constrained conditions indicates that the earliest TAG pyrites are enriched in higher-temperature affinity cobalt and selenium and later pyrite is deficient in metals of higher-temperature affinity, reflecting a general cooling trend for the deposit over time (Fig. D4.3). Compared to pyrite from other seafloor massive sulfide deposits, the TAG deposit is also deficient overall in the majority of trace metals; this does not reflect the composition of the primary hydrothermal fluid, but rather systematic secondary remobilization of trace elements out of pyrite (e.g. spot 10 in Fig. D4.3) in a mature, long-lived hydrothermal seafloor system.

Objective 4

Results are pending.

Outlook

- Comprehensive modelling of spatial and temporal metal distribution in the Reykjanes system
- Two more publications to be written on trace element behaviour

Networking

- Future Ocean Retreat, November 2017

Conferences

- Conference attendance at the Mineral Deposits and Studies Group (MDSG) in the United Kingdom, 3-5 January 2018, requested oral presentation of research
- Potential attendance at an international geoscience conference in 2018.

Publications

- **Grant, H.L.J.**, Hannington, M.D., Petersen, S., and Frische, M. (2017/8) Constraints on the behaviour of trace elements in volcanogenic massive sulfide deposits based in LA-ICP-MS data from the actively-forming TAG deposit, Mid-Atlantic Ridge. In advanced prep.
- **Grant, H.L.J.**, Hannington, M.D., and Petersen, S. (2018) Systematic trace element behaviour in actively-forming and ancient volcanogenic seafloor massive sulfide deposits. In prep.
- Previous: Monecke, T., Hannington, M.D., Petersen, S., **Grant, H.L.J.**, Samson, I. (2016) The Minor Element Endowment of Modern Sea-floor Massive Sulfides and Comparison with Deposits Hosted in Ancient Volcanic Successions. *Reviews in Economic Geology*, v. 18, pp. 245-306.

After end of funding

- Application made for post-parental leave top-up funding from GEOMAR (Inga-Lehmann-Fonds) to bridge the post-doc application period after the end of my Ph.D.

Other information

- I took full- and part-time parental leave from April 2016 to March 2017 and my remaining FO salary not used due to parental leave will be transferred to a GEOMAR account after 31st October 2017
- End date of project is now estimated for May 2017

References:

- European Commission, 2010. Report on Critical Raw Materials for the EU. Report of the Ad hoc Working Group on defining critical raw materials. European Union, Brussels.
- Hannington, M.D., et al., 2016. Gold enrichment in active geothermal systems by accumulating colloidal suspensions. *Nature Geoscience* 9, p. 299-302.

Figure Captions

Figure D4.1: Example LA-ICP-MS profiles using raw data for sulfides in the TAG deposit. Lines indicate count per second for each mineral. A) Ablation profile for pyrite (FeS_2) from 40.1 meters below the seafloor (mbsf). Lattice-hosted iron (Fe), copper (Cu) and silver (Ag) have smooth traces. An inclusion of sphalerite contributes zinc (Zn) and lead (Pb) to the overall element totals. B) Ablation profile for chalcopyrite (CuFeS_2) from 35.37 mbsf. Mineral lattice-hosted copper (Cu) and iron (Fe) have smooth traces and an inclusion of sphalerite adds zinc (Zn), lead (Pb), and minor indium (In).

Figure D4.2: Cumulative overall summary of the mineralogical residence of critical and trace elements analyzed by LA-ICP-MS for the major TAG sulfides pyrite (FeS_2), marcasite (FeS_2), chalcopyrite (CuFeS_2), sphalerite (ZnS) and lead (Pb) sulfides. Critical metals are in bold type and data is in %. For example, 48% of total germanium (Ge) in the TAG deposit is hosted within pyrite, 28% in chalcopyrite, and 24% in sphalerite.

Figure D4.3: Laser ablation ICP-MS transect showing changes in selected element concentrations across a zoned pyrite (FeS_2) with multiple episodes of growth from 78 mbsf. Red dots indicate location of analyses. The core of the pyrite grain (1) is assumed to be the youngest and (10) the youngest in the transect. Selenium (Se), cobalt (Co), and copper (Cu) are of higher-temperature provenance (Group II: $>\sim 250^\circ\text{C}$) and zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), and molybdenum (Mo) are of lower-temperature affinity (Group I: $<\sim 250^\circ\text{C}$). Transect is approximately 0.5 mm across. Spot 10 has a distinctly depleted trace metal signature compared to the rest of the transect.

Figure D4.1

Figure D4.2

Group II Pyrite

Group I Pyrite

Figure D4.3

